

**Exploring interactional competence in the Algerian Higher
Education context: Algerian EFL teachers' and learners'
perspectives and experiences under the spotlight**

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Thesis submitted in partial fulfilment of the requirements of the
University of the West of Scotland for the award of Doctor of
Philosophy

Declaration

I hereby certify that this thesis is my original work except for quotations and citations which have been duly acknowledged. I also declare that this thesis has not previously and is not being currently submitted for any other degree at the University of the West of Scotland or any other institution.

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Dedication

This work is dedicated to my wife, my soulmate and my partner in life,

Nana Ochiai

To the apple of my eye, my son Yassine

To my beloved mother Nadia Habib, and my father Rachid

To my father-in-law Keiichi, and mother-in-law Sachiko

To Mochi, and in the memory of Leo

To all family and friends

Acknowledgments

I would like to acknowledge my indebtedness and my infinite gratitude to who has been a mother, an advisor, a friend, a promotor before being a 'supervisor' Dr. Anne Pirrie for her continuous guidance, support, and patience throughout all stages of this work.

I would like to express my appreciations and sincere gratitude to my second supervisor Dr. Margaret Allan for her valuable comments, suggestions, and assistance for this humble work to come to light.

I am also grateful to the research participants who took part in this research, and to everyone who believed in me and my work.

Abstract

This study explored the notion of interactional competence (IC) in the Algerian higher education (HE) system by foregrounding Algerian EFL teachers' and learners' perspectives and experiences in the context of English as a Foreign Language (EFL). The notion of IC was considered in the light of the implementation of the most recent reforms called the LMD system. The study made use of semi-structured interviews and focus group interviews to explore teachers' and learners' beliefs and experiences with the notion of IC and to unearth the challenges they encounter in operationalising its performative elements in a particular HE institution. The findings established that the inadequate implementation of the LMD presents a challenge to the operationalisation of IC performative elements. Another impediment to the operationalisation of IC is the hierarchical power structure in the institution and teacher-student unequal power relations that are historically and socially constructed. The findings also revealed that the unequal power relations between teachers and students in the classroom nurtured students' passive behaviour and reinforced the maintenance of old teaching practices. This study made a genuine contribution to knowledge to the existing body of literature on teachers' beliefs and IC as it conceptualised the notion of IC through the lens of teachers' beliefs. The latter is a dimension that has been given a little attention in the existing research on the notion of IC. The contribution to knowledge also lies in the fact that the notion of IC was conceptualised in an under-studied context, that is, The Algerian context of Higher Education.

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Lists of abbreviations

CA	Conversation Analysis
CBET	Competency-based Education and Training
CBT	Competency-based Training
CBVE	Competency-based Vocation Education
CC	Communicative competence
CIC	Classroom Interactional Competence
CLT	Communicative Language Teaching
CPD	Continuous Professional Development
DT	Dialogic Teaching
EFL	English as a Foreign Language
HE	Higher Education
IC	Interactional Competence
IR	Interactional repertoire
IRF	Initiation Response and Feedback
FLA	First Language Acquisition
L1	First language
LAD	Language Acquisition Device
LMD	Licence-Master-Doctorate
MESRS	Ministry of Higher Education and Scientific Research
PBTE	Performance-based Teacher Education
PMP	Post-method pedagogy
PS	Pre-Service
PSI	Participant Information Sheet
SLA	Second Language Acquisition
CF	Consent Form

Chapter 1: Introduction

1.1 Setting the scene

The purpose of this small-scale qualitative study is to explore the notion of interactional competence (IC) in the context of higher education in Algeria. This is particularly important at a time when there is increasing emphasis at both national and institutional levels on developing competence in English as a Foreign Language (EFL) in the context of neoliberal agenda of higher education. In the neoliberal climate, EFL education became primarily driven by the neoliberal market principles and tightly associated with the notion of 'linguistic instrumentalism', that is, the development of the language skill results in social mobility, economic prosperity, and deals in competing in the global economy (Kubota, 2011). Such conception of EFL teaching and learning might lead to the suppression of aesthetic and cultural motivations for language learning (Ennser-Kananen et al., 2017, p.17)

The theoretical framework for this study revolves around the notion of IC, which foregrounds interaction from a constructivist standpoint. Interactional competence posits that spoken English is developed through dialogue between interlocutors, that is, teachers and learners (Kramsch, 1986; Walsh, 2013; 2011; Sun, 2014). The main focus of this study is to explore Algerian EFL teachers' and learners' pedagogical beliefs and experiences with the notion of IC and the implementation of its performative elements in a higher education institution in Algeria. Also central to this study are the micropolitical life of the classroom and the impact of power dynamics in an Algerian institution on the overall classroom interaction machinery, where power is regarded as an omnipresent and a continually exercised phenomenon (Foucault, 1980).

Discourse over the notion of IC started to gain attention by the turn of the 21st century, and it has been in the ascendancy ever since. The coinage of the term 'interactional competence' is often attributed to Kramsch's (1986) paper in the context of Second Language Acquisition (SLA). Kramsch (1986) critiqued the proficiency guidelines of the American Council of Teaching Foreign Languages (ACTFL), and she considered these guidelines as an oversimplified view of human interaction. Alternatively, she advocated the promotion of IC to give students 'a truly

emancipating second language education' (Kramersch, 1986, p. 370). Although the term IC occurred in many times in the paper, it had never been comprehensibly defined (Walsh, 2011; Hall, 2018). There have been various attempts to define the term IC. For example, building on Kramersch (1986) and other scholars, Walsh (2006) used the term IC to refer to 'teachers' and learners' ability to use interaction as a tool for mediating and assisting learning' (Walsh, 2011, p. 158; see also Walsh, 2006). One of the obstacles to providing a comprehensible definition to the term IC is attributed to fact that the term has versatile intellectual roots (Young, 2011; Hall, 2018).

The term IC has roots in the field of linguistic anthropology, and specifically, in Hymes' theory of communicative competence (CC) which occurred as a reaction to Chomsky's (1965) theory of linguistics competence (LC) in the field of modern languages (Hall, 2018). It also has roots in the sociological field of conversation analysis (CA) (ibid). Nevertheless, IC new insights in the landscape of SLA, such as the role of the sociocultural and institution environment in the development of competencies have their roots in Vygotsky's sociocultural theory (Johnson, 2008, p. 99). The intellectual roots of the notion of IC will be explored in detail in Chapter 3, Section 3.2. At this stage, it will be sufficient to note that in recent years, the emphasis has shifted from CC to IC (Sun, 2014; Kramersch, 1986; Walsh, 2012; Hall, 2018; Young, 2011).

The main reason for the shift from CC to IC is that CC is concerned with the individual performances and not what participants can achieve together within a communicative and interactional event (Walsh, 2012; Young, 2011; Hall, 2018). In contrast, IC considers the complexities of classroom interaction, which range from the roles of classroom participants, teaching methodologies, as well as teachers' expectations and goals. It maximises the learning space, that is, 'the extent to which teachers and learners provide interactional space that is appropriate for specific pedagogical goals of the moment' (Walsh, 2012, p.6).

Most second/foreign language studies that examined the notion of IC made use of conversational analysis (CA) research methodology. These studies were predicated on the view of language as a social accomplishment and viewed second language learners as capable interlocutor rather than deficient ones (Hall, 2018). Some of the

studies that stand out within this area of research are those by Walsh (2006, 2011, 2013), Donald (2015), who focused on the conceptualisation of IC in Taiwanese foreign language classrooms; and Tguchi (2015) whose focus was on developing IC in the context of Japanese students studying abroad.

Conversation analysis is a useful tool for analysing talk-in-interaction and how classroom participants deploy and develop their interactive skills such as turn-taking and topic management, clarification requests, repairs and so on. However, CA's attention to the external context of interaction, that is, the broader historical, cultural and political contexts, and its impact on the micro context of the interaction are limited (Strazny, 2011; Wooffitt, 2005; de Kok, 2008). In particular, teachers' beliefs about the notion IC and how these beliefs which are historically, socially and culturally constructed might affect the operationalisation of the performative elements of IC in their language classrooms has been given little attention in existing research on IC. This is in spite of the fact that teachers' beliefs influence teachers' pedagogical practices, and in the present case, IC is no different (Borg, 2003; Larenas et al., 2015; Braun, 2011; Kumaravadivelu, 2006). To address this gap in the literature, this research does not use conversational data and uses data gathered *in situ*, that is, in an Algerian HE institution. This includes data collected from interviews, which gives some insight into the perspectives of teachers and students on IC and their experiences with the notion, as well as the challenges they encounter in the implementation of its performative elements.

1.2 The importance of the study

This study is important as it particularly focuses on teachers' and learners' beliefs and experiences with the notion of IC in a particular institution located in a wider sociocultural context as demonstrated in Figure 1. Thus, more attention is given to the practitioners' views with a particular practice, IC in the present case. This is premised on the idea that teachers are active decision-makers and not 'mechanical implementers of external prescription' (Borg, 2015, p.8). Therefore, any teaching pedagogy must arise from the participants' classroom experiences and experimentation, and it should be congruent with their sociocultural context, rather than being informed by philosophies and theories that are usually developed outside the classroom context and give little attention to the classroom participants' lived

experiences and their sociocultural particularities (Kumaravadivelu, 1994; 2006). As it draws on teachers' beliefs in a particular context in relation to a specific practice, this study has the potential to inform policy, anticipate challenges of implementation of the notion IC in Algerian HE context, and help with the effective management of change (Bullock, 2011).

Teachers operate within a complex web of beliefs systems about learning, learners, and about themselves as teachers. The relationship between teachers' beliefs, practices, and the sociocultural context in which they operate is complex, as beliefs are socially and culturally constructed (Borg, 2006; 2018). This PhD study, in addition to conceptualising IC by casting light on teachers' perspectives, attempts to uncover teachers' shared perspectives, on the basis beliefs entail knowledge which constitutes shared beliefs in a community' (Nguyen, 2013, p. 17). The figure below represents the synopsis of the study. It shows the complexity and the interrelationships between the notion under investigation, that is, IC and the other elements of the study, namely teachers' and learners' beliefs and the institutional, and sociocultural context.

Figure 1.2: Scoping the area of inquiry

In addition, the importance of this study lies in the novelty of the context in which IC is being explored. The contribution to knowledge lies in the exploration of the notion of IC in an under-researched context with its unique political, social, economic and educational features, the Algerian higher education context. This study is governed by the belief that IC is not limited to the space and time of interaction but extends to the wider sociocultural context in which the interaction occurs (Young, 2011). The uniqueness of the Algerian sociocultural context will allow for a conceptualisation of IC that is particular to the Algerian higher education institution.

In respect of the context under study, that is, the Algerian higher education context, there are several factors that might have a direct bearing on the principal objective of this study, namely an investigation of teachers' and learners' beliefs and experiences with the notion of IC. First, questions have been raised about the quality of the Algerian higher educational system infrastructure, which is a three-cycle system referred to as Licence, Master, and Doctorate (LMD) (Mohammed, 2011). For the purpose of the present discussion, it will be sufficient to note that there are several contextual factors documented in the literature that might have an impact on teachers' and learners' classroom interaction experience. These include a lack of basic resources such as libraries; large class sizes; the predisposition of teachers to favour outdated methodologies in terms of didactics and their resistance to modify their beliefs and practices. These issues will be explored in more depth in Chapter 2.

Moreover, this study makes a contribution to knowledge in so far as the principles underpinning the notion of the IC which endorse cooperative achievements of goals and equality of roles (Walsh, 2012; Young, 2011; Hall, 2018). It is important to explore and echo these principles in our education settings in general, and in higher education settings, in particular, at a time where the so-called 'neoliberal university' and the market-driven model of education permeates educational fabric, and many educators are unhappy about the agenda's divisiveness for education (Connell, 2013). Although the impact of this agenda is widely spread across the world's higher education institutions, its impact in terms of speed and intensity differs from one context to another (Ball, 2016). In Algeria, for example, this is apparent in the implementation of the European version of the three-cycle system education reform known as Licence, Master, and Doctorate (LMD) as a 'ticket' to join the international

economic competition (Khelfaoui, 2009). The latter will be explored in more depth in the next chapter.

1.3 Aims and research questions

The aims of this qualitative research study are as follows:

- To develop a deeper understanding of IC, with specific reference to the Algerian higher education context.
- To explore Algerian EFL teachers' and learners' perspectives on the impact of power dynamics on classroom practice.
- To investigate Algerian EFL teachers' and learners' perceptions around the challenges of the performative elements of interactional competence.
- To explore how to improve IC in the light of teachers' and learners' perspectives.
- To make a contribution to knowledge on classroom discourse, particularly regarding the phenomenon of IC.

In pursuing these aims, the following research questions were addressed:

- What are teachers' and learners' perspectives, beliefs and experiences regarding interactional competence?
- What are Algerian EFL teachers' and learners' perspectives on the impact of power dynamics on classroom practice?
- What are Algerian EFL teachers' and learners' perceptions around the challenges of the performative elements of interactional competence?

1.4 Overview of the research approach

The investigation of teachers' beliefs and experiences with regard to IC was approached through conducting in-depth semi-structured interviews with 10 Algerian EFL teachers. These interviews were audio-recorded, transcribed, and analysed (see Chapter 4 for a full account of the methodology). Teachers' experiences with IC will be discussed at three main levels: their own educational experiences; experience with

schooling and instruction; and practical teaching experience (Richardson, 1996). O'Donnell et al. (2012, p. 36) summarise these three sources as the following:

- a) Personal experience: activities, events, and understandings that form part of the real world.
- b) Experience with schooling and instruction: the experiences teachers had when they were students.
- c) Experience with formal knowledge: knowledge gained from academic subjects and pedagogical knowledge gained from teacher education programs.

As the nature of interaction implies co-production (Allwright, 1984), IC entails co-construction and joint management of the spoken discourse that forms the basis of classroom talk. Thus, both parties' perceptions, that is, teachers and learners, are of paramount importance to develop a thorough understanding of the conceptualisation of the notion of IC in the context under study. However, the focus will be primarily placed on teachers' beliefs because teachers play a central role in the learning process as they are classroom discourse orchestrators (Yoon and Kim, 2012), topic managers, and turn-distributors in language classrooms (Walsh, 2006, 2011, 2013). It is the teachers' management of the learners' successful or unsuccessful management of the learners interaction through their talk that construct or obstruct learning opportunities in the classroom (Walsh, 2002; 2006). Nevertheless, the learners' views on IC and their perception of the contextual features as well as the quality of interaction taking place were also elicited. To achieve this, two groups of six and ten students, respectively, were selected and interviewed to enquire about their views on IC.

Prior to embarking on the fieldwork, the students' focus group topic guide was piloted with EFL Master students at the University of the West of Scotland to help eliminate ambiguity as much as possible, and to ensure that the questions were clear and comprehensible to the Algerian EFL students. In addition, five PhD students from Algeria who were also enrolled in the School of Education at the University of the West of Scotland were interviewed. The aim was to gain some insights into the challenges of collecting qualitative data not only in the researcher's country of origin but also in the HE institution where he had been a student for five years. The

researcher's positionality in this study is of a complex nature. A detailed account of the latter is provided in Chapter 4 section 4.6.1.

Finally, in addition to the objective stated above, this study aims at raising both Algerian EFL teachers' and learners' awareness of IC and assisting teachers and learners to derive the maximum benefit from their classroom interaction experience. It also aims at enhancing the quality of EFL teaching in the Algerian context, with a specific emphasis on developing teachers' interactional competence. The potential findings from the study might be relevant to similar contexts, especially where English is taught as a foreign language. As this study is qualitative in nature, the research findings cannot be generalised to other contexts. Therefore, it is up to the reader to decide whether the findings of this study are transferrable to his/her context (Korstjens and Moser, 2017).

1.5 Overview of the thesis

In addition to the introduction, this thesis comprises the following chapters:

Chapter 2 offers a detailed introduction to the context of the study. It outlines the key features of the Algerian higher education system, with due attention to the complex sociolinguistic situation in Algeria, specifically the lack of cultural and political plurality that is the legacy of colonialism. This chapter provides an overview of the main educational reforms that followed the colonial era and the conditions that accompanied their implementation. Rigorous attention will be given to the implementation of the most recent reforms, the LMD reforms.

Chapter 3 reviews the literature available on the notion of IC and its relationships with English language teaching methodologies with rigorous attention to the role teachers' beliefs play in this complex interplay.

Chapter 4 concerns the fieldwork of this PhD study and presents the research methodology, research paradigm, sampling procedure, ethical considerations, data collection challenges, data analysis, and researchers' positionality and reflexivity.

Chapter 5 presents and discusses the findings from the fieldwork. It explores Algerian EFL teachers' and learners' beliefs and experiences concerning the notion of IC.

Chapter 6 is an extension of chapter 5. The chapter presents and discusses teachers' and students' views on the nature of power dynamics in the institution and its impact on the operationalisation of the performative element of IC.

Chapter 7 states the main conclusions, provides recommendations, and points to future research directions.

Chapter 2: Overview of the Algerian Higher Education system

2.1 Introduction

Any attempt to elucidate the notion of interactional competence (IC) necessitates an overview of the education system within which the classrooms in question are located. This chapter, therefore, comprises an overview of the Algerian higher education (HE) system with particular focus on the features that impact upon regional and local understandings of the notion of IC in the context of the teaching and learning of English as a Foreign Language (EFL) in the Algerian context. This forms the conceptual backdrop against which the exploration of teachers' and learners' beliefs and experiences that is at the core of this thesis should be considered. Interactional competence is context-specific both at the micro-level (the classroom) and macro-level (the broader socio-cultural context). Therefore, an examination of beliefs and practices cannot be divorced from the socio-cultural context in which they are located (see Chapter 3).

Algeria is a country that is responding to the pressures of globalisation with its neoliberal tendencies and the concomitant advancement of the English language after 130 years of French colonialism (Idri, 2012; Sarnou et al., 2012). The response to the pressure of globalisation is another phase of development for the state of Algeria. In the light of Algerian overdependency on oil as the main source of its income, there is a consensus among the political elite that the investment in the promotion of English will not only bring peace to the complex linguistic and political situation in Algeria but will also help the country to retreat from the dependency on oil, and open its horizons to more versatile sources of income in a bid to develop a more flexible and resilient economy (Belmihoub, 2015; Coleman, 2010). Therefore, in Algeria, as elsewhere in north Africa, universities are increasingly becoming mobilised in the advancement of the knowledge economy, with the English language serving as key currency in the knowledge market. The British Council promotes the aforementioned agenda on the premise that 'English is critical for countries' successful 'participation' in the global economy' (Coleman, 2010, p.3). The participation in the global economy resulted in the state's struggle with a dual economic system which is composed of the remnants of socialism and an imposed free-market economy (Miliani, 2012, p. 68).

This dualism constitutes one of the main factors behind the fragile state of the Algerian economy.

As is the case in many other developing countries, Algeria faces considerable challenges in respect of quality assurance in the education sector. This is for several reasons, but primarily because the fragile state of the Algerian economy has had a notable impact on the fabric of the Algerian higher education system (Rose, 2015; Benziane, 2004). The Hydrocarbons industry owned by the state of Algeria dominates external trade at 95 per cent of foreign exchanged revenue, with a weak private sector that fails to deliver on the job market (Rose, 2015). The higher education system, in return, offers a little contribution to the job market, which is attributed to the mismatch between what the higher education system produces and what the market needs. All these factors have led to an increase in the rate of unemployment (Talbi, 2015). According to World Bank data retrieved in 2020, The current unemployment rate for ages 15-24 rests at 39.31 per cent and increasing. That said, the sociolinguistic situation of the context under study is also extremely complex and merits some elucidation. The latter will be explored in the next section.

This chapter proceeds by providing a brief overview of the linguistic complexity of the Algerian context, as this is the backdrop to the development of English as a key driver of the globalisation agenda. The chapter will then discuss the main education reforms. It also explores how globalisation and opening to the world's economy altered both the Algerian HE system and the Algerian sociolinguistic profiles. This chapter also encompasses a brief discussion of issues related to EFL teachers' training, 'massification' as well as autonomy. These issues and their implications for the overall quality of teaching and learning in the Algerian HE sectors will be introduced and explored in detail below.

2.2 The complexity of the Algerian sociolinguistic profile

Algeria is a multilingual country with a complex history, where successive invaders shaped its socio-cultural and sociolinguistics profile. People native to Northern Africa and particularly in Algeria are Berbers who came under the Phoenician subjugation. Following that, the Romans conquered Algeria, then the Roman Byzantines, the Ismallo-Arabo-Berbers, the Turks, and most recently the French, who

were the colonial rulers from 1830 until 1962. Among all the previously mentioned conquests, the ones that had a significant impact are the Arabs and the French (Benrabah, 2014).

The Arabic language entered North Africa as a result of Islamic expansion. The French language, on the other hand, was imposed by the French colonials through a policy commonly known as Frenchification (ibid). After independence, The Algerian government launched a counter policy referred to as Arabisation. As we shall explore in the next section, Frenchification and Arabisation, for the most part, account for the complex nature of the Algerian linguistic landscape and had a severe consequence on the Algerian education system. For now, attention will be directed to the exploration of the contemporary Algerian sociolinguistic profile.

The sociolinguistic profile of post-independent Algeria comprises five main languages which are in constant contact with one another (Benrabah, 2014). Hence, phenomena such as code-switching, code-mixing and bilingualism are common both at the social and classroom level (Chemami, 2011; Le Roux, 2017). First of all, there is the Algerian Arabic (AA, Derja) which is the mother tongue of the overwhelming majority of Algerians. With its regional varieties, AA is spoken by 70 to 80 per cent of the population. It is a mixture of Arabic, French, and Berber, and mostly used in day to day life and informal situations. Second, there is Modern Arabic which is constitutionally recognised as the official language of the country since 1962. It is mostly used in written form and formal contexts such as education and public administration. Next, there is Tamazight (Berber), a minority language spoken by 20 to 30 per cent of the population. The Algerian government had ignored Tamazight, and it was not recognised as a national language until 2002, and as an official language next to Arabic by a constitutional decree until 2016. Furthermore, there is French (the colonial language) which still maintains a significant presence and is widely used in public administration (Belmihoub 2012; Chemami, 2011). Finally, there is the English language that began to gain traction in the 1980s and 1990s as a result of the emerging agenda, and Algeria's extension of its economic market towards western countries such as the UK and USA (Kouicem, 2019).

In recent years, Algeria welcomed a newcomer to its linguistic landscape, the Chinese language. The entrance of the Chinese language into the Algerian linguistic landscape

is a good example of how economic power aids language spread (Benrabah, 2014). The Algerian linguistics landscape also encompassed other languages such as Russian, German, and Spanish. However, none of these languages was given the attention given to the English language (Belmihoub, 2012). The status of English in globalised Algeria will be discussed later in this chapter. For now, attention will be given to the two main language policies that had a significant impact on the Algerian linguistic profile, namely Frenchification and Arabisation.

2.3 Frenchification and Arabisation policy in Algeria

Language policy and planning in Algeria had always been bound up with power relations (Le roux, 2017). This is particularly noticeable in contexts where a foreign language is introduced through colonisation, and in the present case, the imposition of the French language in Algeria during the colonial period.

The French language has been a long-lasting legacy in the Algerian socio-cultural linguistic profile. During the French colonial period (1830-1962), the French imposed the French language in many areas of social and cultural life through a policy that became known as Frenchification (Benrabah, 2002, 2007). This policy led to segregation and illiteracy among the Algerians, but above all, the aim was to eradicate the Algerian identity by imposing a different cultural identity on Algerians. During this period, the French language became of the official language of the country, while the Arabic language and Tamazight had no official status and their usage was strictly prohibited. The French considered the Algerians to be inferior, uncivilised, and consequently gaining any form of acceptance by the colonialists meant learning how to speak and how to behave like a Frenchman (Maamri, 2009). Thus, in a sense, power lay in the mastery and use of the language of bearers of science, and the agents of civilisation, that is, the French colonial.

Several critics condemned the use of the colonial language as it was considered as a threat to one's nationalism and identity, and a form of betrayal. For example, Ngugi (1989), in *Decolonising the Mind*, argued that the imposition of the European languages on the African colonies is an attempt towards the annihilation of their local cultures. However, many Algerian writers, such as *Kateb Yacine* thought differently. For example, *Kateb Yacine*, as it was the case of many Algerian writers, writing and

expressing oneself in French was viewed as a form of power, and a powerful tool to reclaim the Algerian heritage and reinstate the Algerian identity (Maamri, 2009). In a way, these writers said in French no to being French. This is an example of the complex relationship between language and power. The same language that was imposed by the French colonial to advance their colonial agenda through attempting to eradicate the Algerian identity was viewed as a source of power, and a tool for resistance to reinstate this identity.

The impact of the Frenchification policy was most apparent in the education sector. Education was used as a tool for the Frenchification project (ibid). Pre-colonial education in Algeria consisted of a series of instructions in reading, writing, and arithmetic for children. For learners who wanted to continue their studies, they attended 'madras' or small universities located in urban cities. During the colonial period, this traditional system was replaced by the French schools (Brooks, 2016). As a result, the French language pervaded all walks of life. It was viewed as the language of modernity, and the language of science and technology. The latter, however, was not a popular view amongst Algerian nationalists who wanted to restore the status of the Arabic language.

Indeed, after 1962, the Algerian Government 'engaged' in a new language policy called Arabization. This policy aimed at reintroducing literary Arabic in education and administration as a means of reasserting an Algerian national identity. The Arabisation project gained ground with the coming of the president *Houari Boumediene* between 1965-1978. President Boumediene adopted a radical approach of Arabisation and aspired to make Classical Arabic the sole language in all Algerian life domains. This decision showed no consideration to the diversity of the Algerian linguistic profile. Scholars such as Benrabah (2010), Bekkai (2015), and Benmoussat (2015) contended that the Arabization policy was imposed for reasons of political expediency rather than on linguistic grounds. To legitimise the agenda of the imposition of the Arabic language, the regime manipulated the public through using their religious orientation, namely Islam, and promulgated Arabic as the language of Islam. Therefore, religion was the tool by which power and control were exercised in order to emotionally manipulate the Algerian public and to legitimise the Arabisation agenda. On the surface, it might appear that the goal of Arabization was to reinstate

the Algerian identity; however, it was nothing but an authoritarian top-to-bottom approach, which only led to a new type of alienation (Benrabah, 2004; 2010). If anything, Arabisation is more or less like Frenchification as both policies aimed at superseding the prevailing language and culture. Probably the only difference between the two language policies lies in the type of power used in its imposition (Le Roux, 2017). The French colonial used 'hard power', i.e. use of military force, whereas the Algerian state used 'soft power', i.e. manipulation of public (Daoudi, 2018). In a sense, it is fair to say that both policies could be considered as 'de-Algerianisation' policies (Benramdane, 2002).

There is a large consensus that the Arabization policy was flawed from the outset (Benrabah, 2002, 2010; Zoulikha, 2002). As stated above, the strategy was politically motivated and inextricably linked to the reassertion of Islam as a key element in a putative 'national' identity. The implications for education policy and practice were not considered at the time. At the heart of its failure, there were numerous factors. First, it was a hasty decision with little consideration of the prevailing socio-political climate in the country (Bekkai, 2015; Benmoussat, 2015). Second, during its implementation, many schools did not have a substitute for the existing French system, and this resulted in a lack of teaching materials (Bekkai, 2015).

Similarly, there was also a lack of qualified teachers, and the teachers who were in post were not prepared for this abrupt change in the system. This was the case of many schools in Algeria until the 1990s. However, the situation at the HE level was different, even during the colonial period. Classical Arabic was used in domains such as history, religion, politics, and literature, while the French language was used for science and technology studies (Benrabah, 2014). As some researchers addressed the failure of the Arabization policy to replace the French language, Buitendijk (1977) reports on discoveries made by North African researchers concluding that the status of French in the three African countries, i.e., Algeria, Morocco, and Tunisia, declined as a result of Arabization.

In light of the diversity of socio-cultural reasons that led to the failure of the Arabization policy, there were also political reasons. Most prominent of these is the transition of the Algerian government from a single to a multiparty system of government. The new Algeria was now ready for a bilingual educational system.

Consequently, in the early 2000s, the state declared the implementation of a bilingual educational system where French and Arabic were taught side-by-side starting from the primary level (Nadia, 2011; Benrabah, 2014). At the same time as Arabization started to dominate the Algerian education system, English was also in the ascendant as a global language. Eventually, the Arabization policy failed due to the pressures of globalisation, which brought about diversified world economy, expansion of telecommunication and media (Benrabah, 2014, p. 50). The next section explores the role of globalisation in the spread of the English language in Algeria in more detail.

2.4 Globalisation and spread of English in Algeria

In the late 1980s and the early 1990s, discourse on the eventual success of the English language over French in North-African countries, particularly in Algeria, grew substantially. Academics such as David Crystal pointed out the spread of English in countries that had formerly been French colonies: ‘In 1996, for example, English replaced French as the chief foreign language in schools in Algeria’ (Crystal, 2003, p.5). The use of the English language as a communication vehicle started to gain traction within a globalised Algeria between 1980 and 1990 when Algeria became more liberal both politically and economically. As a result, Algeria became more open towards world markets, especially towards the UK and the US. Besides, the Algerian government’s welcoming of foreign investments in oil and gas resulted in an increased requirement for English teaching and usage (Mami, 2013; Bellalem 2012).

The Algerian state’s openness to the world economy was the main reason for the introduction of the English language into the system. Crystal (2003, p.9) argued that ‘a language becomes an international language for one chief reason: the political power of its people, especially their military power.’ In addition to this, Graddol (1997, p. 9) indicated that ‘any substantial shift in the role of the US in the world is likely to have an impact on the use and attractiveness of the English language amongst those for whom it is not a first language.’ The aforementioned quotation illustrates that the political and economic power of a particular country, the US in this case, promotes the spread of its national languages. The English language had a special status in the Algerian context. In light of the importance of the English language in today’s global economy, the Algerian government devoted a considerable effort to

promote the English language in the context. The promotion of the English language renewed the hopes of the Algerian state to suppress the use of French. Accordingly, English was first introduced in the eighth grade of middle schools (end of the 1970s and early 1990s). In 1993, it was introduced from the fourth grade of primary education as a competitor to the French language (Benrabah, 2007; Benrabah, 2014; Chemami, 2011; Nadia, 2011). Pupils were very motivated to learn English, as teachers from Pakistan, India and the UK were employed. The involvement of native speakers during this period resulted in the students having an acceptable if not an excellent level in the English language (Bouhadiba, 2006). At that time, another reason for the success of learners can be attributed to the fact that learning the language was not only driven by vocational purposes, but also by the curiosity to learn the culture. To promote the use of the English language, the state also created a programme to train Algerian teachers, especially in the UK. Nevertheless, the program failed as a result of the decrease in the price of oil in the 1980s (ibid).

Despite the efforts of the state to promote the English language, French continued to hold its own (Benrabah, 2014; Le Roux, 2017). It should be noted that the introduction of the English language in Algeria was and still is being hampered by its co-existence with the French language. The introduction of the English language revived the hope of the state to inhibit the use of French, as already mentioned, however, this seems very problematic considering the multilingualism of the society. Benrabah (2014) argued that along with the aforementioned reason, the elites have also been active agents in the maintenance of French. Once again, the introduction of the English language at the primary level, as was the case with the implementation of the Arabization policy, the attitudes, sentiments and cultural realities of the Algerian people were disregarded. The latter is a prime example of an authoritarian, antidemocratic top-down approach to education reforms, which might be considered as a revival of the linguistic oppression that the Algerians experienced during the colonial period. Therefore, as Benrabah (2014, p.51) also maintained, for ordinary people, the introduction of English language in the primary school level was considered as another attempt by those who are in power ‘to deny them the right to access “modernity” via the language of economic power.’ Arabization is still growing at a large scale, particularly in Algeria (Nadia, 2011). The use of Arabic in both primary and secondary education meant that there were few hours available for

foreign languages, French and English (ibid). Today French is taught beginning from second-year primary level, while the English language is taught as second foreign language beginning from 6th grade. The competition between the two is still ongoing until the present day. Despite this competition, Benrabah (2014) pointed out that there are still hopes for the English language to supplant French in educational contexts. Particularly In HE, there are roughly equal numbers of students enrolled in English and French departments. For example, statistics from two of the main universities in the west of Algeria between 2010 and 2011, the University of Oran and University of Mascara respectively, as well as statistics from the HE institution included in the empirical part of this PhD study in the east of the country, are a good indicator that the English language is close on the heels of French (Benrabah, 2013).

Foucault (1980; 1982; 1984) reminds us that power relations are very complex, and such complexity can be demonstrated in the light of discussing the conflict between French and English and its impact on society and education. The conflict between the French and English language might seem like a conflict between two languages, but in reality, it is not. It is a representation of a conflict between two powers, the French colonial residual power represented in the continued and large use of French in The Algerian territory, and the neo-imperial and neoliberal power where English is used an instrument to further the neoliberal agenda (Phillipson, 2008). The latter is evident in the escalation of discourse about replacing French with English in Algeria. In recent events, the Algerian higher education minister *Tayeb Bouzid* declared that ‘the French language does not get us anywhere’ and ordered Algerian Universities to use English instead of French. It seems like ‘we’ are stuck in the vicious circle of Frenchification and Arabisation. The Arabic language, which probably could serve as a medium of modernity, is being sabotaged from being so because ‘it serves as a highly charged religious symbol’ (Maamri, 2009). A recent video of an Arabic teacher in one of the Algerian primary schools pervaded social media, which ultimately attracted the attention of the ministry of education. The teacher appeared in the video speaking classical Arabic with the students behind her repeating after her that ‘*Arabic is the most beautiful language, this year my language will be Arabic, and that we won’t speak any language but the Arabic.*’ The video was discussed over a press conference, where the minister of education *Nouria Benghabrit* described the situation as ‘a complete disaster’ and ordered to investigate the matter. The video,

although short, represents the conflict between two ideological powers, the nationalist ideologies who envision the Arabic language tied to Islam, and the neoliberal ideology that rejects the nationalist and argues for an Arabic education model that promotes creativity, individuality, and success on international measures of learning (Smail, 2018). Thus, it is very apparent that the Algerian society did not witness a ‘linguistic stability’ since the colonial era. One could argue that the current Algerian society is ‘linguistically dispersed’, and that today’s generation might be referred to as ‘triangle illiterates’ (Maamri, 2009). The previous discourse is also another layer of power that implicitly advocates the idea of a monolingual Algeria.

Globalisation did not only alter the sociolinguistic profile of Algeria. The impact of this phenomenon is also evident in the reforms that took place in the HE sector in 2003. This reform constituted replacing the old classical system with the new system called the Licence, Master and Doctorate (LMD), and which will be discussed in more detail in this section. The system came into being in response to the Bologna process in the wake of the signing of the Bologna Declaration in the year 1999. The aim of the Bologna process was the harmonisation of the HE system across the European Union. The Algerian government targeted the same objective to bring its education system into line with the European one. Nonetheless, the introduction of this system came with its challenges, mostly because of its incompatibility with the national and regional socio-cultural context (Azzi, 2012; Guendouzi and Ameziane, 2011; Kelfaoui, 2009; Ghemmour and Sarnou, 2016). These contextual factors have a direct bearing on the principal objective of this study, namely an investigation of teachers’ and learners’ perspectives on classroom interactional competence. It is important to recognise that a range of extraneous contextual factors influence practice in the classroom. The contemporary state of the Algerian HE system will be discussed in-depth in the following section.

2.5 The impact of neoliberal globalisation on the Algerian HE system

Algeria is responding to current changes taking place in the globalised neoliberal world, and particularly in the sector of higher education. This section explores the impact of the neoliberal agenda on the Algerian HE system, namely the introduction of the LMD system reforms, also known as the Bologna Process (BP).

The Algerian higher education system witnessed various reforms most recent of which was the LMD system reform. The introduction of the latter was an inevitable response to the modernising imperative in the context of the Algerian education system. For example, Idri (2005, p.1) has pointed out: ‘the application of the LMD system in Algeria is considered as a step towards globalisation because this Anglo-Saxon programme has proved its success.’ The state’s application of the LMD system might be a good initiative to seek conformity with the European and American higher education standards to catch up with the global economy (Djamàa, 2013). However, its success in Europe or elsewhere does not necessarily mean that the system will be successful in the Algeria. Most recent literature questioned the compatibility of the system, where several issues relating to the insufficiency of human and material resources were addressed among other challenges (Guendouzi and Ameziane, 2011; Kelfaoui, 2009; Ghemmour and Sarnou, 2016; Metatla, 2016).

The introduction of the LMD into North African countries Morocco, Algeria, and Tunisia was officially discussed in a conference which was held in November 2004 in Marseille, France under the theme ‘Higher education reforms in the Maghreb countries and the prospect of the Bologna process’ (Eta and Mngo, 2020, p.10). The conference was co-organised by the Agency Universitaire da la Francophonie (AUF), and la Conference des Presidents D’Université-France (CPU). The fact that the conference was held in France and accompanied the involvement of an agency like the CPU is suggestive of the significant role France played in the transfer of the LMD system into Algeria and other Maghreb countries (Ibid). The naming of the system, that is, LMD, has also played a role in the promotion of the system in French African speaking countries. Initially, the system was named BP; however, the name LMD was used in French African countries so as not to stir up the opinion of nationalist individuals and politicians in Algeria who are against anything that is French due to the colonial history (Boufeldja, 2013, also cited in Eta and Mngo, 2020). There is also the possibility that the name LMD was adopted instead of BP because preserving the same name is suggestive of the blind emulation and political conformity (Khelfaoui, 2009, also cited in Eta and Mngo, 2020). There is also a consensus in the literature that argued that the LMD system implemented in Africa is not the same version that was implemented in other European countries. Instead, it is an assimilated version of the French LMD system (Croché and Charlier, 2012).

One of the main objectives of the LMD reform in the Algerian higher education landscape was to remediate some of the issues that characterised the classical (old) system. This included a large number of students with a low attendance rate, a high-rate dropout rate, and the mismatch between university graduates and the market demands (Mohammed and Brahim, 2010). Therefore, the LMD is different from the classical system in both structural and organisational components, as well as pedagogy. From the structural aspect, the LMD system is a semester-based system, unlike the old system, which is a yearly formation system. The LMD system comprises three main teaching units; fundamental, methodological and discovery. Each unit comprises a series of modules and assigned a number of credits which are creditable and transferable (Labeled, 2007, as cited in Mohammed and Brahim, 2010). From the pedagogical aspect, the system fosters learners' autonomy and reduces teachers' role into facilitators of learning (Idri, 2005; Djamàa, 2013).

In line with the neoliberal requirements in the sector of HE, Algeria employed a quality assurance (QA) system to ensure the proper implementation of the LMD. QA system is important to the alignment of degrees, to allow for student mobility, as well as to cope with the global academic environment. To allow for students' mobility, it is not sufficient for Algerian institutions to meet European and American standards only by implementing the LMD system. A certain system had to be in place to assure the quality of higher education through normative regulatory instruments such as transparency, accountability and trustworthiness. Foucault (1982, p.218) referred to systems as such as 'regulated concerted systems'. The normative regulatory mechanisms are not simply administrative procedures. Rather, they are 'mechanism of political power, a projection of interests, and an attempt to control' (Jarvis, 2014, p. 156; Foucault; 1977; Foucault, 2007). The implantation of the QA system is a good example of power in action, where the QA serves as an instrument of surveillance to ensure institutional compliance to protect the market's interests (Jarvis, 2014; Raaper and Olssen, 2016).

The QA system was implemented by CIAQUES (a committee for the implementation of quality assurance in higher education), which was created by MESRS in 2010. The QA system aims at assuring the quality of higher education at the internal and external level. Internal quality assurance refers to higher education institutions

engagements in self-evaluation processes. To do this, Algeria joined a European project called AqiUMed (Reinforcement of internal quality assurance in Mediterranean universities). The AqiUMed project is funded by the European Commission, and involves three European Union state members; Belgium, France, and Spain, and ten Mediterranean universities with ten ministries of higher education as associate partners. The project also encompasses 2 European agencies for external evaluation (Saadi, 2019). Particularly, the QA system consists of the LMD training package, the national qualifications framework, the quality assurance system, the quality assurance frame of reference, the national standards, and the key performance indicators (Miliani, 2013). Despite the state's effort to develop a QA system that is reliable, the path towards the achievement of such a system is fraught with many challenges. The main issue lies in the partial dependence on the mechanisms of the system, and in the delay in selecting key bodies with an effective role which only were assigned in May 2015 (Benaissa, 2017).

One of the main reasons that hampered the successful implementation or the successful imitation of the European version of the LMD is the fact the system was not preceded by a rigorous and robust evaluation of the state of HE in Algeria. Nor was there adequate consideration of the realities of regional and national context (Matatla, 2016; Khelfaoui, 2009). It is important to note that the LMD was piloted in Algeria in the academic year of 2003-2004. The piloting phase had also been preceded by a year which comprised a series of negotiation tables and seminars to ensure the success of the piloting phase (Idri, 2005). One of the main issues of the piloting phase was that these meetings and seminars, which involved teachers of higher education, focused mainly on the structural and organisational component of the LMD system rather than its core pedagogical canons (Idri, 2005).

Most recent literature on the level of implementation of the LMD reforms further argued that the structural and organisational aspect of the LMD system took the lion's share of the implementation process (Kelfaoui, 2009; Djamàa, 2013; Woldegiorgis, 2018). In this respect, Woldegiorgis (2018, p. 48) argued that 'it is the content of the Bologna policy that travelled to Africa, not the practical implementation of its components'. The content of the BP primarily includes the three-cycles LMD, the European Credit Transfer System (ECTS), and mobility (Eta and Mngo, 2020).

Regardless, the system witnessed resistance from many higher education institutions because of the insufficiency of human and material resources noted above (Idri, 2005; Kelfaoui, 2009). The institution under study was one of the institutions that resisted the LMD reforms (see Chapter 6, Section 6.2). The workforce resistance to the LMD reforms is unsurprising given the LMD system, like previous educational reforms, was imposed upon the workforce (Kelfaoui, 2009). Foucault (1978) long pointed out that ‘Where there is power, there is resistance’.

Over a decade since the introduction of the LMD system, the efficiency of the system is still being evaluated, and the results are not encouraging (Aps.dz, 2015; Ghemmour and Sarnou, 2016; Metatla, 2016). This may be attributable to the fact that the system has been imported into a different context rather than explicitly developed for the Algerian context. Semmouk (2005, p. 129) argued that it is the imitation and naïve transmission of western societies reforms that hampered the successful implementation of educational reforms in Algeria. In addition, the right conditions for successful imitation were not available. Poor infrastructure, in terms of library facilities and other key resources, compromised the successful implementation of the system. From the outset, the implementation of the LMD was riven by internal fundamental contradictions (Kelfaoui, 2009; Ghemmour and Sarnou, 2016; Metatla, 2016). These contradictions have been brought about by the inevitable emphasis on modernisation and development along the lines of the western model. Among these contradictions, the implementation of the LMD system disregarded the very fundamentals of the BP (Kelfaoui, 2009; Boufeldja, 2013). The implementation of the degree structure is in line with BP; however, the procedures by which universities and institutions are managed are not compliant with BP. For example, Universities Rectors, Deans, and Heads of Departments are still appointed and not elected. Besides, the majority of appointed university leaders lack the managerial skill and educational competences (Boufeldja, 2013, p. 272).

Another factor that has hindered the harmonious development of the LMD system is its co-existence with the classical system. This co-existence has created some friction between graduates and even amongst students regarding the value of the university degree and concerns about the impact of degree type on future career opportunities and prospects. This is also an area in the implementation of the LMD system where

power was misused in the sense that it had created inequality between graduates' degrees. It transpired that the transition arrangements from one system to the other were inadequate, that is, there was no clear vision of how the LMD would succeed the previous system. Nor was there adequate provision for the co-existence of the two

Infrastructural constraints were not the only impediments to the successful implementation of the LMD system. The level of preparedness of the academic staff was a contributing factor in the limited success of the LMD system. Due to the high demand for teachers, teacher selection procedures were considered poor in comparison to other Maghreb countries (Lamine, 2010). This had implications for both pedagogy and the successful implementation of the system. The newly recruited teachers lacked proficiency in certain key areas and did not benefit from the supervision of more experienced colleagues. Most newly qualified teachers only had a Magister degree, since they all graduated from the old system (Mohammed, 2011, p. 535). According to Mohammed and Brahim (2010), in order to implement the LMD system more successfully, attention should be paid to pedagogy as well as to the accountability of professors and managers. He further argues, 'when speaking about the LMD system, that problem (sic) related to professors remain the focus of this reform, and success or failure can be determined through it, to a large extent.' (Mohammed and Brahim, 2010, p. 278).

The lack of qualified teachers due to inadequate selection procedures within HE has had a detrimental effect on the sector as a whole, with teachers relying heavily on outdated practices and reluctant to embrace new approaches, with a concomitant over-reliance on established routines (Lamine, 2010; Mohammed, 2011). Correspondingly, teachers' inclination towards the old teaching methodologies, old beliefs and practices create the impression that the majority of staff in HE institutions had become accustomed to undertaking tasks concerning particular customs and routines. This situation is not limited to the context of higher education but also includes the sector of education as a whole. For example, at the middle school level Benadla (2013, p. 162) pointed out,

...the former teaching methods are deeply rooted in the teachers' subconscious and still affect their way of teaching. What clouds further the issue is that

many teachers find themselves shifting to the previous way of teaching in which they feel 'safer' during their lesson.

It is worth noting that Benadla (2013) criticised EFL teachers' use of the old methods in relation to the implementation of the Competency-Based Approach (CBA) reform and not the LMD reform. Nevertheless, the critique is still valid in a discussion of the LMD system because both reforms are premised on the same philosophy, that is the decentralisation of teachers and reducing their role into facilitators, and the promotion of learners' autonomy (Idri, 2012). CBA was introduced by means of ministerial instructions as a replacement for the existing communicative approach in the same year in which the LMD system was piloted, that is 2003-2004 (Bouhadiba, 2015; Idri, 2012). It is evident that the implementation of CBA followed the same top-down approach to educational reform since the Arabisation era; that is, power was exercised without the consultation of teachers. Predictably, the shift did not consider the educational and cultural environment as both teachers and pupils were not prepared (Ibid). This has resulted in the teachers' resistance to the reform, and in their persistence to use old teaching methods, namely the transmission model of education (Miliani, 2012; Bouhadiba, 2015). For example, Bouhadiba (2015, p.11) argued that the theoretical principles underpinning CBA reform were completely ignored and teachers are still the centre of the teaching and learning process with their old teaching methods and authoritarian behaviour, and learning is still based on memorisation and recitation.

EFL teachers' use of old-fashioned methodologies seems to be a common phenomenon in the Algeria sector of education. From the perspective of this study, it is imperative to explore teachers' use of old-fashioned methods in more detail, and more importantly, to explore their impact on the micropolitical life of Algerian EFL classrooms. In the present discussion, old-fashioned methodologies refer to the use of methods such as grammar-translation method (GTM), audiolingual method (ALM), which we will explore in more detail in the next chapter, or generally the use of methods that are based on the transmission model of teaching or spoon-feeding as Benadla (2013) preferred to call it. Spoon-feeding is a form of education where knowledge is perceived as tangible, permanent, and transferrable from a well-

informed individual to a less informed one (Raelin, 2009). It has a negative impact on students' critical thinking as it forces them to rote learn (McKay and Kember, 1997). In the Algerian education context, the use of these 'traditional' teaching methods is further anchored with 'the teaching with objectives', which heavily relies on teaching units being accomplished within a particular time-frame. Therefore, learners' achievements and their linguistic and communicative competencies are ignored and marginalised in the process (Benadla, 2013, p. 158; Hadjeris, 2019). The use of old-fashioned methods is a threat to the quality of EFL teaching and learning for they discount the communicative and social nature of language classrooms. Thus, the learners' role in the classroom is neutralised, and their autonomy becomes obstructed (Bouhadiba, 2006; Benadla, 2013).

The notion of 'spoon-feeding', that is, the transmission model of teaching is inherited in the Islamic way of teaching, where the teacher is considered as the only provider of knowledge, and where learning is primarily based on memorisation and recitation of Koranic text in Masjid or Madrasa (Miliani, 2012; Miliani, 2017; Choubane, 2019). Thus, with reference to Benadla's (2013, p.162) quotation above, one might argue that the problem of teachers' inclination towards former teaching methods is not only deeply rooted in teachers' subconscious, but also rooted in abrupt and not a well thought of language policies. In particular, the policy of Arabisation that we discussed previously is relevant in the current discussion of the notion of spoon-feeding. Spoon-feeding denotes the existence of power inequality in the classroom, where the teacher controls all aspect of the teaching process with little to no involvement on the part of the learner. As mentioned earlier, before the French invasion, the Algerian educational system comprised a series of instructions that were rooted in Islamic teaching tradition. In Islam, the teacher is the 'Cheikh', meaning the one who is unchallengeable all-knowing, unlike the western pedagogy which conceptualises teachers as facilitators. During the colonial period, the French system replaced the Islamic way of teaching. However, after the independence of the country, the Arabisation policy was imposed, which consequently led to the revival of the old teaching methods due to the interrelatedness between Islam and the Arabic language. Thus, teachers who are conservatives consider themselves as the only provider of knowledge (Choubane, 2019; Miliani, 2012). This presents a major challenge to the idea of promoting learners' autonomy in the Algerian context for it is highly likely

that learners are brought up in the idea of over-dependence on teachers (Choubane, 2019).

In the above quotation, Benadla (2013) did not only refer to the use of former teaching methods but also the teachers' shift to them. This suggests the presence of a clash between traditional pedagogies and western pedagogies, a clash of power, as it were. Particularly, with the introduction of the LMD system, which is also based on western pedagogy, teachers were unable to cope with the clash, or a dilemma between two pedagogies, i.e., one which is acquired through their own educational experiences and one that is theoretical and systematic (Miliani, 2012). The existence of such clash might affect power relations in education institutions, and impact teacher-teacher and teacher-student relationships. Teachers who are adopting new socio-constructivist and current teaching approaches might be viewed as modern while the others who are confirming to the traditional way of teaching might be viewed as outdated. Thus, the transfer of western pedagogical ideologies willy-nilly into a Muslim country like Algeria is a threat to the culture and might create more pedagogical issues than it resolves (Miliani, 2012). For example, the fact that the LMD system promotes learners' autonomy is threatening to the power of teachers who implement a transmission model of teaching (Choubane, 2019, Missoum, 2015). In a sense, learners' autonomy in Algeria constitutes a threat to the educational culture. Benadla (2013) in her conclusion where she built on the work of the Algerian sociologist Semmouk (2005), clearly indicated that students' lack of autonomy is also the product of the authoritarian nature of the Algerian family, wherein parents' orders must be obeyed without questioning. Semmouk (2005, p.129) emphasised the importance of the role of the family, and society in general in the successful implementation of educational reforms. He argued that it is anti-logical to separate educational reforms from the reality of the Algerian society, where authority is built upon an unjust and undemocratic basis and this constitutes a real obstacle to reform experiments.

What is more important to the object of this study is the impact of the transmission model of education on the micropolitics of Algerian EFL classrooms. According to a study conducted by Miliani (2017) to explore the power dynamics in EFL classroom in the university of Oran, teachers' use of the transmission model was pervasive in the university context. Miliani (2017) argued that the power structure in Algerian

university classrooms is hierarchical, with the teacher being at the top, which is the result of teachers' contact with the Islamic pedagogy, as well as their experience as teachers and learners in an educational system pervaded with such hierarchical conception of power. Miliani (2017, p.6) argued that teachers' authority is domineering in the context, to the extent that students' voices are often marginalised, except for student associations which resist teachers' authority through imposing their own agenda to bring a temporary balance of some sort. The findings of the study also revealed that teachers' authority is evident in teachers use of language in the classroom where 25/28 students considered teachers' way of addressing them is making them feel weak and ignorant. Belittling the students and their abilities is the result of power imbalance. Teachers use of debasing language might have a negative impact on teacher-student relationships. Students might develop a sense of resentment to teachers, and this has a serious implication on learning.

In conclusion, despite the slogans of learner-centred methods, active methodologies, CBA, and LMD, the transmission model of teaching, teacher-centred, and content-based approaches prevail. This is a brief overview of the background to the proposed study of the nature of interactional competence. However, there are also issues regarding teachers' training and readiness for the reception and the implementation of the LMD system in the Algerian HE system, and it is to these that we now turn our attention.

2.6 EFL teacher training in Algerian higher education

Being prompted about what has been mentioned in the literature regarding the level of preparedness of teachers, dedicating a section to investigate the effectiveness of teacher training in Algeria is of great significance to have a good understanding of HE education state in Algeria and to uncover factors that would affect classroom practices. This is despite the fact that teacher education courses have reportedly been described as unhelpful and a waste of time (Benson and Riches, 2009, Zaslavsky and Sullivan, 2011), as being unable to change teachers' practices. However, these courses can be an influential source on the practices that take place in classrooms (Tsui, 2003).

For starters, one cannot overlook that the task of non-native-speaking (NNS) teachers of English is much more challenging than that of native-speaking (NS) teachers. It is crucial for NNS Teachers to communicate in English in a bid to expose learners to the target language and to afford them with opportunities to practise their spoken and written communication. NS teachers, in most cases, are more fluent and intuitive in their language use than NNS teachers. Few decades ago, and probably still the case in some contexts, NS teachers were considered superior to NNS ones, experienced or non-experienced, just by virtue of being native speakers (Doerr, 2009; Sung, 2010). This ideology of the power NS hold because they are native speakers is referred to as ‘the dominance approach’ to ‘nativeness’, as opposed to ‘the difference approach’, where NNS teachers are viewed as ‘linguistically handicapped’ (Medgyes, 1994). Such a conception of NNS teachers affects both teachers’ self-image and teaching attitudes. For example, teachers do not aspire to develop themselves as they think they will never be able to reach NS proficiency (Medgyes, 1992). It also affects EFL learners’ views of their teachers. For example, EFL learners might think that their teachers need to improve their linguistic proficiency, improve their pronunciation, and developed more engaging and wide ranged materials (Sung, 2010).

The ideology of inequality between NS and NNS teachers was scrutinised in 1990, especially on the field of TESOL (Teaching English to Speakers of Other Languages). Arguably, the naming of the profession already conveys the idea of asymmetry in natives and non-natives relationships by assigning *Self-Other* dichotomous subject positions to teacher and learner. It positions ‘Anglo-teacher as self and position the learner in a life trajectory forever being *Other*’ (Lin and Luke, 2006, p. 67). Nevertheless, discourse within the field of TESOL attempted to bring equality between NS and NNS teachers and promote diversity within professional settings. This was evident in the introduction of the difference approach (Brutt-Griffler and Samimy, 1999; Nemtchinova, 2005; Doerr, 2009) which views NNS as different rather than inferior to NS teachers though acknowledging NNS teachers’ attributes. NNS teachers were found to be a good learner model, more empathic than NNS, and understanding of the challenges EFL learners face. However, despite the introduction of the ‘difference approach’ as a form of resistance against the discourse that promotes the dominance approach, power relations between NNS and NS remain intact (Doerr, 2009).

In the Arab world in general, EFL teaching programs seem to struggle in terms of delivery. For example, Fareh (2010) conducted a study to uncover the challenges that EFL teachers encounter in Arab countries thorough asking a daring question; why do EFL programs do not deliver as expected? The findings from this study revealed that challenges encompassed the inadequacy of the adopted teaching methodologies, the fact that EFL teaching is teacher-centred, the examination system is based on rote learning; and there is a lack of emphasis on developing the learners' language skills. In addition, many teachers claim that students are unable to think, uneducable and incapacitated (ibid.). This implies that teachers are not taking initiatives to improve their proficiency and that, further, they are not aware of their responsibilities towards teaching.

It is common that the promotion of teacher quality is a linchpin in the progress and improvement of HE and any education system in general. Teacher training, by definition, refers to the professional preparation of teachers that includes all the aspects that assist teachers to develop their skills. Primarily, it should prioritise classroom practice and teachers' practical efforts to develop and empower the inner abilities of learners which is the primary aim of education, whether it be in foreign language learning or another subject (Zouaozi, 2015, p. 186). However, in Algeria, due to the absence of specialised institutions to train teachers, the task of teaching has become a challenging one for HE teachers. Zouaozi (2015) argued that in the light of the absence of these institutions, teachers refer to their own experience as a strategy of self-improvement. The situation tends to be more severe than this in the sense that many teachers teach the same way as they were taught.

In Algeria, prior to 2000, there were two types of teacher training courses. The management of these courses was sponsored by two bodies: at the university level by the ministry of HE and research, and by the ministry of the education for secondary school teachers (PES) and middle school teachers (PEF). The old training system emphasised quantity over quality. With the new education reform, the teacher training system has become more qualitatively oriented. The latter was devised in order to resolve some of the challenges presented by the old training system (Bellalem, 2008, p.63). In light of the new education reform, the ministry of national education stated that:

Training is a continuous process for all educators at all levels, and its purpose is to allow the participants to gain professional knowledge and to enhance competence, culture, and awareness about the mission that educators are set to accomplish.
[Translated from Arabic]

(Bellalem, 2008, p.65)

Bellalem (2008) conducted a study where he interviewed both teachers and inspectors regarding teaching conditions. He concluded that teachers are more concerned with administrative commitments than with attending to the learning needs of students. This is because the inspectorate is more interested in the former than in the latter. In this case, power misuse is exercised by teachers through responding to the demands of a higher power, that is, the inspectors, by prioritising bureaucratic procedures to the detriment of learners and learning. The inspectors themselves are also reinforcing this reality and nurturing it by showing interest in administrative procedures rather than learners' learning needs. Moreover, teachers complained about the overcrowded classes and deemed them unsuitable as educational environments. Other teachers pointed out that the poor infrastructure of education in Algeria is attributed to the corruption of the system. Furthermore, some other teachers criticised the level of the students' and the teachers' awareness of their role. Schools and universities were figuratively referred to as hollow physical constructions that did little to enhance the spirit of teaching and learning. The latter is probably true in some teaching and learning contexts in Algeria. However, it does not reflect the situation in all Algerian classrooms.

At the university level, with the suppression of Institute of Technology and Education (ITE) and Ecoles Normales (high schools), the majority of universities have taken charge of the training of novice teachers by organising training sessions that aim to familiarise the newly recruited teachers with methodological knowledge prior to undertaking the teaching task. The training sessions organised by universities suffer from a number of deficiencies. Zouaozi (2015) pointed out that new postgraduate students' main interest is finding a job and experience was marginalised. Teachers were recruited with no preparation for the classroom, and they have no idea about

appropriate approaches, techniques, language skills, and materials. Britten (1988) argued that it is more likely for novice teachers to teach the way they were taught. This latter would turn the classroom practices into a set of repetitive scenarios, a carbon-copy version of old teaching methods and the constant manifestation of teachers' old behaviours and attitudes.

The pre-service teaching (PS) is an area where newly recruited teachers are equipped with adequate methodologies to avoid the repetition of old teaching scenarios, that is teacher-centred methods. The sector of PS teaching in Algeria could be considered deficient in many respects. First, attending the PS training programs is not compulsory. Equipping new teachers with teaching methodologies is not considered as a priority. Second, Youcef and Taoufik (2015) noted that although the PS training courses provide students with some methodological aspects and educational psychology, the knowledge introduced is mainly abstract and there is no time devoted to practice-based knowledge.

Another striking feature of teacher training is that it is a continuous process. Teachers have to keep developing their teaching skills throughout their professional careers. Continuous professional development or CPD enables teachers to keep track of any changes that might occur at syllabus or curriculum level, changes in learners' characteristics and attitudes as well as changes in working conditions as a whole. Unlike teacher training sessions, CPD involves various forms of learning opportunities that promote teachers' professional development (Li et al., 2008). Thus, it is individual and idiosyncratic. Day and Sachs (2005) observed that although CPD depends on teachers' initiatives, it is most effective when it arises as a result of a continuous interaction of teachers with their context. CPD is thus highly affected by cultural and organisational environment as well as habits, values and traditions that constitute a particular context.

It appears that the Algerian Ministry of HE pays lip service to CPD (Missoum, 2015). A considerable amount of money is allocated to CPD abroad every year. Missoum (2015) conducted a study to discover the extent of the efficiency of conferences and local study days organised as part of the CPD programmes. He discovered that 89 per cent of teachers said that support and opportunities provided by the programs were not sufficient. These organised programmes are not taken seriously. Since attending

these programs is optional, many teachers claim that they do not have enough time to take part in the programme. Furthermore, undertaking CPD training programmes abroad is costly, and the majority of these programmes emphasise quantity over quality.

The issues above related to the quality of EFL teacher training in Algeria did not appear in a vacuum. The lack of qualified personnel has been a recurring phenomenon since the very first reform of the education system, that of Arabization policy. The lack of proficiency in Algerian language teachers can also be highly affected by the policy of education enacted in the context. The phenomenon of massification (i.e. rapid increase in the number of students attending university) resulted in the recruitment of teaching personnel who did not have the prerequisite qualifications to undertake the teaching task, which inevitably had a detrimental effect on the quality of teaching and learning. Education institutions do not have the autonomy to respond to the issues that pervade the education sector, such as a workforce that is both inadequate in number and quality of preparation. The main reason is that the sector of education in Algeria is centralised, that is, power is concentrated at the level of the government, and the latter controls and manages all sectors of education (Souleh, 2017; Bouzid et. 2013). The latter is a significant layer of power. Within a centralised system, individuals in the communities, such as teachers and learners, are not involved in the decision-making process. This is evident, as explored earlier, in the marginalisation of Algerian people at the level of community, and teachers and learners at the level of education institution since the Arabisation reforms. The following section will shed light on the phenomena of massification and autonomy in HE.

2.7 Massification and autonomy in the Algerian HE system

Throughout this chapter, I have addressed several issues, specifically, the lack of qualified personnel, the inappropriateness of the adopted LMD system with the Algerian socio-cultural context, and the decision undertaken by the state to reform the system of education without careful planning. In addition to these, in this section of the chapter, I will shed light on other factors that bring to light the poor infrastructure of the HE education sector and the inadequate quality of the teaching and learning, namely massification and lack of autonomy in the HE sector.

One of the main problems that threaten HE in North Africa and Algeria, in particular, is the problem of massification (Teferra and Altbachl, 2004; Souleh, 2017). The demographic boom in Algerian society in the post-independence era led to rapid growth in the primary and secondary education sectors, which in turn led to the increase in the rate of the graduates who seek to access university education (Bouزيد, 2013; Mohamedbhai, 2014). Although ‘massification’ was in part motivated by the demographic reality of post-independent Algeria, and the large youth population, there is a consensus that massification was also motivated by the government’s explicit policy choices (Bouchikhi and Zine, 2017). The rapid expansion of the HE sector is not in itself a major problem. Rather, it is the conditions under which this exponential growth is being managed that pose severe challenges across the sector. In Algeria, massification was accompanied by a lack of financial, physical and human resources. Rose (2015) pointed out that massification without adequate preparation and resourcing is a constant threat to quality, and teachers are underqualified, underpaid and overstretched. Massification led to the occurrence of the phenomenon of large class size which affected students’ interaction and engagement (See Findings, Chapter 6, Section 6.5.2). A substantial body of literature maintained that the issue of large class have a negative impact of students’ motivation and engagement (Mulryan-Kyne 2010; Exeter et al. 2010; Hornsby and Osman, 2014).

Although it is an attribute of the neoliberal era, ‘massification’ is not the main factor behind students’ decreased motivation and engagement. As noted at the outset of this thesis, the neoliberal practices in higher education, which promote the instrumentalist view of language education, seem to have a significant impact on students’ motivation toward language learning (Kubota, 2011). Language learning became associated mainly with vocational and instrumental purposes and less with aesthetic and cultural aspects. The latter is evident in the findings of this PhD. Many students seemed to prefer getting good grades over in-depth learning. Also, many students seemed to choose to study English at the university because it was the choice available to them and not because of their love for the subject (see Chapter 6, Section 6.6). Regardless, massification remain a key contributing factor to students’ demotivation. In fact, the subject is more complicated as we dive deeper. Some relevant statistics will help to further our understanding of this phenomenon and provide some insight into the negative consequences for the Algerian HE sector.

It can be argued that the HE system has achieved some quantitative objectives. These quantitative objectives are not confined to increased rates of enrolment, but also encompass reforms such as the LMD system and proceeding reforms, training programmes and others. This section, however, will focus on the increase in students' enrolment rate and graduation, and the expansion of the HE institutions. Mohammed and Brahim (2010, p. 268) contended that 'those observing the performance of HE in Algeria can record that the primary concern is the quantitative aspect. This is reflected in the annual or periodic results recorded by the ministry, or even those recorded by universities.' Since independence, HE in Algeria has expanded swiftly. In 2016, the total number of Algerian HE institutions was 112. This figure comprises 50 universities, 11 centres universitaires, 12 écoles préparatoires, 11 écoles normales supérieures, and 20 écoles nationales supérieures (Souleh, 2017, p. 34). Correspondingly, the number of registered students, undergraduates, graduates, and postgraduates increased exponentially between 1962 and 2011. The table and figure presented underneath are based on the recent statistical data available.

The rapid growth in the sector is evident:

Table 2.7: The evolution of student enrolment between 1962-2011

Year	1962/63	1969/70	1979/80	1989/90	1999/00	2009/10	2010/11
Student enrolment in graduation	2725	12243	57445	181350	407995	1034313	1077945
Student enrolment in post-graduation	156	317	3965	13967	20846	58975	60617
Total	2881	12560	61410	195317	428841	1093288	1138562

Source: MESRS (2012, p.26)

Figure 2.7: The evolution of the number of graduate students by discipline (1962-2011)

Source: MESRS (2012, p.41)

From the statistics above, it is apparent that the national HE policies have been very successful in terms of increasing the number of students enrolling at and graduating from university. Most relevant to the context under study is the continuous and swift increase in the population of students enrolled in the social sciences and humanities (represented in purple in Figure 2.1 above), where foreign languages such as English are located. This has not always been the case for the field of social sciences and humanities. The latter was constantly being downgraded systematically by the authorities who favoured the hard sciences (Miliani, 2012; Mahdjoub and Miliani, 2017). As it is shown above, the field of social sciences and humanities began to exceed the hard science only between 1999 and 2000s, that is, in the era of globalisation. Such discrimination between the fields is a prime example of misuse of power, and under such discrimination ‘the quality of education will remain just a trendy term’ (Miliani, 2012, p.68; Mahdjoub and Miliani, 2017). Nevertheless, this rapid expansion resulted in a number of noticeable constraints and difficulties that cannot be hidden. For example, Bouzid et al. (2013) discussed some of these constraints and highlighted some of the issues concerning the state’s capacities in managing massification while maintaining quality. In the light of the state’s struggle to maintain quality, Rose (2015, p.6) clearly stated that ‘problems remain’. Bouzid et al. (2013, p. 104-105) draw attention to other realities, as follows:

- The university fell victim to the policy of expansion, which was the result of the state main concern of addressing societal needs concerning the labour market. However, the state capacity to cope with the lack of graduate jobs is open to question.
- A very significant proportion of the state budget is devoted to subsidised educational services such as accommodation, transportation, meals...etc.
- Outmoded training programmes.
- The recruitment of lecturers has failed to keep pace with the rapid expansion in student numbers.
- A far too much centralised and bureaucratic management of universities.

The apparent problem with Algerian universities is not merely limited to massification, but rather extends to preliminary and basic educational requirements such as inappropriate education environment (Alexander et al., 2016). Problems that are related to the educational environment include transportation, accommodation, and other socio-cultural obstacles that have a direct negative impact on the performance of HE institutions. Besides, there are also problems that are exclusively associated with libraries such as lack of required books and qualified librarians, as well as a shortage in computing and internet facilities (ibid). Apart from the inappropriateness of the educational environment and the material shortages documented in the literature, there were also references to the underperformance of the teaching staff who are not trained to use technology and are inclined to favour outdated teaching methodologies (Ghiat, 2008). Among the reasons behind the low performance of the teaching staff are the bad working conditions as well as low salaries. Alexander et al. (2016) pointed out that even though the teachers' salaries almost doubled by October 2010; they are still low compared to those in most Arab and African universities. Many of the aforementioned issues had already been echoed in previous sections of the chapter. However, there is a good reason for this apparent redundancy in this discussion of the phenomenon of the massification in the Algerian HE institutions. It serves further to accentuate the conditions under which this phenomenon of massification is being managed.

The pursuit of knowledge, its dissemination and application within societies has always been a cornerstone and a valid indicator of both social and economic growth (Farrell et al., 2006). HE institutions play an integral role in the production and dissemination of such knowledge. These institutions are also considered as the producers of the human capital that meets the needs of employers in both local and global markets. In a country like Algeria, where academic institutions have limited autonomy, those objectives come under the auspices of the state that dominates all sectors of public education. Particularly in HE, the ministry controls everything from budgets allocation, student recruitment, curricula, and management (Bouzid et al., 2013). Such domination inevitably affects both the quality and efficiency of these institutions. Algerian public HE operates directly and exclusively following the state framework of participation and autonomy. Within this framework, the autonomy granted to Algerian universities can be described at three main levels:

- **Administrative autonomy.** The university is administered by a rector or a director appointed by the ministry.
- **Academic autonomy.** The university determines teaching programmes for the subjects within their sphere of competence.
- **Financial autonomy.** The university has budgetary allocation assigned by the state and its funding from public or private sector. The use of university finances is subject to ex-post auditing (Ruffio et al., 2011, p 13).

From the categories outlined above, it can be deduced that HE institutions' autonomy in Algeria is fairly limited. Talbi (2015) claimed that such dependency on the government does not encourage universities to seek partnerships with local business enterprises. This brings to our attention the limited extent to which research and educational programmes in Algerian HE institutions meet societal and economic needs within a framework of limited autonomy. HE institutions in Algeria operate independently from their surroundings, unable to cooperate with society and industry. According to Benouar (2013), this separation is responsible for creating a gap between the interests of the university and those of society. This has resulted in a mismatch between the skills taught to students and the societal and market expectations. Bouzid et al. (2013) pointed out that the lack of correspondence

between the university programmes and labour market conditions has had negative consequences for the development of Algerian HE institutions, on the overall quality of education and for graduates' employability.

The detachment of HE from local labour market conditions is dramatic and severe in its repercussions for Algerian graduates (Sultana, 2017). There are a number of possible reasons for this. On the one hand, there is the phenomenon of massification and the way in which this process has been managed, and on the other the quality of the education offered, especially concerning its contribution to the labour market. Employability rates in Algeria fall below standards in comparable countries (ibid), despite state and private sector intervention to resolve this public concern. The issue of employability also affects Algerian youths in general and students' vision toward their future in particular (Miliani, 2010). As will become more evident when we consider the findings from the empirical research (see Chapters 6) this has a profound effect upon their motivation towards learning and the relationship dynamics within the classroom context.

In the next chapter, I shall turn attention to the exploration of the key notion that informs the study reported in this thesis, namely the notion of interactional competence (IC) and the role of teachers' beliefs.

Chapter 3: Interactional competence and the role of teachers' beliefs

3.1 Introduction

In the last two decades or so, discourse about the notion of interactional competence (IC) gained momentum (Hall, 2018). Fundamentals that the notion of IC promotes, such as collective achievements of goals, joint management of interaction, equality between the speaker and hearer roles, meaning negotiation and meaning co-construction, were considered revolutionary in the field of SLA (Kramsch, 1986; Young, 2011; Hall, 2018). As a consequence, the discourse around the notion of communicative competence (CC) retreated significantly because it primarily focuses on individual abilities. In particular, the field of Second Language Acquisition (SLA) shifted its focus from the notion CC towards the consideration of the notion of IC, that is, from the conception of the notion of competence which resides in individuals' abilities to one that is collectively managed, and corporately achieved by all participants (Kramsch, 1986; Hall, 2018; Young, 2011; Kasper and Wagner, 2011; Walsh, 2012).

The field of Teaching English for Speakers of Other Languages (TESOL) also followed similar patterns to that of SLA, and this was marked by the emergence of sociocultural and critical critiques of the field (May, 2011). Methods that were founded upon theories of SLA such as communicative language teaching (CLT) and its successor Task-Based Language Teaching (TBLT) were questioned for their effectiveness in foreign language classroom pedagogy (Kumaravadivelu, 2006; Butler, 2011). The issue lies in the fact that these methods were devised by theorists who play loosely with the notion of context, and seldom include the broader social, cultural, political and historical particularities (Kumaravadivelu, 2006, p.72). The mismatch between method-based pedagogy and the broader socio-cultural context led to practical difficulties in the implementation of both CLT and TBLT. For example, CLT has been resisted by many language teachers and learners across many parts of the world (Ibid). Particularly in Algeria, both teachers and learners resisted the implementation of CLT because it was introduced with no adequate level of preparation and with no consideration of the educational realities in the context. CLT challenged the prevailing traditional conception of teaching and learning, that is, a

teacher-centred approach (Benmoussat and Benmoussat, 2018). To address the issue of the mismatch between the method and the sociocultural context, Kumaravadivelu (2001; 2006) proposed a shift from a method-based pedagogy to post-method pedagogy (PMP).

PMP encompasses several principles and parameters which are an amalgam of post-method area context-appropriate methodologies and critical pedagogies (Waters, 2012). Being influenced by pedagogies of the emancipation and liberation such as the work of Freire (1970), PMP rejects the *status quo* way of teaching, namely the transmission or the banking model of education. On the note of knowledge transmission, Fulford and Mahon (2018) argued that not all knowledge transmission-based teaching strategies are inadequate. For example, lecturing can be regarded as dialogical and even interactive way of teaching because when addressing the other one is demanding a response.

As pedagogy that occurred in the post-method era, PMP aims at empowering teachers with knowledge and urging them to theorise from their classroom practices to build a classroom pedagogy that is congruent with their lived experiences and local exigencies (Kumaravadivelu, 2001; 2006). It also emphasises the idea of partnership and equality between teachers, learners, and other parties such as theorists, and the role dialogic interaction, and collaboration play in the success of this partnership (Ibid).

The conception of competence inherent in the notion of IC as one that is collectively managed and achieved by all participants is undoubtedly a fascinating philosophy, and one that broadly relates to pedagogies of emancipation and liberation and particularly to PMP (For more details see Sections 3.3.5 and 3.3.6). At the most basic level, such a conception defines the very nature of human beings as we are designed for dialogue rather than monologue (Garrod & Pickering, 2004, p. 8). It also, by extension, defines the very nature of classroom pedagogy where both teachers and learners interact and co-produce, and equally share the responsibility for the good and bad of their classroom interaction experiences (Allwright, 1984). In principle, interaction is a worthwhile human activity that summons mutual understanding, collaboration, cooperation, and co-achievement of goals. In a way, it entails leading life with others and applies to all walks of life (Pirrie et al., 2019). For example, in

the context of research supervision, Pirrie et al. (2019) expressed their rejection to the consumer model of education. They proposed an alternative ontology to research supervision, one that is informed by dialogic interaction, improvisation, and other dialogical tenets such as love and trust (ibid).

As fascinating as it is, the implementation of the philosophy underpinning of the notion of IC is problematic to foreign language classroom pedagogy for a number of reasons. First, the majority of what happens in language classrooms, from teaching to testing is concerned with individual performance and has little to do with collective performances (Walsh, 2012; Campbell-Larsen, 2014). Second, the real challenge, however, lies in the implementation of IC philosophy in foreign language environments without considering local exigencies and lived experiences; a case in point is the implementation of the LMD system in Algeria as explored in the previous chapter. To this end, a holistic understanding of the notion of IC and the challenges that might hamper its implementation in a particular context might be achieved through obtaining teachers' and students' perceptions and their lived experiences with IC, details of which are found in Chapters 5 and 6.

The remainder of this chapter comprises a review of the literature to gain an in-depth look at the notion of IC and the other core element of the study, namely the notion of teacher beliefs. In particular, this chapter investigates the relationship between the notion of interactional competence (IC) and foreign language teaching methodologies and the role of teacher beliefs in this complex interplay. This chapter comprises three main sections. The first section charts the development of the notion of IC competence. It explores the evolution of IC from its early intellectual roots in modern languages, anthropology, and sociocultural theory up to Hall's (2018) notion of interactional repertoire. It also examines the so-called shift from the notion of CC into IC. The second section investigates second/foreign language teaching methodologies. It also explores the relationships between the notion of IC and language teaching methods. The third section examines the notion of teacher beliefs and their role in the complex interplay between IC and English language teaching methodologies.

3.2 The development of the notion of interactional competence

There seems to be a lot of confusion in the literature concerning the true nature of the notion of IC (Hall, 2018; Waring, 2018; Young, 2011). Reasons for the existing confusion range from the versatile intellectual roots of the notion of IC to the fact that thinking around the notion occurred very much at the same time (Hall, 2018). As a consequence, the term IC has been used in various ways by different scholars and in different areas of second and foreign language teaching, learning, and testing (Young, 2011). Besides, the fact that the term has never been comprehensibly defined renders the task of uncovering its true nature more challenging (Walsh, 2012; Hall, 2018). In an attempt to embark on this challenging task, there is a need to revisit the notion's intellectual roots.

The notion of interactional competence (IC) in SLA has two major intellectual roots; linguistic anthropology and more precisely in Hymes' (1972) work on communicative competence in the context of the first language acquisition (FLA) which was introduced as a reaction to Chomsky's (1965) theory of linguistic competence (LC) (Taguchi, 2015; Hall, 2018). The second intellectual root of IC in SLA is conversational analysis (CA). IC also had its insight from Vygotsky's sociocultural theory (SCT) (Johnson, 2008).

3.2.1 The roots of interactional competence in linguistic anthropology

Chomsky (1965) introduced his theory of linguistic competence as a response to the behaviourist theory. Within the latter, language learning and development was viewed as a set of habits and skills that are the product of the interaction with the environment through stimulus, response, and reinforcement (Larsen-Freeman, 2012). A prominent work predicated on this view of language is Skinner's (1957) *Verbal Behaviour*, which was considered by Skinner as one of his best works (Skinner, 1977). Chomsky (1959) published a review that was written in an aggressive and confrontational manner (Palmer, 2006). In this review, Chomsky (1959) heavily criticised Skinner's *Verbal Behaviour* in particular and the behaviourists' philosophy in general and argued that linguistic competence is far more creative than as presented by Skinner's (Savignon, 2017). For Chomsky (1965), language is innate, has a generative property, and universal to all human beings. Chomsky's (1965) theory of

linguistic competence did not only criticise the behaviourists' take on language learning and development but also represented an initial challenge to second and foreign language methods that were rooted in the behaviourist philosophical current, particularly the audiolingual method (Savignon, 2017). Chomsky's (1959) review of Skinner's *Verbal Behaviour* lit the touch paper between cognitivism and behaviourism. Harris (1993) documented these conflicting perspectives in his book *Linguistic Wars*. The dispute between Skinner and Chomsky was indeed a war. It had a hallmark of a personal vendetta that was the result of intellectual intolerance, rather than an intellectual dispute due to the level of emotionality involved (see Chomsky, 1959; MacCorquodale, 1970; Palmer, 2006, Harris, 1993). Notwithstanding the disagreement between the two scholars on the nature of language and language learning, there is a consensus in the literature that both paradigms are somewhat similar, complementary, and have striking affinities (For example, see Moerk, 1992; Richelle, 1993; Goddard, 2015).

Chomsky (1965) used the term 'competence' in a technical sense for the first time and distinguished it from performance. The former refers to 'the speaker's/ hearer's knowledge of his language,' while the latter refers to 'the actual use of language in a concert situation' (Chomsky, 1965, p.4). Chomsky's (1965) theory of linguistic competence attempted to describe an idealised and abstracted version of language (Campbell-Larsen, 2014). Hymes (1972) criticised Chomsky's conception of competence as being narrow, and his notion of performance as being 'trivial', a 'dustbin' for linguistics phenomena (Hymes, 1972, Tylor, 1988). Hymes's (1972) notion of CC provided a broader view of language use (Hall, 2018). The introduction of the notion of CC marked a total redirection of focus, from the study of language to study of language in use, that is, communication. Hymes's (1972) notion of CC is predicated on the idea that it is not enough for language speakers to know only grammatical structures but also the social rule of usage. Therefore, the focus was not only on what is grammatically correct but also to what is appropriate in a given communicative event. Despite Hymes's (1972) criticism of Chomsky's linguistic theory, many scholars from different fields preserved Chomsky's (1965) distinction between competence and performance. For example, Habermas (1970) preserved it in his conceptualisation of the notion of CC in the field of philosophy of language. Campbell and Wales (1970) also maintained Chomsky's (1965) distinction between

competence and performance, and they described it as 'eminently honourable'. Chomsky's (1965) linguistic theory impact extended to include the field of SLA. For instance, the CC model developed by Canale and Swain (1980) explicitly adopted competence/performance distinction. Chomsky's notion of language acquisition device (LAD) that is, human beings are equipped with a language organ in the brain that makes language learning possible is evident in ground-breaking work in SLA. For example, in Corder's (1967) work on learner's errors, Selinker's (1972) work on the notion of 'interlanguage' and Dulay, Burt, and Krashen's (1982) model of second language speech processing (Firth and Wagner, 1997, p. 287).

Moreover, Chomsky's (1965) notion of idealised native speakers fashioned SLA research around the native speakers' norms, or what came to be known as the monolingual bias in SLA (May 2011; Firth and Wagner, 1997). Consequently, this has led to the emergence of the deficit model in SLA, that is second and foreign language speaker's oral performances are considered inferior to that of native speakers (May, 2011). The issue of monolingual bias in SLA was first echoed by Kachru (1994) and further reiterated by Firth and Wagner (1997). For example, Firth and Wagner (1997) critiqued mainstream SLA that followed the prevailing monolingual orientation and argued that SLA research that investigated foreign-language speakers' discourse and interaction based on the view of FL learners as deficient communicators is impaired. They also maintained that English learners are competent speakers who deploy a wide range of interactional and discursal features in different social settings to accomplish a wide range of interactional goals (Firth Wagner, 1997; May 2011). As will be explored later in this chapter, the conceptualisation of communicative competence as presented by the anthropologist and sociolinguist Hymes (1972) was also predicated on the idealised view of native speakers. This also includes language teaching methods that are founded on the basis of his theory such as communicative language teaching (CLT) and its subsequent manifestation Task-Based Teaching and Learning (TBLT) which continue to dominate TESOL pedagogy (May, 2011).

Hymes' (1972) notion had its roots in his *Ethnography of Speaking* (Hymes, 1962) and *Ethnography of Communication* (Hymes, 1964). The Prague School of functionalism had a significant influence on the development of Hymes' thinking at

this time, and partly explains his emphasis on language function and social dimension of language use (Savignon, 2017). It should also be noted that Hymes' notion of CC also had a situational origin, a less well-known one (Cazden, 1996). Hymes discussed the notion of CC for the first time in a conference held at the Ferkauf Graduate School in NYC in June 1966. The conference was entitled *Research Planning Conference on Language Development among Disadvantaged Children*. The conference title communicates the socio-political scene that marked the period between 1965-1966. At that time in the US, the civil rights movements and the war on poverty were at their peak. These circumstances might have affected the form of expression of CC, and the negative response the theory of the linguistic competence received on the part of the Prague School. On the other hand, it certainly added to the reception and the influence of CC (Cazden, 1996).

There are several issues related to the development of the notion of CC. These issues are non-existent in most recent accounts on the development of interactional competence (see, for example, Hall, 2018). Although Hymes provided a broader conception of competence, the theory of CC was built upon an invalid criticism of Chomsky's conception of competence, and his notion of idealisation. Technically sociolinguistics is broader than linguistics, hence Hymes' (1972) conception of competence was broader than Chomsky's (1965). Even though it is broader, sociolinguistics also idealises, probably to a lesser degree (Davies, 1984). Hymes' (1972) conception of CC is an idealisation of the speech community, which is a community with a shared understanding of the rules for conduct and interpretation of speech, in this case, native speakers of English (Hymes, 1974). In respect of Hymes' criticism of Chomsky's linguistic theory Van Compernelle (2014, p.39) notes that: 'there is some irony in this transformation inasmuch as Hymes' original ideas were themselves part of a critique of Chomsky (1965)'.

The notion of idealisation is also evident in the work of Habermas' (1970) on CC in the field of philosophy of language. Habermas' (1970) CC is considered as an attempt towards the understanding of CC in terms of linguistic theory through retaining Chomsky's (1965) original conception of competence (Habermas, 1970, p.273). Unlike Hymes (1972), who idealised the speech community, and Chomsky (1965), who idealised 'speaker and hearer,' Habermas (1970) idealised the speech situation,

that is 'communicative competence means the mastery of an ideal speech situation' (Habermas, 1970, p.369).

Not only the notion of CC was built on invalid criticism, but it also introduced the notion of competence into a world of messiness. Hymes' (1972) notion of CC expanded upon Chomsky's conception of competence by incorporating the sociocultural context. As shown in the model above, Hymes added another type of competence, namely sociolinguistic competence, that is, knowledge of social rules. In Hymes' (1972) model of CC, 'competence is understood to be dependent on two things: (tacit) knowledge and (ability for) use' (Hymes, 1972, p.282). The problem with Hymes' expansion lies in the integration of the latter, namely the ability for use within the notion of competence. This implies that competence is defined in terms of knowledge and ability. According to Hymes (1972, pp.283-284), the incorporation of ability for use within competence 'allows for the role of non-cognitive factors, which partly determine competence like motivation to take place'. Chomsky (1980, p. 59) took issue with the integration of the aspect of ability within competence:

The term competence entered the technical literature in an effort to avoid entanglement with the slew of problems relating to 'knowledge', but it is misleading in that it suggests ability...an association I would like to sever.

Elsewhere, Douglas (2005) also commented on this notion of 'ability for use'. He distinguished between communicative competence and communicative success. In his view, 'ability for use' is not the same as use. There are situations where the speaker of a second language possesses the knowledge to accomplish a particular communicative task. However, he or she may choose not to do so for their own reasons, or due to other external factors (ibid). This means that the 'ability for use' precedes use (ibid). The former includes internal psycholinguistic factors and external factors that come between the speaker and the accomplishment of a particular communicative task. The aforementioned is the same distinction between competence and performance put forward by Chomsky (1965).

The issue of integrating the aspect of ability within competence was also carried into the context of second and foreign language teaching and learning. For example, Savignon (1972) was among the first methodologists to apply Hymes' (1972) theory of CC in second language learning. Savignon (1972) put even more emphasis than Hymes (1972) on the notion of ability (Bagarić and Djigunović, 2007). Hence, competence was no longer viewed in terms of knowledge and ability but merely ability. According to Savignon (1972, p.8), CC is:

The ability to function in a truly communicative setting, that is, in a dynamic exchange in which linguistic competence must adapt itself to the total informational input, both linguistic and paralinguistic, of one or more interlocutors.

Savignon (1972; 1983) believed that performance is a clear manifestation of competence, i.e. that competence can be observed, tested, and measured through performance. In addition, Savignon (1983) seemed to identify competence (knowledge) with proficiency (ability to use knowledge). This is evident in the following quotation from Savignon (1983, p.53):

The competence of native speakers, well developed though it may be, is relative. Mother-tongue proficiency varies widely from child to child and from adult to adult in vocabulary range, articulation, critical thinking, persuasiveness, and penmanship are, but a few of the many, many facets of competence wherein native speakers differ.

In the above quotation, we notice that Savignon (1983) discusses competence in terms of the proficiency of the native speaker, where she identified the native speaker's competence with proficiency in the 'native' language. The identification of competence with this level of proficiency is immensely problematic.

Canale and Swain (1980) built upon Hymes' model of CC, and they were among the first to adopt the framework of CC and apply it to the field of second language testing.

Their interest in this theory of competence was initially driven by the need to develop a language test for learners of French. These tests involved the measurement of both knowledge of and proficiency in the language (Canale and Swain 1980; Peterwagner, 2005). Their notion of CC is different from that of Hymes (1972). It only covered the knowledge aspect of Hymes' CC, and not the ability for use (Ritchie and Bhatia, 2006). Canale and Swain (1980) argued that the inclusion of psycholinguistic competence is not necessary. From their perspective, factors such as memory or perceptual strategies are non-specific to CC, and they simply represent general psychological constraints on communication. This echoes Chomsky (1980) who referred to the same phenomenon as an 'irrelevant extraneous consideration'. These psychological constraints constitute the theory of performance and not competence. Therefore, instead of including the ability for use in the CC, as Hymes (1972) did, Canale and Swain (1980) included it in the notion of communicative performance. Hence, they distinguish between 'communicative competence' (knowledge) and 'communicative performance' (the realization of these competencies and their interaction in the actual production and comprehension of utterances) (Canale and Swain, 1980, p.6). They further argued that these basic distinctions should be maintained in the context of second language teaching and testing. The extent to which Canale and Swain (1980) deviated from Hymes' original conception of CC can be seen in respect of the following. First, the notion has not been rigorously explored within the framework of CC. Second, they were sceptical about the existence of any theory of human action that could adequately explain the ability for use; and third, they had concerns about the communication deficits that arise from social class and power relations (Canale and Swain, 1980; Peterwagner, 2005, p. 12-13).

Canale and Swain (1980, p.29) proposed that CC is made of three major components: grammatical competence; sociolinguistic competence; and strategic competence. These components are further elaborated as follows:

- Grammatical competence: Knowledge of lexical items and of rules of morphology, syntax, sentence-grammar semantics, and phonology.
- Sociolinguistic competence: Knowledge of sociocultural rules of use which are crucial for interpreting utterances for social

meaning, particularly when there is a low level of transparency between the literal meaning of an utterance and the speakers' intention.

- Strategic competence: Knowledge of verbal and non-verbal communication strategies that may be called into action to compensate for a breakdown in communication due to performance variables or insufficient competence.

The model above was later revised and expanded by Canale (1983), who added a further component: discourse competence. The latter refers to the learners' mastery of understanding and producing texts in the modes of listening, speaking, reading, and writing. It deals with cohesion and coherence in different types of text.

It appears that claims that Canale and Swain (1980) disregarded the 'ability for use' in their model of CC were exaggerated. For instance, Shohamy (1996, p.143) argued that components of discourse competence and strategic competence involved the ability for use as well as knowledge. Many researchers and scholars concur with the aforementioned argument, for example, McNamara (1995, 1996), Peterwagner (2005), and Csepes (2009). Thus, Canale and Swain return to Hymes' conception that competence involves both knowledge and ability, although they claimed otherwise. McNamara (1996) regarded this return as symptomatic of the fact that Canale (1983) was interested in advancing a theory of performance. This means that both Hymes and Canale (1983) were dealing with performance and not competence. A further critique of Canale's (1983) framework of CC concerns its static nature and the fact that it appeared to disregard how the proposed components of the model interact with each other or how language users cope in a range of diverse contexts (Bachman and Cohen, 1998, p.6). Moreover, the proposed models, both in the original and revised versions, do not explain how CC is translated into communicative performance (Csepes, 2009). That said, Canale and Swain's model and Canale's revised version have one interesting feature which is overlooked in many discussions in the literature, namely 'autonomous Competence', i.e., the involvement of personal rules more than the social rules of language use (Allison, 1999, p.49).

In an attempt to address the definition issue surrounding the concept of competence, Tylor (1988) proposed the usage of the term 'competence' as put forward by Chomsky (1965) and differentiated between three dimensions. First of all, there is 'competence' that is defined as knowledge or state of knowledge. Second, 'proficiency' is defined as the ability to use knowledge. Third, there is performance, which refers to the actual use of knowledge. In addition, Tylor (1988) ironically concluded that the integration of the ability for use within competence by Hymes and those who followed him turned the concept of competence into a dustbin. This was the very analogy used by Hymes (1972) to critique Chomsky's (1965) views on performance. It should be noted that the relationship between knowledge and ability is very problematic, both in the description of learners and language users, as well as in language pedagogy (Widdowson, 1989). Referring to competence as 'ability' suggests performance and not competence (Tylor, 1988).

The work of Hornberger (1989) is also relevant to the present discussion. Her empirical work was based on her personal experience in Peru as a second language learner. She made use of Hymes' (1972) model of CC to analyse speech events. She explicitly acknowledged the influence of Hymes (1972) on the development of her work. Hornberger (1989, p.299) also noted Tylor's (1988) suggestion for usage of the term competence in the sense proposed by Chomsky, that is, as knowledge, and proficiency as the ability to use of competence. She responded to Tylor (1989) as follows: 'while it seems reasonable to me to distinguish competence and proficiency in this way, at the same time I see no problem in retaining Hymes' conception as the most adequate model for communicative competence' (Hornberger, 1989, p.229). To further her argument on the retention of Hymes' model of communicative competence, in the end, Hornberger (1989) adduced the work of Spolsky (1989), who used the same framework. However, neither author acknowledges the other's contribution.

3.2.2 The Fundamentals of IC within the framework of CC

Several fundamentals of the notion of the interactional competence were echoed within the framework of the communicative competence, such as intersubjectivity and meaning negotiation.

The notion of intersubjectivity which entails putting one's self in the shoes of the other in a bid to achieve a successful interaction dates back as early as the work of Goffman's (1959) in dramaturgical sociology. The literature that explored the notion of IC gave little attention to the influence of Goffman's (1959) work on the current conceptualisation of the notion of IC. The most recent reviews that explored the intellectual roots of the notion of IC argued that IC has its roots in Hymes' (1972) work on CC. However, the in-depth literature review of this PhD study established that the notion of IC is rooted in the field of dramaturgical sociology and particularly in Goffman's (1959).

In fact, the very first time the term IC came to the fore was in Hymes' (1972) work on CC. Hymes (1972) cited Goffman (1959) in his discussion of the notion of performance and pointed out 'the concept of performance will be important in the light sociological work (cited above), as its concern with general interactional competence helps make precise the particular role of linguistic competence' (Hymes, 1972, p. 284). It is therefore somewhat surprising that research that explored the notion of IC from Kramsch (1986) right up to Hall (2018) appears to have overlooked this detail. This detail is essential in the understanding of the notion of IC, especially in considering Hymes' (1984) appreciation of Goffman, and the fact he admitted that few researchers were prepared to pick up Goffman's 'golden shovel' (Hymes, 1984; also cited in Drew and Wotton 1988 and Fine and Manning, 2003). Hymes' (1972) reference to picking up the golden shovel suggests that he saw himself as one of the few researchers who began to dig deeper, although it appears that he was unaware that he was dealing with IC.

One of the fundamental elements of IC that were accentuated with the framework of CC is the notion of intersubjectivity. Goffman (1959) viewed a competent communicator as an actor, a performer who appreciates the encounter, co-present, and helps protect other individuals' social identities when threatened by a faux-pas. Wiemann (1977, p.196) pointed 'Goffman's work, in particular, leads to the conclusion that competence is a dyadic construct.' Kramsch (1986, p. 367) reiterated Goffman's characteristics of competent communicator in her discussion of the notion of intersubjectivity. She maintained that interaction always entails...' adjusting one's speech to the effect one intends to have on the listener.'

The notion of intersubjectivity also surfaced in the Habermas' (1970) work on CC. As explored earlier, Habermas (1970) defined CC as the mastery of an ideal speech situation. For Habermas (1970, p. 371), an ideal speech situation is one that involves 'pure intersubjectivity', and co-generated through participants' dialogical engagement, where neither party's performance is characterised as privileged. Although Habermas's (1970) conception of CC was based on the linguistic theory, he demonstrated an understanding of IC through underscoring the role of participants' reciprocity towards each other to achieve intersubjectivity (Habermas, 1970, p.371). In a similar vein, Kramersch (1986) also spoke of intersubjectivity in the framework of IC. She referred to successful interaction as an interaction that does not only involve a shared knowledge of the world, and an external context of communication, but also a shared internal context or 'the sphere of intersubjectivity.' Intersubjectivity is achieved through participants' collaborative efforts to minimise the occurrence of uncertainties and misunderstandings (Kramersch, 1986, p.367).

Habermas's (1970) notion of 'pure intersubjectivity' deserves further consideration. Habermas's (1970) take on the notion of intersubjectivity as one that is pure is, probably, ahead of its time. This is because Habermas viewed communicative competence as a developmental phenomenon. Habermas (1970, p.372) pointed out 'we are quite unable to realize the ideal speech situation; we can only anticipate it.' Perhaps, in all times, there are extraneous factors that influence the development of individual perspectives: for instance, at the micro-level personal beliefs and perspectives, and the macro-level social, political, economic, and institutional structures. The former will be explored later in this chapter in relation to the empirical work reported in Chapter 5. Chapter 2 comprised a brief overview of the social, political, economic, and institutional structures in Algeria.

In addition to the notion of intersubjectivity, meaning negotiation was also emphasised within the framework of CC. For example, Savignon's (1983) conception of CC draws attention to the notion of 'meaning negotiation'. Unlike Hymes (1972), who focused on CC from the point of view of the individual's use of language, Savignon emphasised the notion of meaning negotiation. The latter depends on the participants involved in a particular communicative event.

Savignon (1983, p.8) pointed out:

Communicative competence is a dynamic rather than a static concept. It depends on the negotiation of meaning between two or more persons who share to some degree the same symbolic system. In this sense, then, communicative competence can be said to be an interpersonal rather than an intrapersonal trait.

According to the view outlined above, CC is considered dynamic rather than static. As noted before, Savignon (1983) considered performance as a direct manifestation of competence, which logically entails a degree of variation in the level of individual performances. This has led Savignon (1983) to suggest that it is logical to speak of 'communicative competencies' (ibid). Nevertheless, the claim that CC can be directly measured and evaluated through performance suggests that Savignon was dealing with an individual's performances under what she has labelled as communicative proficiency. The fact that Savignon (1983) underscored meaning negotiation and referred to CC as interpersonal rather than intrapersonal indicates an understanding of IC. Similarly, Kramsch (1986, p. 268) argued that communication is predicated on the relativity and unpredictability of interpersonal interaction. Therefore, in this particular publication, that is, Savignon (1983), there is the surfacing of the notion of IC. This publication, as it were, marked the transition from CC to Kramsch's (1986) paper and the introduction of the notion of IC. Savignon (1983) referred to what Kramsch (1986) referred to as 'sphere of intersubjectivity' as a 'symbolic system.' Such an understanding of the notion is quite close to, if not identical with, the fundamental principle of IC, i.e., IC is collective rather than individualistic. It is important to note that Kramsch (1986) cited Savignon (1985) in discussing the notion of the native speaker, yet Savignon (1983) was not referenced.

The subsequent section will turn attention to another intellectual root of IC, that is, conversation analysis (CA).

3.2.3 Interactional competence and conversation analysis

The second intellectual root of the notion of IC is conversational analysis (CA) (Hall, 2018). CA is concerned with how participants develop and deploy the observable or elements of IC such as turn-taking, repairs, and clarification. As a method for the

analysis of talk-in-interaction, CA was developed around the same time as Hymes' theory of CC (ibid). This resulted in some CA studies to be based on the Hymesian (1972) CC theory (Pekarek Doehler and Berger, 2018). However, the current CA studies on SLA (Also known as CA-SLA) are founded on a notion of IC that made use CA's roots in ethnomethodology (Pekarek Doehler and Berger, 2018).

As opposed to the conception of IC in linguistic anthropology, interactional competence in CA is not perceived as contrary to performance, rather as inseparable from performance (Roever and Casper, 2018). Also, unlike linguistic anthropology, CA is not concerned with the variability of individual knowledge but instead views competence as a universal construct (Hall, 2018; Roever and Casper, 2018). The latter can also be referred to as basic-interactional competence (BIC), one that is universal and common in all human being and constitutes a requirement for sociality (Kecskes, 2018). CA also views IC as a context-specific and goal-oriented construct that is dependent on participants and their local abilities (Hall, 2018; Roever and Casper, 2018). A point of commonality, however, between linguistic anthropology conception of IC and CA's conception is the idea that competence can be observed and measured using naturally occurring data such recordings (Hall, 2018).

In addition, unlike other methods of talk-in-interaction analyses such as interaction analyses (IA) and discourse analysis (DA), CA views the classroom context as dynamic and continuously takes shape as the participants interact, co-construct meanings and adjust their talk to the pedagogical goal of the moment. In addition, CA analysis does not start from a pre-existing set of categories, rather the interactional processes deployed by the participants emerge from the data itself (Walsh, 2006; Cancino, 2015). Using CA methodology to analyse classroom talk (Walsh, 2002; 2006; 2012) unveiled a wide range of interactional process, and referred to them as features of classroom interactional competence (CIC) (see Section 3.3.6). Walsh argued that these features, or performative elements of IC as referred to in this study, play an essential role in creating or obstructing learning opportunities language classrooms.

CA-based research demonstrated how teachers' and learners' moment-by-moment interactive decisions could affect subsequent interactions and learning opportunities (Walsh, 2006). The teacher is not viewed as only a 'facilitator' of learning but rather

as a creator and a maximiser of learning opportunities (Ibid). The conception of teachers as only facilitators of learning is endorsed by the methods such as communicative language teaching (CLT), and task-based approach (TBA) (Cancino, 2015). It is also the same way teacher are viewed within the LMD system reforms as explored in Chapter 2. Viewing teachers as only a facilitator of learning is diminishing to their central role in the creation and management of interaction in the classroom which immensely affect learning and learning opportunities (Walsh, 2012; 2013). This understanding of the teacher's role is rooted in Vygotsky's (1978) sociocultural theory (SCT) where the teacher is considered the expert and the learner as an apprentice who acquires interactional skills via interacting with the teacher or with more experienced peers in a hypothetical learning zone commonly referred to as the Zone of Proximal Development or ZPD (Johnson, 2008). The next section will provide an exclusive account of the SCT insight into the notion of IC (see Section, 3.2.4).

The most recent conceptualisation of the notion of IC in the field of CA-SLA is the concept of interactional repertoire (IR). The concept was proposed by Hall 2018 to be used in research that makes use of CA methodology. The main reason is that Hall (2018) understood IC as a developmental phenomenon. The concept IR is viewed to be useful as it believed it 'aptly captures the variable nature of the multilingual and multimodal resources' that learners deploy and develop in various performative contexts. Although the term IR was first proposed by Hall (2018), IR was first discussed by Markee (2008) who considered it as a by-product of IC and not an alternative to it (Markee, 2008; 2019). Due to the intricacy of the notion of IC and its broad dimensions and eclectic theoretical roots, Markee (2019) preferred to refer to IC as competence in CA-SLA.

As noted earlier, IC insights in SLA have their ground in Vygotsky's (1978) sociocultural theory (SCT) (Johnson, 2008). Hence, the notion of competence seems to have undergone another stage of development where researchers drew on SCT in their conceptualisation of IC, namely the idea that learning and knowledge are socially and culturally constructed (Markee, 2019). This will be explored in the next section.

3.2.4 Interactional competence and socio-cultural cultural theory

The sociocultural theory came as a reaction to Piaget's theory of language development (Jarvis, 2005). Within the latter, the child was perceived as a learning individual, 'alone scientist' who can develop his cognition through interacting with stimulating materials. The child's cognitive development is based on the number of experiences the child happens to encounter. However, the spoken discourse also plays a salient role in the development of the child's intellectual abilities and these abilities are not merely restricted to what is already known and what is newly encountered. Rather, they originate from the child interaction with his social environment. This was the pitfall in Piaget's paradigm that paved the way for Vygotsky to form his SCT (Jarvis, 2005, p.27).

In his SCT, Vygotsky (1978, p.22) put emphasis on 'the dominant role of social experiences in human development'. For Vygotsky (1978), human higher mental processes have their origin in social activities. Thus, learning first occurs at the interpersonal level, that is the social, historical and institutional level, and the individual internalises the social patterns at the cognitive and psychological level. The process of internalisation is very complex and dynamic and involves a gradual and dynamic shift of the individual from one stage of development to another. The environment mainly controls the first stage. The second stage is where the individual needs the assistance of more proficient individuals, and the third stage is where the individual takes control of his or her mental processes. The process of internalisation requires a medium between the intrapersonal level and interpersonal level, usually a symbolic system, that is language (Johnson, 2008; Lantolf, 2000).

Inherent in Vygotsky's (1978) sociocultural theory is the notion of mediation. The latter is premised on the philosophy that individuals do not establish a direct relationship with the environment, but first, it is mediated through the use of tools (Lantolf, 2000; Simon and Thi, 2016). Vygotsky distinguished between three types of tools. Material tools which refer to anything human being invented to master nature, for example, a shovel; psychological tools which mediate between individual's psychological processes; and other individuals like tying a handkerchief to recall something or write a to-do list to manage time efficiently and develop self-will.

Vygotsky's notion of mediating tools led many SLA researchers to explore their implications in language classrooms (Guerrero Nieto, 2007; Lantolf, 2000).

Probably, one of the closest conceptualisations of the notion of IC that made use of Vygotsky's (1978) notion of mediation is Walsh's (2006; 2011). Walsh (2011, p.158) defined interactional competence as 'teachers' and learners' use of interaction as a tool for mediating and assisting learning'. From the previous definition, it is noticeable that Vygotsky's (1978) concept of mediation surfaced in Walsh's definition of IC, where interaction is considered as a mediating tool firmly put at the centre of teaching and learning to improve both learning and learning opportunities. Similar to Vygotsky, Walsh (2011) drew on the idea of learning as a social activity and underscoring the centrality of the of learners' active involvement, engagement and participation (Walsh, 2011; Larsen-Freeman, 2010).

Another fundamental concept of SCT is the Zone of Proximal Development (ZPD). The ZPD had a significant impact on many areas of research such as developmental psychology, education, and applied linguistics, to name a few (Lantolf, 2000). According to Vygotsky (1978, p.352):

An essential feature of learning is that it creates the zone of proximal development; that is, learning awakens a variety of internal developmental processes that are able to operate only when the child is interacting with people in his environment and cooperation with his peers.

The above quotation indicates that competence and its development primarily lie in partaking in social activities and collaborating with other individuals. The ZPD is compelling to researchers and educators for two main reasons. The first reason is the notion of assisted performance where an individual engages in tackling particular tasks with the assistance of the more experienced individual. The second reason is that ZPD does not only look at the individual current level of development but also asserts that what one can with the assistance and guidance is indicative to his ability to perform independently in the future (Lantolf, 2000, p. 206). The most common definition of ZPD is 'the distance between the actual development level as determined

by independent problem solving and the level of potential development as determined through problem-solving under adult guidance or in collaboration with more capable peers' (Vygotsky, 1978, p.86).

In the classroom context, the ZPD can be viewed as a space where knowledge or learning is co-constructed between novice and expert, that is between teachers and learners and between learners themselves (Kinginger, 2002). Walsh's (2006; 2011; 2012) work on IC explored how teachers and learners might go about creating and maximising learning space. A similar understanding of the learning space creation was also echoed in the field of TESOL in the post-method shift, which will be explored in the upcoming section. For now, there is a need to further our understanding of the notion of IC. This can be achieved through drawing on some of the theoretical frameworks derived from SCT. These theoretical frameworks are somewhat akin to the notion of IC.

As pointed out earlier, Kramsch (1986) referred to successful interaction and IC as participant's joint management of interaction and co-production of knowledge. Jacoby and Ochs (1995, p. 171) referred to it as 'co-construction', that is, 'the joint creation of forms interpretations, stance, action, activity, identity, institution, skill, ideology, emotion, or other culturally meaningful reality' (Jacoby and Ochs, 1995; Young, 2013). A most recent term that resonates with IC is what McCarthy (2005) refers to as co-fluency, that is individuals' collaborative effort to make spoken language fluent with another speaker. The notion of IC resonates with other concepts that made use of the concept of dialogue. This includes Dialogic Teaching approach developed by Alexander (2000), and other concepts such as Jerome Bruner's (1996) mutualist and dialectical pedagogy, the form of dialogic inquiry explored by Wells (1999), Littleton and Mercer's (2013) notion of inter-thinking, that is, spoken language is the primordial medium that enables to people to inter-think creatively in a collaborative setting, and more. A common thread that runs through all the concepts mentioned above is the idea that learning and knowledge are socially situated and jointly co-constructed between individuals.

To summarise, after reviewing the literature on the development of the notion of IC, it became clear that the so-called shift from CC to IC is not as fundamental as it seems. For example, Young (2011) claimed that IC is a totally new notion that differs from

CC as IC views competence as a collective ability rather than the mastery of individual skills can be considered as an overstatement. As explored in section 3.2.2, many fundamental of IC were present within the framework of CC (see, for example, Goffman, 1959; Habermas, 1970; Savignon, 1983). Also, the notion of IC seems to draw a lot on principles of Vygotsky's (1978) SCT. Therefore, there is little evidence to consider this constructivist practice-oriented notion of IC as a completely new notion. Rather, it is a redirection of focus. The review of the literature also leans toward the possibility that the notion of CC might be a misnomer especially when considering the influence of Goffman's (1959) work on interactional competence on Hymes' (1972) theory of CC.

The in-depth review of the literature on IC also revealed that the notion of IC seems to focus on excessively on spoken interaction (Young, 2011; Campbell-Larsen, 2014). Reading and writing were given little attention and considered as secondary abilities (Campbell-Larsen, 2014). However, the initial conceptualisation of the IC did not disregard the dimension of reading and writing. Kramersch (1986) exclusively equated between face-to-face interaction and the reader interaction with a text.

Whether it is face-to-face interaction between two or several speakers, or the interaction between a reader and a written text, successful interaction presupposes...a shared internal context or "sphere of inter-subjectivity" that is built through the collaborative efforts of the interactional partners.

In the above quotation, Kramersch (1986) did not only suggest that speaking and reading are equally important but also equated between the collaborative effort of partners involved in both interactive events. Just like the speaker and the hearer, the reader and writer collaborate in meaning-making and understanding. In her conceptualisation of the notion of IC, Kramersch (1986) emphasised the role of listening. Elsewhere, May (2011) drew attention to the importance of listening for effective interaction.

The excessive emphasis on the spoken interaction also seems to blur other important elements to the notion of IC, for example, the role of non-verbal behaviour in the

operationalisation of IC (Plough et al., 2018). The role of nonverbal behaviour in IC was first addressed by the Kramsch (1986). She suggested that non-verbal cues might be more irritating to native speakers than linguistic inaccuracies.

After exploring the development of the notion of IC, attention now will be turned into exploring the relationships between IC and foreign language teaching methodologies, and how IC related to pedagogies of liberation and emancipation.

3.3. English Language teaching methodologies and interactional competence

TESOL witnessed a multitude of English language teaching methodologies that were founded upon different philosophical currents and theories which occurred first in the context on first language acquisition (FLA) and then transferred into the context of SLA, as explored earlier. From there, each language teaching method or approach seems to emphasis a particular aspect about language teaching and learning depending on the philosophical bend in which the method or the approach is rooted (Kumaravadivelu; 1994).

In theory, the philosophy underpinning a particular teaching method seems at first plausible. However, its application in a foreign language classroom is a totally different matter. Language teaching methods are theories that are developed outside the classroom context. Therefore, transferring them into the classroom presents a significant challenge to practitioners. Simply put, methods devised by theorists do not mimic the reality of language classrooms, and broader socio-cultural context in which these language classrooms are located (Kumaravadivelu, 1994; 2006). Classroom decisions which are informed by teaching materials and ‘methods’ are less likely to promote active learning and students’ active engagements. Therefore, classroom decision should instead be centred around dialogue as the notion of IC and post-method pedagogy posit (Walsh, 2012; Kumaravadivelu, 2001).

An effective pedagogy should depart from putting dialogue at the centre of teacher education programs, which are essentially method-based programs and seldomly include aspects of dialogic interaction, and its importance in the facilitation and creation of learning and learning opportunities in the classroom (Walsh, 2013; Kumaravadivelu; 2001). This would offer the space for teachers’ voices, beliefs,

concerns about ELT teaching to be heard (Kumaravadivelu; 2001). Similarly, teachers also should put dialogic interaction at the centre of their classroom practices as this would give the students the opportunity to voice their wants and needs, as well as other socio-political issues that are of concern to students. The teacher can make use of the students' socio-political awareness to facilitate interaction and learning in the classroom (Walsh; 2006; Kumaravadivelu; 2001).

To promote our understanding of the relationship between the notion of IC and English language teaching methodologies, methods from the Grammar-Translation Method (GTM) up to the communicative language teaching (CLT) are explored. Attention is given to the role of both teachers and learners within each method to show emancipation in foreign language education evolved over time, and how IC relate to the pedagogies of freedom and emancipation, and particularly, to post-method pedagogy.

3.3.1 Grammar translation method

Also known as the classical or the traditional method because it was adopted in the teaching of Greek and Latin. After the decline of Latin in the early 19th century, the method was used in the teaching of foreign languages (Stansfield, 1985; Benati, 2018). There are two main assumptions underlining GTM. The first is the memorization of the grammatical rules. The second is the ability to translate from L1 to L2 and vice versa. GTM is a teacher-centred method; that is, the teacher must assert his authority in the classroom as a knowledge provider (Benati, 2018). The main focus of the method was on writing and reading. Speaking and listening were not given much attention (Benati, 2018; Sierra, 1995). This is the opposite of IC which considers speaking as the main skill and reading and writing as secondary (Campbell-Larsen, 2014). GTM was described as tedious and useless due to its emphasis on memorisation of grammatical rules (Benati, 2018). It also over-emphasises the use of L1 inputs in the learning of target language, and promotes learners' dependency on the teachers' input (Benati, 2018). Communicating in the target language was marginalised (Sierra, 1995). Due to the teacher authoritative role, the interaction was predominantly between the teacher-student (Sierra, 1995; Benati, 2018).

In addition to memorisation, dictation is also another practice that is generally associated with GTM (Stansfield, 1985). Dictation was a very popular tool for teaching and assessment until 1960 when its popularity declined due to the emergence of the ALM (ibid). Despite the decline, dictation is still widely used practice in the Algerian HE context (see Chapter 6, Section 6.4.2).

3.3.2 Audiolingual method

The Audiolingual method (ALM) was predicated on the behaviourist philosophical current. The latter was briefly discussed at the outset of this chapter. Learning was exclusively based on notions such as stimulus, response, repetition, and practice, which found their basis in Skinner's notion of verbal behaviour. The environment was considered as the only significant parameter to successful learning (Larsen-Freeman, 2012). Classrooms were equipped with comfortable seating and arrangements in a bid to minimise or eliminate the stress that accompanies the assimilation of particular target language content (Mart, 2013). Language learners, on the other hand, were viewed as passive, unemancipated, mainly responding to environmental stimuli, that is their role was limited to limited sentence repetition and mimicry after the teacher (Larsen-Freeman, 2012). It was considered necessary for a teacher to stop learners from making a mistake as might lead to the formation of bad habits. The focus of the method is oral communication, and habit formation of native-like speakers through practising basic structures and sentence patterns of the target language, and repeating and memorising dialogues (Mart, 2013; Larsen-Freeman, 2000; Rodgers and Richards; 2014; Savignon, 2017). Larsen-Freeman (2000, p.47-p.50) provided an account of ALM techniques, such as dialogue memorisation, dialogue completion, repetition drills, transformation drills, question and answer drills, among others. These techniques target the teaching of the four skills, listening, speaking, reading and writing respectively (Savignon, 2017).

On the one hand, the method proved to be beneficial in terms of exposing the learners to authentic speech, which helped with improving pronunciation, stress, and rhythm of the target language (Wang, 2017). On the other hand, the method was teacher-centred, mechanistic, unrealistic, and tedious. The mechanistic nature of the method

limited students' creativity and spontaneity for language use. These are common critiques of behaviourist-based methods and approaches. Despite this criticism, Williams and Burden (1997) argued that the method might be of use, especially in contexts where teachers are not provided with an adequate level of professional training, or where teachers have limited knowledge of the target language. This may explain the persistence in the use of ALM in Algeria. As explored in Chapter 2, EFL teachers' level of competence in the target language leaves much to be desired.

3.3.3 Competency-based education

Another language teaching method that is rooted in behaviourist philosophical current is Competence-Based Education (CBE) (Wesselink et al., 2003; Hodkinson and Issitt, 1995; Hodge, 2007). CBE originated in performance-based teacher education in America in the 1960s (Olesen, 1979; Hyland, 1995). Competency-Based Language Teaching (CBLT), which is an example of CBE, focuses on learning outcomes, that is on what learners are expected to do rather than what learners are expected to learn. Competency or competencies refers to any attributes of an individual such as specific knowledge, skills, thinking processes that help with the accomplishment of a particular task at academic settings or otherwise (Richards and Rodgers, 2014). Unlike the ALM, where learners were perceived as passive agents, within the CBLT approach, both teachers and learners are active. EFL teachers act as a guide, needs analysts, assessors, and martial designers. Learners, on the other hand, need to monitor their learning in reference to the target competencies, to develop and be to use different strategies to achieve communication, and to be able to transfer knowledge and skills to new situations (Ibid).

CBE has been used and implemented in various parts of the world including the UK, Asia, Australia, and Algeria, and has numerous models implemented in different countries (Velde, 1999, also cited in Wesselink, 2003). For instance, in Algeria, as explored in Chapter 2, the implementation of CBE disregarded the socio-economic culture, which led to Algerian EFL teachers' resistance to this approach. This is mainly because the approach was ethnocentric and only viewed context in terms of the linguistic and pragmatic feature of language use. Another good example that was impacted by this ethnocentric view is the implementation of the LMD system, and as we have seen the system was implemented on the basis that since the system was

good for Europe, it must also be good for Algeria. Consequently, the implementation of the structure of the LMD system overpowered the implementation of its key pedagogical canons (see Chapter 2).

In the context of language teaching, CBLT was criticised for being prescriptive as learners were prepared to fit the *status quo*. CBE and by extension CBLT were criticised by scholars from different disciplines and received the same criticism as the ALM, that is the approach was viewed as mechanistic and an underestimation of the complexity of human agency (see for example Hyland, 1995; Velde, 1999; Weselink et al., 2003; Barnett 1994; and Hodkinson and Issitt, 1995; Richard and Rogers, 2001). For instance, Barnett (1994) argued that the description of competences on the bases of the behaviourist standpoint, and the detailed level of the description could not provide guidelines for educational curricula. The detailed level of description failed to account for the unscripted and spontaneous nature of human actions. Similar reflections were also echoed by Velde (1999) in the context of vocational education and training who described the approach as narrow as it emphasises predefined skills and ignores other skills such as communication, problem-solving, and group techniques. This is also the consensus within the broader discipline of psychology (Hodkinson and Issitt, 1995).

Velde (1999) dissociated herself from the behaviourist approach, i.e., CBT, and took account of a more holistic and interpretative-rational approach. The latter considers all workplace dimensions, as these have an impact on learning. These dimensions include the individual, the specific context in which the individual is located, work relationships, and the different variations in the level competence (Velde, 1999, p.444). Sandberg (1994) first proposed this approach, which is predicated on the idea that human competence originates from the lifeworld. It thus puts the emphasis on the individual, as well as his or her conceptions and experiences in context for identifying and describing competence (Sandberg, 1994, p.59 as cited in Velde, 1999).

3.3.4 *Communicative language teaching*

The above-mentioned language teaching methods were criticised on two bases, namely on their linear view of language learning inherent in the detailed level of description, and their limited view of context which undermined the wider social,

political, institutional context of the practice. These are also the same grounds upon which CLT and its offshoot Task-Based Approach (TBA) were criticised (Nunan, 2004; Savignon, 1991; Willis, 1996, also cited in. Kumaravadivelu, 2006). In theory, CLT can create and promote a genuinely 'communicative' classroom environment. In fact, in theory, CLT has many fundamental elements in common with the notion of IC. This might be approached through considering the relationships between CC, the theory upon which CLT is founded and IC. As explored in the previous section, many of the fundamentals of the notion of IC were underscored by scholars within the framework of the CC (Savignon, 1983; Canale and Swain, 1980). This included fundamentals such as meaning negotiation, viewing competence in term of social interaction, as well as the spontaneous, creative, and unpredictable use of language. Therefore, by extension, CLT underscores all the aforementioned fundamentals. In fact, CLT fundamentally dealt with the concepts of meaning negotiation, interpretation and expression as well as '...the creative, unpredictable, and purposeful use of language' (Kumaravadivelu; 2006, p.61). However, the communicative curriculum, with its limited prescriptive nature, cannot account for unpredictability and dynamicity of language classrooms (Widdowson, 1990; Kumaravadivelu, 2006).

In addition, in theory, within CLT approach, learners were perceived as active agents in the teaching and learning process. Instead of just reacting to teachers' initiations and making use of memorised patterns and repetitions which characterized the ALM, learners need to engage in meaningful interactive exchanges between their peers and the teachers and initiate speech (Kumaravadivelu, 1993, p.12). In practice, however, CLT failed even among teachers who strictly adhered to its principles, probably because of the mismatch between teachers' intention and learners' interpretation. It is also possible that teachers were not properly equipped with strategies to face the challenges of a communicative environment. More attention was given to developing communicative material, and less attention was given to preparing teachers for the communicative role (Savignon, 1991; Kumaravadivelu; 1993). Therefore, the individual's experience, which was overlooked in CBE approach, was also overlooked in the implementation of CLT. Savignon (1991) and Kumaravadivelu (1993) reprise Auerbach's (1986, p.425) critique of the CBE in ESL, which argued that 'when teaching competences becomes an end itself, students and teachers become an object rather than subjects of the education process.'

To emancipate teachers and learners from the limitation inherent in the method-based pedagogies, a shift was proposed from a method-based pedagogy to post-method pedagogy (PMP). The latter gives firmly put teachers' and learners' beliefs and lived experiences at the centre of teaching and learning process, and views that the role of the teacher is central to the success of this process. Likewise, the notion of IC seems to resonate with many of the principles of PMP in this respect (Kumaravadivelu, 2001; 2006). For example, the teacher within the framework of IC is not only viewed as 'facilitator' but as a creator and maximiser of learning opportunities (Walsh, 2006; 2011; 2012). More commonalities between IC and PMP will be explored below.

3.3.5 Interactional competence and post-method pedagogy

Language teachers and curriculum designers moved away from the idea that there exists only one correct language teaching method towards the consideration of post-method pedagogy. The aim is to emancipate teachers from the limitations inherent in the concept of method and open their eyes to the infinite possibilities of the uncharted water of PMP (Kumaravadivelu, 2001; 2006). It aims at freeing teachers from the emphasis on the western knowledge and ignoring local knowledge, from being prevented and their learners from using their L1 resources, and from the privileged conception of native speakers (Kumaravadivelu, 2003). The use of L1 in FL classrooms proved to be useful in the mastery of the target language, and it all depends on a balanced exposure of L1 and the target language (Kumaravadivelu, 2003; Brevik and Rindal, 2020). As previously noted, PMP seeks to empower teachers with the knowledge, skill, and autonomy to help them generate a pedagogy that is context-sensitive and specific to their lived experiences (Kumaravadivelu, 2001). The notion of IC seems to resonate with many of concepts that are key to PMP such as empowerment, emancipation, and freedom. To explore points of commonality between IC and PMP, there is a need to draw on the main principles of PMP and compare them to the main philosophy pertaining to the notion of IC.

First, PMP is a pedagogy of particularity, that is, 'post method pedagogy must be sensitive to a particular group of teachers teaching a particular group of learners pursuing a particular set of goals within a particular institutional context embedded in a particular socio-cultural milieu' (Kumaravadivelu, 2006, p.171). The philosophy pertaining to the notion of IC is aligned with PMP context-sensitivity parameter. IC

is also context-specific, and it cannot be separated from the sociocultural context in which the interaction is taking place (Tarvin, 2015; Doehler; 2013). The context of the interaction is not only limited to the immediate/micro context of the interaction. Rather, it extends to the broader socio-cultural context with all its dimensions; political, social, institutional, and historical (Young, 2011). In a similar vein, Walsh (2012, p. 12) pointed out that 'interactional competence is highly context-specific both at the social/geographical sense and in the more specific sense context of the moment.' In practice, however, Walsh's (2011; 2012) conceptualisation of the notion of IC mainly focused on the pragmatic features of language and language use and did not consider the political, social, and institutional context of the practice.

Second, PMP is a pedagogy of practicality. It seeks to 'to rupture the reified role relationship between theorists and practitioners' (Kumaravadivelu, 2006, p.69). The latter can be achieved by enabling teachers to theorise from their practice and to practice what they theorise. By the same token, IC is also emancipating to teachers. Similar to Kumaravadivelu (2001; 2006), Kramsch (1986) called for empowering teachers, albeit indirectly, and called for the emancipation of second language education from the ties of ACTFL proficiency guidelines (testers) because they are linear and prescriptive and failed to account for the complexity and dynamic nature of the language learning. Instead of being limited to teaching only what can be tested, teachers are encouraged to teach learners discourse and interactional skills. This will enable foreign language learners to cope with new cultures, new contexts and new life challenges, and to learn how to negotiate ideas and thoughts instead of dictating them (Kramsch, 1986, p.370).

Third, PMP is a pedagogy of possibility which values the socio-political consciousness language learners bring with them into the classroom (Kumaravadivelu, 2006). Within the framework of IC, it is also important that teachers make a reference to the learners' social, cultural and political knowledge in order to maximise interaction opportunities, and boost learners' active participation and engagement (Walsh, 2006).

In addition, akin to PMP, IC also rejects the privileged view of native speakers. Within the framework of IC second and foreign language learners are no longer viewed as 'deficient communicators' where their oral performance are constantly

construed as abysmal compared to native speakers. Rather, IC views foreign language learners as capable interactants who can demonstrate features of IC (Kramersch, 1986; Hall, 2018; Walsh, 2011; 2012). Furthermore, IC emancipated teachers and learners from the oversimplified view of interaction and competence. Within the framework of the IC, interaction is a dynamic and complex phenomenon shared and managed by all participants (Walsh, 2011; Kramersch, 1986; Young, 2011).

In the light of exploring the relatedness of IC to pedagogies of freedom, it is important to draw on some of the macro-strategies introduced by Kumaravadivelu (1994, 2006) within the framework of PMP. These Macro strategies operate through micro strategies or classroom activity designed by teachers.

3.3.6 PMP Macro-strategies and interactional competence

A fundamental macro strategy in PMP is maximising learning opportunities. The latter is very similar to Walsh's notion of maximizing learning space within the framework of IC. Maximising learning opportunities does not only mean that the teacher creates space for learning but also utilises the learning opportunities created by learners. Effective learning opportunities are created when teachers constantly adjust their lesson plans and use of language to the learners' feedback (Walsh, 2011; 2012, Kumaravadivelu, 1994). According to Walsh (2006; 2011; 2012), the use of a language that is convergent to objectives set for that moment is a feature of IC. The language should also be adjusted to the learners' level of understanding and needs, as well as adjusted to promote meaning negotiation to allow for meaning co-construction and the unfolding of the agenda of the lesson. Adjusting language use to a particular pedagogical goal is a mutually shared responsibility between teachers and learners.

Effective learning opportunities are also created when the teacher does not strictly adhere to a particular syllabus. Instead, teachers should have a certain degree of flexibility in adjusting the syllabus to the learners' needs and wants (Kumaravadivelu, 1994). Learning opportunities can also be created through teachers' use of humour to promote students' engagement (Reddington, 2015).

According to Walsh (2006; 2011; 2013), leaning opportunities or space for learning is maximised through the deployment the following performative elements, micro-strategies, or features of *Classroom* Interactional Competence as Walsh referred to them.

- Extension of waiting time: extending the waiting time is one way that enables learners to come up with answers that can be potentially more elaborate. This involves the ability to resist silence and decentre the role of the teacher as the main speaker in classrooms. In so doing, learners would be able to take part in the co-construction of meaning. Moreover, learning space is also maximized through promoting extended learners' turns, allowing planning time and time to repair transient breakdowns in the conveyance of meaning.
- Shaping the learners' contribution: instead of simply reacting to the learners' contributions, teachers would shape an inclusive atmosphere of learning and make much more room for learners to participate widely and more freely. This means the promotion of the learners' initiation rather than relying on tradition interaction sequences, where teachers initiate, learners contribute, and teachers provide feedback. Shaping the learning contributions involves not merely accepting what the learners say and doing something with it. It also involves enabling learners to elaborate upon their contributions and extending them to open more space for them to take part in the discussion. This would unearth new aspects of learning as it champions the heterogeneous feature of classroom interaction. Shaping the learners' contribution can be achieved using paraphrasing, scaffolding, and reiterating.
- Seeking clarification: requesting clarification is a fundamental interactional strategy, the primary role of which is to ascertain that understanding is established.
- Repair: teachers are responsible for understanding errors and making the necessary adjustments, depending on the degree of urgency, i.e. the extent to which they disrupt the flow of communication. In cases in which the error does not affect the way communication is taking

place, and it is not central to the pedagogical goal of the moment, it would be better if it were overlooked, as it does not hamper communication.

- Minimal response token: this shows that understanding is taking place without disrupting the flow of interaction. This includes the use of expression such as ‘right’, ‘OK’ and ‘hmm’. According to Walsh (2013), this shows that language use is convergent with the pedagogic goal of the moment.
- Content feedback provision: feedback remains an instrumental aspect of classroom interaction. Content feedback is responding to the message and not merely to the linguistic forms that are used to articulate the message.

Creating more space for learning entails creating more opportunities for student-student interaction and teacher-student negotiated interaction (Walsh, 2011; Kumaravadivelu, 1994; 2006, Kramsch, 1986). Promoting negotiated interaction is also another commonality between IC and PMP. On this note, Walsh (2012, p.6) maintained that learners need to be offered opportunities to participate in discourse and to receive feedback on their contributions. This does not mean ‘handing over’ turn to learners, but rather encouraging learners to engage in meaning negotiation and co-construction.

To facilitate negotiated interaction, learners should be encouraged to initiate talk. They also should be actively engaged in clarification, confirmation, comprehension checks and turn-taking (Kumaravadivelu, 1994; Walsh, 2006). Negotiated interaction is promoted through creating small group activities, and through the teacher asking referential questions (debatable questions) rather than display questions (questions for checking knowledge). Negotiated interaction can also be promoted by giving the opportunity to choose and manage topics of discussions (Walsh, 2011; 2012, Kumaravadivelu, 1994; 2001). For example, students should be encouraged to bring topics from internet and discuss them in the classroom (Kumaravadivelu, 2001). However, this practice might have an impact on the nature of power relations in contexts where power is of hierarchical structure as might be viewed as a threat to teachers’ authority (Alshahrani et al., 2017)

Another macro strategy which is fundamental in PMP is promoting learners' autonomy. For learners to maximise their learning potentials, they need to be autonomous, that is, to take charge of their own learning (Kumaravadivelu, 2001). Learners' autonomy is vital in PMP, and it is as important as teachers' autonomy. Learners' autonomy encompasses both their social and academic autonomy. Academic autonomy is mostly intrapersonal, where learners need to be able to identify and develop their learning strategies and styles, evaluate their learning outcomes, and extend their learning beyond the classroom (Kumaravadivelu, 2001). Social autonomy is interpersonal and encourages learners to be a cooperative member of the classroom community. The latter involves learners to ask dialogically for further feedback from the teacher and communicating and interacting with more experienced peers.

Apart from academic and social autonomy, there is another third type of autonomy; 'liberatory' autonomy. This is where teachers assist and provide their learners with intellectual tools to recognise socio-political obstacles so that learner achieves their full potential (Kumaravadivelu, 2001, p. 546-547). The notion of IC also promotes learner autonomy in the classroom, probably not with the broad conception of autonomy presented in the post-method pedagogy. Learners have the opportunity to exercise their autonomy through topic selection, topic management, negotiating meaning with their teachers and peers, as well as promoting classroom discussions through building on their classmates' contributions (Walsh 2012; Campbell-Larsen, 2014).

Furthermore, within the framework of PMP and IC, teachers are no longer simply viewed as teachers, and learners as only learners because both are equally responsible for the good and ill of classroom management (Allwright, 1984; Kumaravadivelu, 2006; Walsh, 2012). Then by extension, the pursuit of learners' autonomy should also be viewed as a collective endeavour, mutually and equally shared by both teachers and learners. Therefore, teachers' also need to be autonomous in order to promote learners to become autonomous.

3.3.7 Teachers' autonomy and interactional competence

Teachers' autonomy means that teachers need to be free from the constraints inherent in the concept of method and to theorise from their own practice. For teachers to generate their theory of practice, they need to have a reasonable degree for competence, confidence, and autonomy (Kumaravadivelu, 2001). Teachers' autonomy lies at the heart of the post-method pedagogy, and it is nurtured by teachers reflecting on their practices, and continuously working on their self-development. In order to improve their practices, and respond to learners' wants and needs, teachers, need to be able to do their own classroom research. This does not mean engaging in very sophisticated inquiries for which teachers have neither the time nor the energy. It suffices for the teachers to keep their eyes, ears and minds open to what is unfolding in the classroom, and to be attentive to what is working and what is not (Kumaravadivelu, 2001). In terms of tools for investigation, teachers, for example, can use questionnaires, surveys, and interviews to collect information about their learners' learning strategies and styles, identities, anxieties, and socio-political concerns (Kumaravadivelu, 2001, p. 550).

Since learners' autonomy is contingent on teachers' autonomy, then the development of the learners' interactional competence is also contingent on teachers' development of IC. Therefore, teachers need to understand and develop their own IC through continuously reflecting on their classroom interaction experience (Walsh, 2006; 2011; 2012; 2013). Walsh (2006) developed a framework called SETT (Self-Evaluation of Teacher Talk) so that teachers will be able to evaluate and improve their classroom interaction experience. SETT proved to be useful in raising teachers' awareness about their use of language in the classroom and the extent to which it is convergent to the pedagogical goals of the moment. The SETT framework is based on four assumptions. First, all L2 classroom discourse is goal-oriented, and the prime responsibility of the establishment and the shaping of interaction falls on the teacher. Second, pedagogic purpose and language use are inextricably intertwined. Third, any higher education L2 classroom context is made up of a series of micro contexts or modes. These are associated with the social, political, cultural and historical beliefs of the participants. Finally, micro contexts or modes are constructed by teachers and learners through participation, face-to-face meaning-making and the process of

language socialisation (Walsh, 2006; Seedhouse, 2004; Bowles and Seedhouse, 2007; Ädel and Reppen, 2008).

Zotzmann (2018) conducted a study which aimed at exploring the viability and utility of Walsh's (2006) SETT framework for foreign language teachers' professional development. Four in-service Spanish teachers in Mexico made use of Walsh's (2006) SETT framework to analyse their classroom interaction practices and language use. The participants were interviewed after the analyses of their classroom transcript to reflect on their classroom behaviour and decision. The study revealed several limitations of Walsh's (2006) SETT framework. Some of the participants could not fit their micro-classroom mode into any of the classroom modes presented by Walsh (2006) in his SETT framework. In addition, during the interview phases, the participants were frequently referring to factors outside the classroom that had an impact on their behaviour and interactive decision in the classroom, including conditions in the institution and relationships. Zotzmann (2018) concluded that the framework is useful, however, it could benefit from including aspects beyond the classroom context such as institutional practices, interpersonal relationships and the socioeconomic realities in which a particular practice is taking place (Zotzmann, 2018).

Therefore, the distinction between theory and practice also had its influence on reflective teaching and action research (Kumaravadivelu, 2001), including Walsh's (2006) SETT framework. Teachers' reflection on their classroom practice is merely perceived in term of teachers reflecting on what is happening in their classrooms in relation to particular or a set of theorist-theories (ibid). However, teachers' self-conceptualisation and self-construction of pedagogical knowledge are ignored (ibid). Their sense and decision making, which are greatly influenced by their beliefs and experiences are completely disregarded in the process. The next section will provide a detailed discussion of the role of teachers' beliefs in their classroom practices and decision-making processes. Exploring teachers' beliefs in relation to the performative element of IC and its implementation in their classrooms might give us some illuminating insights about their own theories of practice, and about the practicality of these performative elements in their language classrooms (see Chapters 5 and 6).

3.4 The role of teachers' beliefs

In recent decades, the study of beliefs has attracted considerable interest within a variety of fields of inquiry including medicine, law, anthropology, political science, business and education (Pajares, 1992). The advancement of research in cognitive psychology, as well as in ethnographic and qualitative research fuelled the enthusiasm and interest of many researchers to explore teachers' cognition (Fang, 1996; Zheng, 2015). In particular, the teaching process involves two major dimensions. One concerns teachers' observable behaviour, and by extension, this includes teachers' interactive practice, use of language and so on, and the other dimension concerns teachers' thoughts and processes which are unobservable (Clark and Peterson, 1986). These epistemic beliefs play a key role in the construction of knowledge and explain how teachers make sense of the world around them (Borg, 2015, p.8).

Pedagogies of freedom and emancipation recognises the complexity of teachers' beliefs and the important role they play in shaping teachers' classroom practices. Teachers are viewed as active decision-makers, and not absorbers and 'mechanical implementers of external prescriptions' (Kumaravadivelu, 2006; Borg, 2015). They are 'not empty vessels waiting to be filled with theoretical and pedagogical skills' (Freeman and Johnson, 1998, p.401). Teachers are the ones who are in terrain of teaching and learning, not theorists. They are continuously interacting with various complexities such as learners and their learning styles and individual variables, and the complexity of EFL learning. Teachers are also the one who deal with the challenges they encounter in their day-to-day teaching (Kumaravadivelu; 1994). Therefore, the facilitation of the social interaction and improvement of teaching and learning should depart from gaining understanding of the histories and lived experiences of teachers, as well as learners in a particular institutional and socio-cultural context (Norton, 2000, p.142 as cited in Kumaravadivelu, 2006, p.71). As will be demonstrated in Chapters 5 and 6, teachers' interactive practices are greatly influenced by their own formative educational experiences and their own personal theories about teaching and learning which were shaped by various contextual factors (see Chapters 5 and 6).

The exploration of the theoretical underpinnings of attitudes and beliefs is important to the understanding of teachers' thought, thought processes, classroom practices, change, and learning to teach (Richardson, 1996). The notion of teachers' beliefs, as it were, belongs to a broader concept, namely teachers' cognition (Borg, 2003; 2015). The latter focuses on what language teachers' think, know, and believe rather than on how they behave.

The literature review on the notion of IC revealed an excessive emphasis on the study of observable behaviour. The latter was evident in the imbalance within the field of SLA, where conversational analysis (CA) dominates the exploration the classroom interaction routines, and discursive/interactive practices (Hall, 2018). As a result, the individuals' beliefs and experiences have been given relatively little attention within this area of inquiry. Research has identified many factors that affect teachers' decisions and behaviour. These range from the social environment to formal training among others, yet teachers' epistemic beliefs tend to be the most influential factor (Gill & Hoffman, 2009; Pajares, 1992; Goodman, 2005; Speer, 2005; Thompson, 1992, Kumaravadivelu, 200; Borg (2003), and IC is not exempted from this influencing phenomenon. This is the very reason that motivated this research in the first place.

The exploration of this notion, that is, teachers' beliefs is a challenging and complex task. The complexity of this notion lies in the fact that there does not exist a single consistent, and an overall encompassing definition of the term. This complexity arises from an ongoing debate about what is considered as beliefs and what is considered as knowledge. There is also an inconsistency between beliefs and practices. This means it is not always the case that individuals demonstrate behaviour that goes hand in hand with their beliefs.

3.4.1 Teachers' beliefs versus teachers' knowledge

Much of the current debate revolves around the distinction between belief and knowledge. In reviewing the literature of traditional philosophy, it is common to refer to knowledge as based on truth conditions. Green (1971, p.69) pointed out that beliefs and knowledge are very similar and, seemingly, truth condition is what distinguishes them from one another. These truth conditions compel individuals and communities

to accept this knowledge as true. On the other hand, beliefs do not require truth conditions.

From the perspective of contemporary analytical philosophy of mind, the term belief is often used to refer to what we take and regard as true. Generally, contemporary philosophers refer to beliefs as propositional attitudes: the mental state of having some attitude, stance, take or opinion about a proposition or the potential state of affairs in which that proposition is true (Cheyne, 2001; Schwitzgebel, 2006). From the perspective of educational psychology, Raths and McAninch, (2003) claimed that there often is no difference between the two.

In the fields of educational psychology, psychologists often consider beliefs and knowledge to be intertwined (Pajares, 1992). It is not possible to speak of one without mentioning the other. Beliefs are defined in terms of knowledge, or more accurately 'personal knowledge' (Kagan, 1992). Kagan (1992) argued that most of the teachers' professional knowledge could be considered as beliefs (ibid).

Pajares (1992), a British educational psychologist, concluded that teachers' beliefs are more influential than teachers' knowledge in many ways: lesson planning and decision making; this incorporates interactional decisions and classroom practices in general. This is suggestive of the fact that there is a clear-cut distinction between teachers' beliefs and teachers' knowledge. However, this distinction seems to be more complex than it actually appears. Having the property of being culturally bound, teachers' beliefs, as a concept, demonstrate a certain complexity in terms of what they mean. No clear definition of both terms, which would enable us to set a distinction between beliefs and knowledge, is existent.

Pajares (1992) contended that beliefs are based on evaluation and judgement, whereas knowledge is anchored on objective facts. He further adds that the notion of the knowledge is closer to the truth than beliefs, yet suggesting that knowledge and beliefs can be similar as both are open for scepticism, evaluation and judgement. The use of terminology like 'closer' does not imply a definite state of truthfulness. In this respect, Nilsson (2014, p. xii) maintained that it is impossible to distinguish beliefs from knowledge in a meaningful qualitative way because it is impossible to tell 'whether or not a sentence or a set of them represent reality faithfully'.

Nespor (1987) advanced another distinction between beliefs and knowledge. He discussed beliefs in terms of how they are stored and where they reside in memory. According to Nespor (1987) 'knowledge system information' is semantically stored, whereas beliefs are stored in the episodic memory. He also suggested that beliefs originate from past episodes, events, and experiences, which in turn would affect the upcoming events in terms of comprehension. These past episodes and experiences, which are involved in the formation of certain beliefs, can become a prototype for teachers' practices. Similarly, Crawford (2007, p. 590) argued that beliefs 'are highly subjective, have a significant emotional component, include attitudes, and are derived from significant episodes that one experiences.'

Nespor (1987, p.321), furthermore, differentiated between beliefs and knowledge in terms of appropriateness and validity. In contrast to the system of knowledge, belief systems do not require a general or communal consensus regarding their appropriateness and validity. Knowledge can be evaluated and critically examined; beliefs, however, cannot. Moreover, a system is defined and mostly perceived as receptive to reason, unlike the system of beliefs, which might defy logic and trespass the realm of concrete reality. Having said that, beliefs are still held to be more influential than knowledge in terms of how individuals organize tasks and define problems. Beliefs can strongly anticipate or generate behaviour.

Moreover, a significant number of researchers regarded beliefs and knowledge as inextricably intertwined. Alexander et al. (1991, p. 317), for example, argued that the term knowledge encompasses 'all that a person knows or believes to be true, whether or not it is verified as true in some sort of objective or external way'. Likewise, Angeli et al. (2015) advocated the idea that beliefs and knowledge are intertwined: beliefs, however, involve emotionality while knowledge implies cognition. As regards this very link between beliefs and knowledge, (Nilsson, 2014) pointed out that beliefs constitute a large part of our knowledge of the world; not knowing, thus, implies not believing. He referred to beliefs as theories, and that is formed through every experience. Similarly, Larenas et al. (2015) argued that beliefs depend upon teachers' experiences.

To sum up, beliefs refer to what is held by the individual as true. Although several researchers distinguished between beliefs and knowledge, the relationship between

the two is inextricably interlaced. Due to the absence of a clear cut between what constitutes belief and what constitutes knowledge, it is difficult to provide an exact definition of the beliefs.

3.4.2 *Definition of teachers' beliefs*

Many researchers provided different definitions of beliefs. The educational psychologist Pajares' (1992) critique and evaluation of research on teachers' beliefs is by far the most cited one. For Pajares (1992), the notion of beliefs is a messy construct. This 'messiness' is due to 'definitional problems, poor conceptualisation, and differing understanding of beliefs and beliefs structures' (Pajares, 1992, p.307). Due to this messiness, there does not exist a single unanimous, all-encompassing definition of the term (Pajares, 1992; Fraser et al., 2012). In consideration of the absence of a solid definition, Pajares (1992) suggested that it is of central importance for researchers to define what they mean by beliefs. Thus, defining beliefs is 'at best a game of players' choice' (ibid, p.309).

There is a wide range of terminologies used to refer to the notion of teacher's beliefs. The study of teachers' beliefs was highly affected by educational psychology. Within the aforementioned field, constructs were not treated with precision nor consistency. These consisted of terminologies, such as attitudes, perceptions, conceptions, opinions, judgments, values, dispositions, and perspectives (Pajares, 1992). All of the aforementioned terms were almost used interchangeably (ibid).

Clandinin and Connelly (1987, p.487) also reached similar findings. In their exploration of origins, uses, and meaning of *personal knowledge construct* in studies of teachers' beliefs, they were baffled at the multitude of the terms used. In addition to their own term 'personal practical knowledge', their list included teachers' criteria, principles of practices, personal constructs, personal theories, teachers' conceptions, teachers' perspectives, among others (Pajares, 1992, Clandinin and Connelly, 1987).

The main reason for the existence of this vast array of different terms is that the study of beliefs has been affected by different research agendas (Pajares, 1992; Eisenhart et al., 1988; Kagan, 1992). This is very much similar to what we have noticed in the review on the development of the notion of competence (see Section 3.2). Within this

regard, beliefs can be defined as people's manipulation of knowledge for particular purposes and under certain conditions (Abelson, 1979). Beliefs have also been defined as 'any simple proposition, conscious or unconscious, inferred from what a person says or does, capable of being preceded by the phrase "I believe that" ...' (Rokeach, 1968, p.113).

For Harvey (1986), beliefs are individual representations of reality that are credible, true and valid enough to guide thought and behaviour. Kagan (1992) in her review of teachers' belief studies and methodology, pointed out that beliefs are often broadly defined as 'unconsciously held assumptions about students, classrooms and academic materials' (Kagan, 1992, p. 65). She concluded that 'the more one reads studies about teacher beliefs, the more strongly one suspects that this piebald form of personal knowledge lies at the very heart of teaching' (ibid, p.85).

Following Pajares' (1992) suggestion that it is of central importance for researchers to define what they mean by belief due to the lack of a definite, all-encompassing definition. In this study, the term 'belief' refers to everything that is held by teachers as true, whether it be a belief, an opinion, or even knowledge. By virtue of the openness and inclusiveness, the term 'teachers' perspectives' is adopted in this study. Teachers' perspectives about IC in the Algerian context encompass all the aforementioned terms. The next section will turn attention to the relationship between teachers' beliefs and classroom practices.

3.4.3 The relationship between teachers' beliefs and classroom practices

There is growing evidence that teachers' beliefs exert a powerful influence on teachers' practices (Borg; 2001, Borg, 2006; Borg, 2003, Levin et al., 2013; Levin et al., 2010; Kumaravadivelu; 2001; 2006). For example, Borg (2001, p.186) argues that a belief is 'a proposition which may be consciously or unconsciously held, is evaluative in that it is accepted as true by the individual, and is therefore imbued with emotive commitment; further, it serves as a guide to thoughts and behaviour'. Along the same lines, Zanting et al. (2001) emphasised that in contrast to knowledge, a belief is held both consciously or unconsciously and plays a preponderant role in propelling individuals to make sense of the world, affects how new information is perceived, and shapes individuals' behaviours.

In addition, Goodman (2005, p. 305) ascribed actions to the kind of beliefs individuals hold, and he maintained that 'Beliefs determine actions because they can be expressed as conditional expectations; we expect that certain sensible result will follow particular actions and can thus know how to act if we want that sensible result.' Hence, the achievement of certain sensible results is preconditioned by the existence of a conditional expectation that would enable us to decide on a particular way of acting and thereby bring those expectations to fruition.

Larenas et al. (2015, p. 172) explain, 'beliefs guide teachers' behaviour and inform teachers' practice by serving as a kind of interpretative framework through which they made sense of what they do in their classrooms.' Thus, tracing and understanding the roots and sources of these beliefs within a particular cultural and social milieu is fundamentally important should we wish to enhance teachers' reflective practice and as well as the efficiency of school administrators and mentors.

The exploration of the relationship between teachers' beliefs and practices is not a novel inquiry. For example, Fang's (1996) review demonstrated both consistency and inconsistency between teacher beliefs and practices. In the last two decades, research on teacher belief and classroom practices yielded similar results. Particularly, in the field of language teaching, Basturkmen (2012) review showed both correspondence and lack of correspondence between teachers' beliefs and practice. The majority of studies, however, showed limited correspondence. The review also concluded that consistency between teachers' beliefs and practices were more common amongst more experienced teachers. Nevertheless, there were some reservations with the quality of Basturkmen's (2012) review. Many of the doctoral theses used in the review were unpublished, and this had raised the question about the quality of selection criteria employed (Borg, 2018).

There were some studies where teacher beliefs seem to correspond with their actual classroom practices. For example, Ng and Farrell (2003) study explored the relationship between teachers of grammar beliefs and classroom practices. The study revealed some consistencies between what teachers say and what they actually do. Similarly, in a small-scale study, Farrell and Lim's (2005, p.8) findings suggested that 'teachers' beliefs are the best indicators of the type of instructional decisions they made during their teaching.'

The most recent review of empirical studies that explored the relationship between teachers' beliefs and practices revealed four types of relationships. (a) Beliefs influences practices (b) Practice influences beliefs (c) Belief and practices are separate (d) The relationship between belief and practices are reciprocal (Buehl and Beck, 2014). The reciprocal relationship between beliefs and practices represent the complex fashion by which beliefs and practice interact during teachers' career (Borg, 2018). For example, Zheng (2015), who looked at teachers' beliefs through the lens of complexity theory, argued that the relationship between teachers' beliefs and practices is complex and dynamic, reciprocal. Zheng (2015) further argued that the interaction between the two is context-bound; that is, context mediates between beliefs and practices (Borg, 2006; Zheng, 2015).

In terms of the discrepancies between teachers' beliefs and practices, there are numerous factors that often impede teachers from putting their beliefs into practice, both internal and external (Borg, 2018; Fives and Gill, 2014). Internal factors include teachers' biography, personality trait, experience, motivation, self-awareness and self-reflection (ibid). External factors include contextual factors that related to the context the classroom such as students' abilities and attitudes, classroom management, and class size, as well as institutional factors with include curricular policy, curriculum, and time (Borg, 2003; 2006; 2018; Fives and Gill, 2014). Similarly, Larenas et al. (2015, p. 173) indicated that beliefs are often influenced by social, institutional and physical settings and all of which eventually bear on teachers' classroom performances.

Fang (1996, p. 53) suggested that 'contextual factors can have a powerful influence on teachers' beliefs and, in effect, affect their classroom practice.' Particularly, in the area of foreign language classroom interaction, the findings of a small-scale study conducted by Walsh (2011) unearthed the existence of a complex and personal relationship between teachers' beliefs and practices which are closely related to the contextual factors. In light of this complexity, Walsh (2011, p. 53) described the relationship between teacher beliefs and practices as 'symbiotic', that is, beliefs are shaped by and shape subsequent interactions. The description echoes mainstream educational research findings (Foss and Kleinsasser, 1996, p.441; Walsh, 2011). Elsewhere, Farrell and Lim (2005) argued that teachers have a complex belief system

that is not reflected in their classroom due to contextual constraints imposed by the school administration, and parents.

Further understanding of the complexity of teachers' belief can be approached through exploring their different sources. The exploration for these sources would enable for an in-depth exploration of the teachers' and learners' beliefs about IC and various sources that inform, particularly, their classroom interaction practices.

3.4.4 Sources of teachers' beliefs

Beliefs can be associated, to a great extent, with cultural aspects. Pajares (1992) contended that teachers' educational beliefs are developed through the process of cultural transmission. Tao and Juliang (1999) adopted quite a similar stance in this regard and concluded that the sources of teachers' beliefs originate from self-construction and cultural interaction. Tao and Juliang (1999) concluded that beliefs are individual and unique but are also often shared among individuals that belong to the same socio-cultural context. As Nguyen (2013, p. 17) explained, 'beliefs entail knowledge which constitutes shared beliefs in a community (see also Ball and Tyson, 2011). Nguyen further argued that 'beliefs are social, cultural, but also individual, unique but also shared' (ibid). The understanding of how beliefs are deeply embedded in culture and transmitted through it depends on how we define culture per se. Fullinwider and MacLean (1996) and Wren (2012) define culture as transmitted behavioural patterns, which include beliefs, values, customs and perceptions.

With regards to the sources of teachers' beliefs, Fives and Gill (2014) pointed out that identifying these sources can determine whether those beliefs are subject to change or not. Teachers' beliefs serve as a sort of knowledge for teaching, a knowledge rooted in various sources: external such as formalised knowledge and internal like personal experiences. Johnson (1994) argued that teachers' beliefs arise from a certain perceptual image of formal and/or informal language learning experience, the teachers' self-image, as well as the teachers' preparation programs. Similarly, Richardson (1996) identified three categories of experiences that have a bearing on the development of teachers' beliefs and knowledge vis-à-vis teaching: their personal experience, their experience with schooling and instruction, and their experience with formal knowledge (Richardson, 1996; Farrell, 2015; Pawlak, 2016; Agudo, 2014)

Richards and Lockhart (1996) also argued that teachers' personal experiences with L2 learning shape their very beliefs on teaching (Richards and Lockhart, 1996; Zheng, 2015). In contrast, Bruner (1996) stressed that teachers' beliefs lie in what he dubbed folk pedagogy, which refers to beliefs that one holds based on the perception and expectation of what characterises a good teacher. Richards and Lockhart (1996) further list the teachers' consistent classroom practices and actions that arise from their presumption of what works best for them. Moreover, teachers' personalities have a significant influence on their own beliefs. Richards and Lockhart (1996) argue that teachers tend to be more inclined towards the use of teaching methods and strategies which coordinate with their personality.

To sum up, there are three main sources of teachers' beliefs: their own experiences, experience with schooling and instruction as well as practical teaching experience. In our bid to probe the impact of teachers' beliefs on IC in the Algerian HE EFL classrooms, the investigation will revolve around these three interrelated experiences. Now, attention will be turned into exploring the methodology for the study.

Chapter 4: Methodology

4.1 Introduction

The present chapter provides details of the methodology used in this research project in order to put flesh on the bare bones of the brief overview provided in Chapter 1 (Section 1.4). The chapter begins by giving a brief account of the epistemological and ontological underpinnings of the study. Then, it proceeds to discuss the research design employed in this PhD study. This chapter also presents the methods of data collection, namely the use of semi-structured interviews with EFL teachers in a HE setting and focus groups with students.

Readers are reminded that the broad purpose of the study was to explore the notion of IC in the Algerian HE context through the lens of Algerian EFL teachers' and learners' perspectives and experiences. The present chapter provides details of the sample of the study, the procedures by which participants were recruited, and a full account of the ethical considerations that governed the study. These extend beyond mere compliance with ethical guidelines and include considerations about my positionality as a researcher who conducted both his undergraduate and Masters study in the host institution. I conclude by explaining how the data were analysed within the framework of a constructivist/interpretivist paradigm.

4.2 Research paradigm

As Creswell (2007) explains, a paradigm is a lens through which the world is viewed, and knowledge is filtered. It comprises a set of philosophical beliefs about the nature of social reality (ontology) and how knowledge is created, acquired and communicated (epistemology) (Creswell 2015; Creswell and Creswell; 2017). There are many worldviews or research paradigms, and these vary from one research to another depending on the nature of the study, research questions, and research objectives. There is the positivist world view, constructivist (usually combined with interpretivist) worldview, the transformative worldview, and the pragmatic worldview (Creswell and Creswell, 2017).

The present research adopts a constructivist/interpretivist research paradigm in order to respond to the research questions and to achieve the research objectives (see Chapter 1, Section 1.3). Particularly, the constructivist/interpretivist research paradigm is viewed as a research approach to qualitative research. Within this research paradigm, the researchers seek the understanding of a particular phenomenon in the world in which they live and work (Creswell and Creswell, 2017). The researcher relies extensively on the participants' subjective meanings, views and their lived experiences in order to understand a phenomenon. This provides a more complex picture of a situation or a phenomenon being investigated than would be possible solely by ascribing meaning derived from other sources, such as relevant research literature.

The constructivist/interpretivist research paradigm is predicated upon the view that the researcher cannot be separated from the research process (Robson, 2002). The engagement of the researcher in a particular research project will inevitably influence the results. Therefore, the constructivist/interpretivist paradigm, as opposed to for example the positivist paradigm, rejects the idea of the existence of an 'objective reality' and aims to understand the world as it is experienced and made meaningful by human beings (Collins, 2018, p. 39). In a way, this view of reality might carry the assumption that interpretivism is a subjective philosophy, that is, we make sense of the world around us, through our theories, perceptions, beliefs and interpretations. Our social reality is constructed through our interactions with others and with the material world, both of which are embedded in a particular culture. Positivists reject such view of reality and believe that there is a social reality, a reality 'out there', that is independent of our interpretations and perceptions (Mill, 2010, p. 701). Interpretivists find this claim unintelligible, at the same time they take no issue with the existence of a reality 'out there'. In fact, what is not 'out there' is the interpretation of that reality. In this sense, reality is viewed as something that is constructed rather than something that is discovered (Given, 2008, p.460).

The constructivist/interpretivist research approach is viewed as appropriate for this research for several reasons:

First, it reflects the researcher's view about the nature of social reality and 'knowing'. He particularly believes in the existence of multiple realities that dependent on participants and context, and that 'knowledge' is constructible and not discoverable.

Second, the constructivist/interpretivist views on the nature of social reality and knowledge are consonant with the nature of the notion of IC, which as was made clear in Chapter 3 is multifaceted and context-specific (Walsh, 2006; Young, 2011; Hall, 2018). It is also consonant with the nature of the study as a whole, which as explored in Chapter 3, rejects rigid categorisation and limited conceptions of human interaction, and aims at developing more complex meanings of the phenomenon of IC through obtaining participants' views and lived experiences.

Next, the constructivist /interpretivist paradigm is adopted in this study because it relates to the nature of the questions and objectives of the study (see Chapter 1 Section 1.3). The latter primarily foreground the participants' views and their lived experiences, which, as explored above, lies at the heart of the constructivist/interpretivist research paradigm (Creswell and Creswell, 2017).

In addition, within the constructivist/interpretivist paradigm, the researcher tends to be actively involved in the research process, including in the stages of data collection and analysis (Robson, 2002). My PhD inquiry necessitated my active involvement in the research process in order to explore the participants' perspectives and experiences with the notion of IC.

Furthermore, the constructivist/interpretivist paradigm is considered appropriate as the data for this PhD study was collected in a natural environment. Therefore, face-to-face interaction between the researcher and the research participants was necessary to probe the participants' beliefs and experiences vis-à-vis the notion of IC.

This research is exploratory rather than being prescribed or fixed like the positivist research approach (Robson, 2002). This research did not start from a number of hypotheses that need to be tested or a clearly defined problem. Rather, a research design was developed with a specific focus on the conceptualisation IC in the Algerian HE context.

4.3 Research design

This research study made use of qualitative research design. Qualitative research studies, in general, follow the same procedures and contain the same elements found in scientific research. Like most research, it begins by identifying a problem or gap in the literature, examining the literature, posing the questions, setting the objectives, gathering data, analysing the data, and finally writing the final the report (Creswell, 2007). This PhD study also followed the same steps, that is, the steps of the scientific method.

In particular, this study began by identifying the problem in literature around the notion of interactional competence (IC). This is evident in the insufficient attention to participants' beliefs and lived experiences, as well as the limited conception of the notion of context prevalent in research that explored the notion of IC. As argued in Chapter 3, such research focused mainly on the micro context of interaction and overlooked the impact of the broader socio-cultural context on the performative element of IC. Accordingly, the present study was designed to address the aforementioned gap in the literature through exploring the notion of IC in one of the under-researched contexts, that is, the Algerian higher education context. The researcher explored some of the historical, institutional, economic features of the context that might have a direct bearing on the objectives of the study. Rigorous attention was given to the concepts of power, and how it was exercised throughout the history of the country, at the social, institutional, and classroom level (see Chapter 2).

The identification of the gap in the literature led the researcher to engage in an in-depth review of the literature on the notion of IC. This review uncovered a series of misunderstanding, misidentifications, and a sense of ambiguity surrounding IC. The literature review also encompassed reviewing the literature of the notion of teachers' beliefs, and the role they play shaping teachers' classroom practices, and in the present study the operationalisation of IC (see Chapter 3).

After reviewing the literature, the researcher formulated the questions and set up the objectives of the study (see Chapter 1 Section 1.3). In qualitative research, good research questions allow for adaptation and modification, which demonstrates an

increased understanding of the problem (Croswell, 2007; Swaminathan and Mulvihill, 2017). Similarly, the research questions and objectives of this PhD study evolved and changed as the researcher conducted the study, particularly the impact of the power dimension in the operationalisation of the notion of the IC became more evident. The questions and objectives of the study are found in Chapter 1, Section 1.3.

The main reason for adopting a qualitative research design is its appropriateness for exploring Algerian EFL teachers' and learners' perspectives and experiences with the notion of IC, and its performative elements, as well as the participants' views on power relations and their impact of the operationalisation of the performative elements of IC. The researcher opted for an exploratory study design because there are no published works that investigated the notion of IC in the Algerian higher education context, or research that explored the notion of the IC within the broader socio-cultural context. Therefore, an exploratory case study design is appropriate and flexible enough so that it is possible to develop a research design that mainly looks at the conceptualisation of the notion of IC in the Algerian higher education context (Yin, 2015).

Having provided details for the research pertaining to the study, attention now will be given to the research methods.

4.4 Research methods

Interviews are one of the most common and powerful research methods used within the qualitative research realm. This research made use of two primary methods of data collection; individual interviews and focus group interviews. Both interviews were used to draw on Algerian EFL teachers' and learners' perspectives and experiences with the notion of IC in the context.

Interviews are of a different variety ranging from unstructured to fully structured. For the purpose of this study, in-depth semi-structured individual interviews were conducted with 10 Algerian EFL teachers, three men and six women, with different levels of experience in a HE setting (see Appendix A for interview schedule). This type of interview is sufficiently structured to explore a particular topic related to a particular phenomenon, in this case, IC. Semi-structured interviews also provide

some flexibility, as the participants have the opportunity to give new meanings and insights to the focus of the study (Galletta, 2013, p.24). The interview questions were developed specifically to probe on the teachers' own beliefs, and experiences, and the meanings they make of them to inform their conception of the notion under study within the Algerian HE context.

The second research method used in this study was focus group interviews. These interviews were conducted with Algerian EFL learners, where two groups of six and ten learners were interviewed (i.e. 16 students in total). The questions of the interviews were developed to probe the learners' views on the quality of interaction; their experiences and beliefs relating to IC; the way interaction took place; their views about their teachers' feedback on their contributions; and their perspectives on factors that might impede the development of their IC (see Appendix B). The main aim here was obtain an in-depth exploration of the nature of their classroom interaction experience, as well as the contextual factors that might hinder the effective implementation of IC in that particular context. Focus group interviews were selected as a method of data collection instead of individual interviews because there is evidence to suggest that group interaction may result in the emergence of new thoughts and ideas, which may not manifest themselves in individual interviews (Cohen et al., 2013; Stewart and Shamdasani, 2014). Besides, focus group interviews facilitate the generation of a large amount of data in a very short time.

Moreover, within focus group interviews, participants do not feel pressured to answer every single question as they have the opportunity to react and build on the responses of the other members of the group (Stewart, and Shamdasani, 2014, pp.45-46). Similar to individual interviews, focus group interviews may range from unstructured to fully structured. However, for the purpose of this research, the researcher opted for a semi-structured approach. This approach enabled gathering specific answers related to the investigation of the participants' views on IC, and also to arrive at an understanding of the participants' meanings and interpretations. The use of semi-structured approach allowed for a space to ask more questions in response to what emerged during the group interaction.

Although the use of focus group interviews had a number of advantages, which served the objective of this study, there were also some disadvantages. For example, as the

moderator, the researcher might be biased and thus provide cues of what type of responses were desirable (Stewart, and Shamdasani, 2014, pp.47-48). Also, responses of an open-ended nature obtained from participants are often difficult to interpret or summarise. There is also the possibility of obtaining results that might be biased by the dominant and opinionated members of the group. Thus, to resolve some of these issues, the researcher assured that everyone in the group had the opportunity to say his/ her opinion, as well as promoting group discussion. In addition, the researcher did not provide any cues on the type of desired responses and focused on obtaining the participants' own understanding and conceptualisation as much as possible.

Before the participants were interviewed, they were provided with information regarding the nature of the project as well as the procedures in place to ensure anonymity and confidentiality. The researcher also made sure that the participants were comfortable with taking part in the focus group by making himself available to answer any questions they had in advance. To put participants at ease, he asked general questions at the beginning of the session as a warmup, with more specific as the focus group progressed. The researcher was able to follow up on issues of particular interest once he felt sure that the participants had settled into a joint exploration of the topic. Finally, once the interview finished, the participants were thanked for taking part in the project, and kindly asked to email the researcher if they thought of anything else in relation to what took place in the interview session, and contact was maintained. Only one participant provided additional information via email after the interview session (see Chapter 6, Section 6.7).

The in-depth interviews with the teachers lasted between 45 minutes to approximately an hour and a half. The focus groups also varied considerably in length, with sessions lasting between 38 minutes minimum and one hour and 12 minutes. To record the interviews, the researcher used his personal smartphone galaxy s7 edge. The phone is equipped with two microphones, which made it convenient for the task. The quality of the recording was adequate, except for some background noise, which did not affect the overall quality of the recording.

4.5 Sampling procedures

For convenience and ease of access, the research sample for this study was sought from the university in Algeria, where the researcher completed his education. Due to some of the sensitive information obtained from the participants and to ensure confidentiality and anonymity in accordance with the principles of ethical research conduct, the name of the university will not be disclosed. Two sampling strategies were implemented in this study. Simple random sampling was used for the recruitment of teachers, and purposive sampling for the recruitment of students.

In the case of both in-depth the individual interviews with teachers and the focus groups with students, participants were approached in person by the researcher in their classrooms before the commencement of the fieldwork. I engaged in a friendly conversation with participants as a way to establish bonds. Following this, an email that contains the participant information sheets (PIS) and the consent forms were sent to the participants (see Appendices C and D respectively). The PIS incorporated details about the purpose of the investigation, aims and objectives, data collection methods, why the participants were chosen to take part in this project, what was expected from them if they decided to take part in the project; and how the data will be used. Phone numbers were also sought from students and staff in order to maintain contact. Prospective participants were invited to signal their interest in taking part in the project by reply to the email and returning the signed consent form. At that stage, they were asked to suggest a suitable time to be interviewed. Participants were kept informed of arrangements via email. In addition, the researcher also employed snowball sampling in order to reach two or three additional participants. On the advice of those who had already given their consent to participate in the study, the researcher approached a few participants via email, having had no prior contact.

The ten teachers ranged in age from approximately 30 to 55 and had different levels of teaching experience. Their teaching experience within the university ranged from a minimum of 5 years up to about 40 years. Apart from the age group, gender, and the teaching experiences, these teachers taught different disciplines including mainly linguistics, and literature and civilisation.

The total number of EFL teachers within the University is 59 divided into five main categories according to their ranks (see Table 6.1 below). I interviewed a total of two teachers from each category. The reason for this was to gain an array of perspectives, as well as to avoid being biased to a particular category. In addition, I was a student at that HE institution for five years, during which time I completed my undergraduate studies in *sciences de langage*. This means that I had a pre-existing relationship with some of the participants, which may have an impact on the development of trust and rapport and the overall credibility of the data (see Section 4.6.1). The issue of positionality was discussed with my supervisor prior to the commencement of the fieldwork. In order to maintain credibility and to ensure the validity of the data by avoiding undue biases, I took the opportunity to interview teachers whom I have not previously encountered during my time as a student. For the sake of accuracy, the number of interviewed teachers whom I did not have a pre-existing relationship with was 4 out of 10.

Table 4.5: An overview of EFL teaching faculty in study institution

EFL teachers' ranks	Number of teachers	Number of interviewees
Professor of higher education	6	2
Lecturer A	3	2
Lecturer B	3	2
Assistant professor A	22	2
Assistant professor B	25	2
Total	59	10

In respect to focus group participants, they were 3rd year Algerian EFL students within the same university. These participants were both males and females, with a female majority. The total number of the overall students within all the focus groups is 16. Although the research intended to have precisely six students per focus group, the number of the students varied from one group to another. The focus groups were

comprised of the following number of students, respectively six and ten. The second group comprised ten students because some of the participants brought their classmates, who showed a high interest in taking part in the project. The researcher has suggested, however, to schedule another focus group interview with them, but they have responded that they do not have any other availability except this one. In response to this, I briefed them on the purposes of the study and decided to allow them to join the group after they had provided informed consent.

4.6 Research ethics

Before commencing this study, the researcher sought ethical approval from the University Ethics Committee. The research was conducted in accordance with ethical codes of practice for educational research, such as those provided by the Scottish Educational Research Association (SERA). In respect of participants, the principle of voluntary informed consent was observed, and participants were assured of confidentiality and anonymity. Every effort was made to ensure that the questions were intelligible to the participants and that they had ample opportunity to provide answers. All personal data were stored securely on the researcher's personal computer that is password encrypted. The signed consent forms were also stored securely in digital format on a password-protected device. Pseudonyms were used to guarantee the anonymity of the participants. Although the data-gathering phase of the study presented considerable challenges (see under Section 4.8 below), the researcher made sure that he behaved professionally throughout the fieldwork.

4.6.1 Researcher positionality and reflexivity

The adaptation of the constructivist/interpretivist research paradigm necessitates addressing the researcher positionality. This becomes imperative mainly while conducting qualitative research due to the degree of the involvement of the researcher within the research process, and the potential biases that the researcher might bring in the research project which might affect the research process and outcomes (Robson, 2002). Therefore, the researcher needs to be aware of his position, and reflexive, that is, to 'question ways of doing'. Besides, the researchers' acknowledgement of his/herself or positionality is considered part and parcel of conducting ethical research.

In respect of the researcher's positionality, the choice often falls between either the researcher taking an insider or outsider position vis-à-vis the researched community. Taking either position comes with several advantages, as well as challenges. Insiders, for example, are valued for their unique position to understand the experiences of the groups of which they are members. They contend that outsiders will never be able to fully understand a culture which they are not part of, or an experience or a situation which they have not experienced themselves (Chavez, 2008; Kerstetter, 2012). On the other hand, the outsider is valued for their neutrality, detachment and objectivity, and they maintain that the insiders are too close to the researched subjects, and such proximity might threaten research validity.

The researcher of this PhD study is an insider because he is from the community under study and shares many cultural identities with the research participants such as race, language, and ethnicity. The researcher is also an insider to the researched community having studied and graduated from the institution in which the data for this research project were collected. Therefore, the researcher has access to exclusive knowledge about the Algerian student community. This type of knowledge might be difficult to be accessed by an outsider. Although the researcher shares the aforementioned experiences with the research participants, he had never referred or used his personal experience during the data collection or data analysis and focused explicitly on eliciting participants' views.

Being an insider eliminated access related issues as the researcher benefited from what Merton (1972) referred to as monopolistic access. The insider position also facilitated the engagement with research participants (both teachers and learners). Consequently, this eased the participants' recruitment. The insider positionality also resulted in greater honesty on the part of the research participants and contributed to the generation of richer data (Dwyer and Buckle, 2009). Apart from the privileges that come with the insider position, the researcher is aware of the limitation of his positionality and its impact on the data analysis, and research outcomes. In particular, he is aware of the lurking threat of being overly positive 'if the knowledge, culture, and experiences he shares with the participant manifest as a rose-coloured observational lens or blindness to the ordinary' (Chavez, 2008, p.475). Not only these assumptions about insiders are theoretical but also supported by little empirical

evidence (ibid). Regardless, the researcher is aware that it is crucial to separate his self from the researcher self and continuously monitor his position by being reflexive.

To continuously monitor his position, while conducting the fieldwork the researcher took field notes to document participants' behaviours and during and after the interview session, the researchers' feelings and emotions, as well as to document certain random encounters with his former teachers and administrative staff. Some of these notes were written down on the research journal, while others were recorded using his smartphone. On the reflexivity note, the researcher problematises the notion of a single-self researcher position and does not consider himself a 'complete insider' for the reasons outlined below (Kerstetter; 2012).

Arguably, the black and white dichotomy between insider and outsider position is a limited conception of researcher positionality. First of all, cases in which a researcher is a complete insider or outsider are very few (Mercer, 2007; Kerstetter; 2012). In addition, the researcher's position is relatively based on when and where the research was conducted, the researcher's and research participants' personalities, and the research topic (ibid). Consequently, many researchers transcended this strict distinction between the two extremities towards the consideration of a new multidimensional space called the 'the space between', which is more flexible and offers more space for researchers to express their positionality (Dwyer and Buckle, 2009; Kerstetter; 2012).

Although the researcher is from the researched community and shares several cultural identities with them, he is also an outsider. He is an outsider because he approached the research setting, presented himself to the participants, and behaved as an international student in the UK. This is evident in the schedule of interviews with teachers (see Appendix A) and focus group topic guide with learners (see Appendix B).

Also many community-based researchers approach their communities not simply as outsiders but as privileged ones (Kerstetter, 2012). The researcher's position as an international student in the UK might be considered as a privileged one. The researcher is aware that his 'privileged' outsider positionality could have created power imbalance. However, the researcher did not, either explicitly or implicitly,

demonstrate such privilege. On the contrary, he always valued and prioritised the participants' comfort and well-being and assured to all participants, teachers and learners alike, that the encounter is friendly.

To further argue for the researchers' outsider positionality, the researcher took a field note after his arrival to Algeria to conduct the fieldwork:

It has been a while since my last visit to my home country. How could I feel so strange in an environment that is so familiar? I was criticising, scrutinising almost everything; the way people talk, lifestyle, and ways of thinking. I was culturally shocked within my own culture. Before I arrive at the international airport in Algiers, I was expecting a close friend of mine to come and pick me up. We have not seen each other for a long time. I was watching him coming towards me with open arms, and he hugged so tight. However, I was surprised by the whole airport surroundings. I could not move, think, act or react. I was literally fixed to the ground that I was standing on, and I wondered...How could I feel so strange in an environment that is so familiar?

Entry 01: Field notes

The above reflection demonstrates a valid emotion and feeling of strangeness. The researcher viewed himself as an outsider to his own culture and home country. In the above quotation, the usage of the terms 'criticise' and 'scrutinise' refers to the surfacing of the researcher's self. This minimises the threat to the validity of the research posed by the researcher's overfamiliarity with researched population and culture addressed above. Therefore, the researcher of this PhD project is neither a complete insider nor a complete outsider. Instead, he is some of both and occupying 'the space between'. He is not too close to not be able to separate his personal experiences from the participants'. Thus, attaining the distance deemed to be

necessary for research validity. However, he is also not too far to impose his own opinion and interpretation (Chavez, 2008).

4.7 Challenges encountered while collecting data

In preparation for the fieldwork, the researcher interviewed five of his fellow Algerian students at UWS to ascertain their perspectives about the challenges they faced during their data collection in the Algerian HE context. The results of this small-scale scoping study formed the basis of a presentation at the annual conference of the Scottish Educational Research Association (SERA), which was held at UWS in 2017 (Necib, 2017). To achieve the aforementioned objective, semi-structured interviews were conducted with the participants. The analysis of the interview built on Goffman's (1959) dramaturgical perspective. Particularly, the argument for the study was predicated upon the following quote:

A researcher's path is usually fraught with challenges, especially those related data collections. When conducting fieldwork, there is a large amount of data that is collected by working backstage. Backstage is an analogy inspired by the theatre; it refers to everything that happens behind the scenes when conducting fieldwork (De Munck, 2009; Leavy, 2014). What the audience sees on the stage at a theatre is the final product of a particular performance. The audience, however, is not aware of the challenges that the performer encountered in order for the final product to come to fruition.

(Necib, 2017)

The quotations below provide an overview of some of the challenges faced by my peers at UWS when conducting their fieldwork. As will be explored, the researcher of the present study faced many similar challenges.

'Oh man! You just got me on the right spot [laughter] challenges I have never expected.'

Student X

I felt offended by some of the teachers' attitudes regarding my ideas...they say: Oh no! This will never work.

Student Y

Man, as an international researcher...I don't know how it was but the teachers... the way they look at you. Some of them they show... yeah... they were happy, and they will help you. Some of them they show you that, but they don't mean it. So, for example... most of them refused to take part for no reason... the worst thing...when you approach teachers like you tell them and give them the consent form to know about your research, and then if they have any questions and stuff like that... they do accept it, and they say yes, we will take part. But then when you give them the questionnaire and they give it back to you. That's one of the things, which I did not expect. Since the teacher says yes, I will be happy and then sign the consent form... so that's it, that's done. I am not like having participants like... as kids. You're a teacher, so I think you would be like...at the level of your words... then you start running after teachers, you literally look for their numbered...oh I will get it by tomorrow and then the day after...it absolutely shocked me... that was only the questionnaire.

Student X

According to 'Anonymous Y' response, there seems to be a resistance to new ideas on the part of the teachers. This resulted in the researcher being offended. 'Anonymous X', however, presented some of the teachers' attitudes and behaviour regarding the acceptance of the image of international students, and abiding by the recruitment procedure such as signing consent forms. The researcher of this PhD study also faced some challenges in these regards with minorities of participants, such as lack of punctuality, not reading the participant information sheet, and not responding to email and signing the consent form. The researcher, however, did not experience participants refusing to take part in this project.

Overall, the research interviews and focus groups were conducted under conditions that were conducive to maintaining the confidentiality and ensuring that the recorded material was of sufficient quality to enable me to proceed to data analysis. However, I did encounter significant challenges during the data collection process, some of which were related to the behaviours and attitudes of some of the participants. One of the challenges the researcher faced was finding a suitable location for conducting the interviews, as the facilities were overcrowded, and the corridors were filled with students chatting loudly. On one occasion, the researcher had to stop during an interview with one of the research participants, as students barged into the room where the interview was taking place, interrupting the proceedings. The researcher resumed the interview with the participant after finding a more suitable location. Most of the interviews took place in laboratories, which were the most convenient site in terms of quietness and privacy. Others were conducted inside classrooms which had limited privacy due to the fact that classroom doors had no locks on them.

It is also important to note that the time allocated for conducting the fieldwork was only one month. This called for the need for time to be managed wisely. This was particularly critical as the period allocated to fieldwork in Algeria coincided with the end of the academic year and the approach of the holy month. This situation did not significantly affect the quality of the data, although data gathering during the holy month presented some challenges due to the effects of fasting on the participants. The researcher made sure that all the participants who were interviewed during the holy month were comfortable with taking part, and they assured me that they would

not suffer any ill effects. In addition, the interviews were conducted in the morning when individuals were still feeling relatively energetic.

4.8 Research validity and reliability

Validity and reliability are two important measures of the research quality of all kind of research, including a qualitative one. Research validity refers to whether the research findings are accurate from the perspectives of the researcher, the participants, or the readers (Creswell and Creswell, 2017). Reliability refers to the extent to which the research findings are worthwhile, dependable, consistent and replicable (Golafshani, 2003). Although in quantitative studies validity and reliability are usually separated, in qualitative research these aspects are interrelated. This means for a qualitative research to achieve reliability, establishing research validity and trustworthiness is crucial (Lincoln and Guba, 1985; Golafshani, 2003).

4.8.1 Research validity/trustworthiness

There are other terms in the literature that are used to address qualitative research validity, such as trustworthiness, authenticity, and credibility (Creswell and Creswell, 2017). Accordingly, certain measures were used to increase the validity of the study. This includes piloting the study (Guba and Lincoln, 1985; Hall, 2008), prolonged engagement (Maxwell, 2008; Thyer, 2009), rich data (Maxwell, 2008), and Triangulation (Maxwell, 2008; Creswell and Creswell, 2017).

Piloting

Conducting a pilot study is one of the expedients to test the research design and to maximise research validity (Hall, 2008). As mention in Chapter 1, the focus group questions were trialled and piloted prior to beginning the fieldwork. Topic guide questions were piloted with six EFL Master students from different nationalities at the University of the West of Scotland (UWS). The participants were approached in the classroom by the end of the session within the aforementioned university. The teacher introduced the researcher to the participants, and the participants for the pilot study were recruited.

The pilot study aimed to ensure that the questions are accessible to the actual research participant, as well as to ensure that the questions being asked are the correct corrections. In addition, due to the fact that the researcher had no previous experience with conducting focus group interviews, the pilot study was also viewed as an opportunity for the researcher to practise his role as a moderator, and to gain practical experience on how to manage group discussion successfully, and to ensure that everyone took part and heard. The piloting of the focus group questions echoes the researcher's awareness of the potential limitations of focus group interviews (see Section 4.4).

Piloting teachers' interviews questions were deemed to be unnecessary since, with ten interviews, there was always the chance to adjust the questions and add new topics through reading the transcript or listening to the recording of the previous interview (s) (Collins, 2018). However, In the case of focus group interviews, the chances for making such adjustments were limited.

In addition to piloting focus group questions, the researcher used semi-structured interviews to interview 5 of his fellow Algerian students at UWS. The aim was for the researcher to gain an understanding of the potential challenges (see Section 4.7). This illustrates the researcher's awareness of the implication of returning home to Algeria as an international PhD researcher for data collection.

Prolonged engagement

One of the best ways to increase research validity is the researcher use of prolonged engagement (Thyer, 2009). Herein, the researcher needs to demonstrate that sufficient time was spent with the research process, in the fieldwork, as well as with data analysis (Maxwell, 2008; Thyer, 2009).

The data collection for this PhD took one month. This was long enough for the researcher to establish a relationship with the participants in order to maximise the reliability of the obtained data and hence the findings. The data analysis phase took around five months. The first three months were allocated to the first stage of the analysis, which included transcribing, coding and extracting themes, followed by two months for scrutiny and further checks. This extended time was used to check to

question the interpretation and findings, to reflect on the field notes, and establish whether the extracted themes are relevant to the purpose of the study, as well as to eliminate irrelevant information.

As mentioned earlier, the researcher of this PhD study graduated from the university where the data for this PhD project were sought. Therefore, there is a threat of the researcher's unconscious bias to creep in while collecting and analysing data. Prolonged engagement assisted with the reduction of the researcher bias through having allowed extended time for reflexivity. As prolonged engagement could be useful to reduce and or eliminate researcher bias, it can also lead a greater researcher bias as it might be difficult to maintain the research role over a long period of time (Robson and McCartan, 2016, p. 171). This is why it is important to use triangulation to reduce bias and to increase research validity and reliability (see Section 4.8.1).

Rich data

The richness of the data of this PhD study can be viewed from two angles. First, the research insider position enabled the honesty and the openness of the participants, which led to the generation of rich data as well as to eliminate the chance of the occurrence of misinformation. Second, the richness of the data was also attributed to the use of in-depth interviews which are considered as most powerful tools to obtain rich and in-depth data about a particular phenomenon, and in the present case, the notion of IC competence in the Algerian HE context (Given, 2008). In addition, the richness of this PhD study data can also be viewed in the multiple sources from which the data was generated, that is, the study did not only consider the teachers' views and experiences, but also the learners'.

Triangulation

According to Robson and McCartan (2016, p. 171) 'triangulation can help counter all of the threat to validity'. Generally, there are four types of triangulation, and the one that was employed in this PhD study is data triangulation. Data triangulation refers to 'the use of the of more than one method of data collection' (Robson and McCartan, 2016, p.171). It could also refer to obtaining data from multiple sources, that is, obtaining data from different informants (Stavros and Westerberg, 2009).

Data triangulation is the most used type of triangulation (Thyer, 2009). Data for the present study was collected from teachers and learners, which allowed for the phenomenon of IC to be considered from a variety of perspectives. Consequently, this strengthened the emergent themes, reducing researcher bias, and ultimately increasing confidence and reliability of in the findings.

4.8.2 Reliability

As argued earlier at the beginning of this section, validity and reliability of a qualitative study are interrelated, that is, the 'demonstration of the former (validity) is sufficient to establish the latter (reliability)' (Lincoln and Guba, 1985, p.316). Therefore, the reliability of this research study was achieved through collecting data from multiple sources (see Section 4.8.1), analysing data in line with methodological rigours (see Section 4.9), identifying potential biases and the procedures by which they were reduced (see Section 4.6.1), as well as conducting the study following research ethics (see Section 4.6).

One of the main limitations of qualitative research in general (Lodico et al., 2010), and a case study, in particular, is that it does not allow for generalisability of the findings as the data collected is highly contextualised (Remenyi, 2012). However, it can be argued that despite the lack of generalisability, the findings of this study might be found very insightful and transferable to similar EFL contexts. The researcher provided a full and rich description of all the aspects pertaining the study, and it is up to the reader to judge the transferability of this study their research area (Lodico et al., 2010).

4.9 Data analysis

After the data collection phase was completed, the data analysis phase began. The present qualitative PhD study made use of thematic analysis method to analyse in-depth and focus group interviews. The reason behind the choice of thematic analysis is not only because it is the most used approach for qualitative research analysis (Nowell et al., 2017), but also for its suitability for research questions that deal with individuals' conceptualisation and their experiences with a particular phenomenon (Braun and Clarke, 2006; King 2004; Willig, 2013). In the present study, this

concerns the exploration of Algerian EFL teachers' and learners' perspectives and experiences with the notion of IC, as well as their views on the impact of power dynamics on its operationalisation in the Algerian HE context.

Conducting thematic analysis involves the consideration of two main approaches: an inductive and a deductive approach. Within the former, codes and themes are derived from the data, while using the deductive approach involves data being fitted into 'a pre-existing coding frame or the research's preconception' (Nowell, 2017; Braun and Clarke, 2006). As a qualitative researcher, this research opted for an inductive approach to thematic analysis (Given, 2008).

There are several advantages associated with the use of thematic analysis such as flexibility, and providing rich, detailed and complex data. In addition, the use of thematic analysis is very convenient in highlighting similarities and differences in participant responses (Braun and Clarke, 2006; King, 2004; Nowell, 2017). Despite these advantages, the potential risk of inconsistency associated with its flexible nature is one of the disadvantages of the thematic analysis method. Therefore, it is important for the researcher using thematic analysis to establish validity/trustworthiness and reliability of qualitative research (see Section 4.8). Besides, to increase research validity and reliability, thematic analysis was conducted following a step by step guide towards a trustworthy thematic analysis (Braun and Clark 2006; Nowell, 2017). This section will explore the different principles of thematic analysis approach, and the techniques used for the analysis of in-depth interviews and focus group interviews. Although the steps were presented linearly, the analysis process was more interactive and reflective and sometimes it was necessary to move back and forward through the different stages (Nowell, 2017).

Stage one: Getting familiar with the data

Ten in-depth interviews with a minimum of 45 minutes in length, as well as two focus group interviews, is a considerable amount of data. Therefore, it was vital for the researcher to listen to the recordings along with the field notes in a bid to familiarise himself with its depth and breadth (Nowell et al., 2017). Each recording was listened to at least once, and the listening sessions were accompanied by the documentation of the first thought and impressions.

Stage two: Data transcription and further familiarisation

The use of software could make the process of data transcription easier and saves both time and effort. In respect of this PhD study, two softwares were used in the transcription of the in-depth interviews. First, the interviews were automatically transcribed word for word using Otter. Otter is a live video meeting note with a built-in audio transcription software which offers up to 600min minutes transcriptions monthly. The transcription is not 100 per cent accurate, and this is why it was necessary to check the transcription manually with the assistance of multimedia player called QuickTime Player to achieve better transcription accuracy. The Multimedia player was easy to use and did not require an upgrade to access its basic features. QuickTime was convenient for navigating through digital records and enabled me to adjust speed without affecting sound quality. During the checking phase, the researcher assigned other features, such as teacher participants' tone of the voice to be included in the analysis.

In respect of focus group interviews, it was not possible to use Otter app for the transcription because of the students' overlapping voices. Focus group interviews were transcribed verbatim and manually with the help of QuickTime play software. Once the transcription was completed, the researcher further immersed himself with the data for more familiarity.

Stage three: generating initial codes

Once the data transcription and familiarisation were completed; the coding stage was initiated. In thematic analysis approach, a code is 'often a word or a short phrase that symbolically assigns a summative, salient, essence capturing and/or evocative attribute for a portion of language based visual data' (Saldaña, 2013, p. 3). Data coding is the process of close inspection of text to look at recurrent themes, topics and relationships, and mark passages with codes or labels to be recognised for later retrieval and theory building (Mills et al., 2010, p.926). Due to the large amount of data, it was necessary to use software to help with the analysis. The transcribed data was uploaded in NVivo software which made the process data analysis more organised, systematic, and efficient, and ultimately enhanced the credibility of the research findings (Nowell, 2017). The initial codes were generated though carefully

reading throughout the transcripts and assigning codes. After initial codes were created, the researcher checked that the codes were relevant and appropriately named, as well as ensuring that codes were not redundant. This paved the way for the commencement of the next stage, which is searching for themes.

Stage four: Searching for themes

As mentioned at the beginning of the section, this study made use of an inductive approach to thematic analysis. After the data was coded, the relevant codes were extracted into themes. The main themes were identified based on recurrent participants' ideas and experiences, and some of the themes, unintentionally, matched the interview questions. The inductive approach to theme extraction led to further review of the literature, especially in respect of concepts related to power demonstration and use (see Chapter 2). After the identification of the main themes, subthemes were also identified using NVivo 12 software, as well as mind maps.

Stage five: Reviewing themes

After identifying the main themes and subthemes, the next stage was to review the extracted themes. This involved going back to the coded data to ensure that themes were extracted correctly, that none were redundant, and that they resonated with the participants' voice. Accordingly, certain themes were merged while others were broken down into other themes.

Stage six: Defining and naming themes

At this stage, it was necessary to define and analyse each theme and subtheme. It was also essential to make sure that the themes were well organised in relation to the whole story. In these regards, certain themes had to be renamed in order to be more reflective of the participants' voice, as well as to give the reader a clear idea of the content of the theme.

Stage seven: producing the report

At this stage, the final analysis phase was commenced, and direct quotes from the participants were included in order to boost the credibility of the analysis. The findings from the study are reported in next two chapters (Chapter 5 and 6).

Chapter 5: Algerian EFL teachers' and learners' perspectives experiences

5.1 Introduction

The primary objective of this study is to conceptualise the notion of interactional competence (IC) in the Algerian higher education context. The study is premised on the fact that foreign language teaching and learning theories usually promote the *status quo* and give little attention to classroom participants' beliefs, lived experiences, and contextual particularities (Kumaravadelu, 2006). Accordingly, this study chiefly drew on Algerian EFL teachers' and learners' perspectives and lived experiences with the notion of IC. The aim is to gain an in-depth understanding of the possibilities and impediments of operationalising a socio-constructivist-based notion such as IC in a higher education context with unique sociolinguistic, economic, political, cultural and institutional features (see Chapter 2). The data comprised ten interviews with teachers and two focus groups with a total of sixteen 3rd year students of English (see Appendices A and B for interview schedules and topic guides, respectively). The data were first transcribed and analysed using thematic analysis approach as previously explored in Chapter 4.

As noted in the outline of the thesis and briefly at the end of Chapter 4, the findings and discussion chapter will be divided into two interrelated chapters. The two chapters were divided only to maintain equilibrium between the chapters of the thesis in term of volume. This chapter will primarily deal with Algerian EFL teachers' and learners' perspectives with the notion of IC. It will look at teachers' views of the training they received, their perspective about EFL theory and practice, and more importantly, their views about the notion of IC. The subsequent chapter, Chapter 6, will explore and discuss the participants' experiences with the notion of IC, and the challenges they face in operationalising its performative elements. The chapter primarily shed lights on their perceptions of the nature of power dynamics in the institution and in the classroom and its impact on the operationalisation of the notion of IC.

The research findings presented and discussed in this chapter and the subsequent one (Chapter 6) relate to the three main research questions, which guided all stages of the study, posed in Chapter 1, Section 1.3.

The first research question was devised to explore teachers' and learners' perspectives and experiences with the notion of IC. As per the teacher participants, three primary levels of experiences were considered; their personal experiences as teachers within the institution; their previous experiences as EFL learners; and their experiences with the formal knowledge (Knowledge gained from academic subjects and training programs). As for learners, the study considered their former classroom interaction experiences at the middle and high school level, and most notably at the university level. The findings revealed that teachers' perspectives varied considerably from one teacher to another depending on their individual beliefs, and personal and academic experiences. As for the students, their accounts demonstrated an understanding of the notion of interactional competence.

The second research question was designed to obtain teachers' and learners' perspectives on the nature of the power dynamics in the institution, and its impact on their classroom interaction experience and students' engagement. The findings revealed that the power structure in the institution is hierarchical and authority-based. Particularly in the classroom context, the findings disclosed unequal power relations between teachers and students. The prevalence of increased teacher talk time in the classroom constitutes a significant obstacle to students' learning opportunities.

The third research question was designed to obtain the respondents' perceptions of the challenges that might impede the implementation of IC in the institution. The findings demonstrated that there were a number of obstacles to the implementation of the notion of IC. Primarily, the shift in the balance of power between teachers and learners as a result of increasing emphasis on IC might be threatening to the teachers' authoritarian behaviour in the classroom, to the academic culture in the institutions. Also, time constraints and large class size constitute an obstacle for implementing of the performative elements of IC in the classroom.

5.1.1 Participants' profile

The ten teachers who participated in the study, three men and seven women, had varying degrees of experiences in higher education (see Table, 5.1.1). Each teacher was interviewed once, and the interviews varied in length from forty-five minutes to one and a half hours. Some interviews were lengthy for two chief reasons. First, many participants tended to talk a lot, and this was viewed as a sign of openness and transparency. Second, a few interviews were punctuated with long pauses as the interviewees took time to formulate their responses. As will be evident from some of the quotations below, there was a substantial variation in terms of their level of linguistic competence.

Teachers were invited to reflect on the nature of their experiences in teaching in HE: working conditions, training opportunities, the education system, and most importantly, their conception of IC. The interviews were conducted in English, as the teachers were nominally EFL specialists. In two occasions, once with a teacher and another with a student from Focus Group 2, the use of the Arabic language was necessary when the participants found it challenging to understand the question or to formulate a response.

In order to minimise misunderstanding and data compromise due to fluency level, the participants were given the option to express themselves in Arabic or French. Particularly, participant Amal experienced difficulties in voicing her thoughts in English, and this is evident in the dominant use of Arabic and French in her accounts throughout the chapter. Variations in levels of IC are to be expected, and these are overlaid by differences in levels of competence in EFL. These variations are not merely confined to the EFL context. Generally, whether inside or outside the classroom, there are substantial differences between different individuals concerning their ability to understand and share their ideas (Walsh, 2012).

The sixteen students, five men and eleven women, were asked about their experience of verbal interaction in the target language. The focus group interviews also probed into the nature of their relationship with their teachers, the extent to which they were able to initiate conversation and manage interaction in English, and the opportunities they were given to practise the target language in the classroom setting. This is a

particularly important area of inquiry in an educational context where teachers tend to monopolise classroom talk (Hadjeris, 2019).

The first focus group comprised seven women and three men, and in the second, there were four women and two men. The focus group interviews were also conducted in English. The students were relaxed, enthusiastic, and expressive, especially while describing their experiences of classroom interaction. It was noticeable that they had a good level of fluency.

In the discussion of the findings, teacher participants were referred to using pseudonyms shown in table 5.1.1 below. Student participants were referred to by the letter 'S'; S1 for student one, S2 for student two and so on followed by the number of the focus group, that is, F1 for Focus Group 1, and F2 for Focus Group 2. The letters Ss was used to refer to a group of students. In the students' excerpts, the researcher was identified by the letter 'R'.

Table 5.1.1: Overview of teacher participants.

Pseudonym	Gender	Age range	Field of Expertise	Modules Taught	Training	Teaching Experience within the institution
Asma	Female	30- 35	Literature	Literature, Oral Expression, Written Expression, and	1-Year USA After recruitment	5 Years
Jamila	Female		Civilisation	British civilisation, and American Civilisation, Written Expression, Oral Expression,	1-year training after recruitment in Civilisation, literature, and Linguistics	5 Years
Amina	Female		Linguistics	Oral Expression and Written Expression	No Training	10 Years
Amal	Female	50 above	Linguistics	ESP, Oral Expression, Grammar	Studied Abroad.	25 Years
Sami	Male		Literature	Literature, Oral Expression, Written Expression,	Few Training Sessions in Algeria organised by the British Council.	More than 30 years
Laila	Female		Linguistics	Oral Expression, Didactics, Oral Expression, and Educational Psychology	Master's degree from the UK in Educational psychology. 2 weeks training organised in Algeria.	39 Years
Soumia	Female		Linguistics	Linguistics	PhD. UK	28 Years
Ahmed	Male		Literature	Literature, Linguistics, Oral Expression	Few Training Sessions after recruitment	More than 30 Years
Hayam	Female		Linguistics	Linguistics, Oral Expression, and Written Expression	No Training	20 Years
Talib	Male		Literature, and Linguistics and Phonetics	Literature, Linguistics and, Oral Expression.	One-month training in the UK.	35 Years

5.1.2 Participants' linguistic behaviour

In the light of exploring the notion of IC, bearing of the participants' linguistic behaviour during the interview will promote an in-depth understanding of this phenomenon. Many participants, both teachers and learners switched between French, English and Arabic. This phenomenon of switching between two different linguistic codes or more is referred to as code-switching (CS), and it a very common phenomenon among Algerian individuals both inside and outside the classroom (Chemami, 2011; Le Roux, 2017). From the point of view of interactional competence, CS can be viewed as an interactional strategy that defines the nature by which Algerian individuals interact.

There were four types of CS deployed by the participants. The first where participants code-switched between English and French, such as in the case of the participants Soumia and Sami and a student participant from Focus Group 2. English-French CS was the most common type of CS. It was more prevalent amongst the older generation of the teachers, mainly because they are more attached to French than to English. The latter is consistent with the literature as the promotion of the English language is relatively a new phenomenon due to globalisation (Crystal, 2003; Mami, 2013; Bellalem, 2012). In this respect, Teacher participant Talib maintained that *'...my son, for instance, even though I am very fluent in French. I am more fluent in French than in English, that in Arabic even, he likes English. He doesn't like French.'* The participant's account indicates that the new generation of students prefer English more than French, which indicates that English is gaining a position in the Algerian linguistic landscape (Benrabah, 2013). Besides, the prevalence of English-French CS is also an indication of strong position the French language still holds in the Algerian linguistic landscape despite the Algerian government's promotion of the English language (Benrabah, 2014, Le Roux, 2017). Below there are few examples of the English-French CS deployed by the participants. The French language in the quote will be preceded by (Fr). The translation is provided below the French text between brackets [].

In less frequent cases, French was used by some of the participants to further an argument through incorporating a French saying, as shown below:

...There is a saying in French (Fr) on ne parle pas des mauvais étudiants, mais il y a des mauvais enseignants.

[There are no bad students, there are bad teachers]

{Soumia}

In the following examples, participants code-switched to provide the exact French equivalent of an English word or expression. The latter is preceded by (En) in the quote.

...The style is said to be the map. (Fr) Le style c'est l'orb]

{Sami}

...the teacher is here, (En) the master, (Fr)le maître...

{Ahmed}

It's not the kind of classical seating one row behind the other. It's kind of (En) round Table (Fr) table ronde, as we say in French.

{Soumia}

The use of French amongst senior teachers is consistent with the literature, and the reality of the Algerian linguistic landscape, where French is considered as the language of the elites, and usually associated with elegance, prestige and respect (Benrabah, 2007).

The second type of CS involved participants switching between English and Classical Arabic. For example, in the case of participant Amina, Classical Arabic was used to provide the exact equivalent of the English word or expression. The Arabic in the quote is preceded by (Ar).

...in the primary school, we have written expression,
and we have oral expression, (Ar)*Taabir shifahi wa
taabir kitabi...*

{**Amina**}

[...in the primary school, we have written expression
and oral expression.]

[**Translation**]

The third type of CS was between English, Algerian Arabic and French, such as in the case of participant Amal. The Algerian Arabic, French, and English text in the quote is preceded by (AA), (Fr), and (En) respectively.

*Kouna hnaya (...) (AA)c'est déjà une (Fr) farha kbira
li tla'ana lil jamia'a(AA). We were very, very few
(En). Li yedi l'BAC Lwaqt adek shkoun.*

[We were (...) it was extreme happiness for us that we
got admitted into the university. We were very few.
Very few people pass the baccalaureate exam at that
time.]

{**Amal**}

The last type of code-switching was between English and Algerian Arabic (AA) deployed by one of the student participants. In the transcripts, AA was used on two occasions. In the first, one was used by one of the students asking his classmate to speak up; '(AA) Hiz sotek xxxx' [Speak up xxxx] {**S1F2**}. Here, Arabic was used by the participant to draw attention to a factor that might be disruptive to the interaction, that is, the low speaking register. This particular participant was very active and highly articulate and demonstrated features of IC. For example, the participant successfully managed turn-taking amongst his classmates and knew when to speak and when to remain silent.

The second occasion where AA was used was by a student participant while reporting her perspectives about her teachers because she was shy to speak in English. *'I am so shy'*, said the participant. Then she added, *'(Ar) sa'aet, les profs maya'ajboubich, dorka le prof houwa li habek fil modules hedek.'* which translated to [*sometimes I don't like the teachers. In fact, the teacher is the one who makes you like that particular module.*] In this situation, Arabic was used to transcend the shyness caused by speaking the target language to accomplish a communicative act, that is, reporting a perspective.

The phenomenon of CS, and particularly between Algerian Arabic and French, is an important language repertoire which students bring with them into different communicative situations, including the classroom context. Both Arabic and French constitute an important linguistic resource which learners might use to fulfil different communicative needs. These resources might also be used by teachers as an effective tool for teaching and learning, as well as a research tool to explore more about learners' identities (Kumaravadivelu, 2001). However, the interview data revealed that many teachers neglect the learners' language repertoire.

5.2 Teachers' neglect of learners' language repertoire

The interview analysis revealed that many teachers disregard the students' language repertoire. As emerged from the teachers' accounts, the use of Arabic and French in classrooms is prohibited. The prohibition is propelled by the teachers' belief that the use of L1 (Algerian Arabic) or L2 (French) interferes with the learning of the target language, as well as constitutes an impediment to the fluidity of interaction. For example, Soumia maintained that: *'a face to face interaction sometimes doesn't work that well because they don't know how to express themselves. Sometimes when they get stuck, they say some words in Arabic, or in French.'* Soumia's account suggests that she is against the use of French and Arabic in the classroom. In a similar vein, Asma maintained that *'I kinda use all kinds of language except the mother tongue. I restrict my students from using any mother tongue, any Chinese, Portuguese, any other languages.'* In addition, participant Hayam indicated that she does not allow pair work and group work within her classes because students are prone to use Arabic instead of English: *'We don't have the culture that when students are gathering, they have only to talk about the topic. They switch to talk into Arabic.'*

They switch to talk about another topic...for me, I adopt individual work to impede them from deviating from the topic.'

A point of commonality between the participants' accounts above is that students are discouraged from speaking languages other than English in the classroom. Participant Hayam's account, in particular, shows a degree of authority and behavioural control which promotes individual rather than collective performances. This participant's account is not consistent with the literature as IC champions collective performances. Asma and Soumia's accounts are also not consistent with the literature because they undermine students' previous experiences which is a valued aspect in post-method pedagogy (PMP) (Kumaravadivelu, 2006).

It might be true that excessive use of the mother tongue in the classroom could limit the opportunities of exposure to the target language, which would affect the students' development of IC. At the same time, students' linguistic repertoire should be respected and valued, and focus should be on balancing between the exposure to the target language and students' need for the use of other languages (Brevik and Rindal, 2020; Kumaravadivelu, 2003). As explored in the previous section, the use of L1 might reduce affective factors and provide a sense of security to shy students and fosters students' engagement.

Teachers' neglect of the learner's language repertoire was not a surprising finding given the adequacy of teacher training programs in the context. These training programs tend to promote the *status quo* and give little to no attention to contextual particularities (Kumaravadivelu, 2006).

5.3 The inadequacy of teacher training

The analysis of teacher interviews revealed the inadequacy of teacher training in the context. It was established that the majority of teachers, especially from the older generation (50 years old and above), received no training before commencing their role as EFL teachers. Most teachers, however, had some sort of training after recruitment, and this was also not free from the teachers' criticism. As shown in the participant profile, the majority of the teacher participants are older generation teachers. This latter renders the issue of lack of pre-service training a widespread phenomenon, and it is still the case up to the present date: *'We don't have training.*

Most people are teaching from what they have learned ten years ago...teachers are left alone. {Talib}. The findings are unsurprising given the little attention devoted to teacher training in the Algerian Higher education (Missoum, 2015; Youcef and Taoufik 2015; Zouaozi, 2015).

According to the participants' accounts, commencing teaching immediately after graduation is a common practice.

In the beginning, I didn't have any training as a teacher. Just graduated and then started like the majority of teachers here in our university.

{Laila}

...for those of my generation, we just teach what we know. We have never had any training at all.

{Amal}

Not at all. From my BA degree, so this is the system in Algeria. Once you got your BA degree, which is four years in the licence program, and you can be hired as a part-time teacher.

{Hayam}

The account above indicates that most teachers were recruited with no training. Teachers were left to learn on the job, that is, by trial and error (Zouaozi, 2015). As Talib explained, *'We really learned from the practice from our experience in the classroom. We need to adjust each time our manner of teaching, how to deal with classes. If you want practical experience than theory'*. Echoing Talib's account, Soumia also maintained that *'...when I came as a young teacher, I didn't have any training. All what I learned, I learned in my classroom with my students.'* The limited access to theoretical knowledge and lack of practical training made the transition very challenging for many teachers. Some resorted to following their former teachers' ways of teaching, that is, the transmission model of education (Zouaozi, 2015). In these regards, Talib argued that *'Teachers if you want stuck if you want (sic), kept to the knowledge they had ten years ago. They are teaching; we*

are teaching, I include myself even, our students the same way our teachers taught us...very few innovations if you want.’ The participant’s account suggests that many teachers are still relying on outdated practices (Lamine, 2010; Mohammed, 2011).

In term of EFL pedagogical theories, teachers mentioned two modules, Didactics and TEFL. These modules are taught to EFL students as a pre-service training before their graduation, where they are equipped with the basics of EFL methodology and educational psychology (Youcef and Taoufik, 2015). Accordingly, Talib reported the following *‘We used to have four years licence, and in the fourth year we have if you want didactics that helped us a lot to have notions of how to teach and psychology, but we didn't have a special if you want training.’* {Talib}. In line with Talib’s account, participant Amina also maintained that,

No, there's no training because...in our graduate studies or even the old system magister studies, we have a module of didactics. In didactics, you learn how to teach. TEFL also we have the module of TEFL in our magister Studies they teach us how to teach, but we did not, for instance, have any specific training outside this university or abroad.

{Amina}

Although Talib found these modules to be helpful, Amina deemed the modules to be unsatisfactory because they lacked the practical side: *‘I have to be honest with you, I say not really. They are um just theoretical, purely theoretical.’* Due to the incongruity between theory and practice, Amina stumbled at the reality of teaching that is different from theory (Kumaravadivelu, 2006). According to Amina’s account, these courses failed to prepare her for her first contact with the students. As a result, the participant maintained that she experienced a certain level of anxiety, and even doubted her success as a teacher. *‘the first contact with the students; it was difficult at the beginning. Especially there was some anxiety some fears, are you going to be successful in your teaching. These were the main difficulties.’*

Similar to Amina’s account, participant Amal expressed a sense of loss: *‘It was very difficult because I was young, I didn't know what to prepare. where to start, and*

especially students were almost my age.' The participants account about the inadequate level of preparation provided by the modules of didactics and TEFL modules is consistent with the literature. For example, Youcef and Taoufik (2015) established that TEFL and didactic lack many facets of pre-service training, particularly compulsory practical training.

Some of the participants' accounts provided areas of improvements with regards to the received training. However, from the perspective of this study, the most crucial aspect is whether these training sessions included any aspects of classroom interaction. In this respect, the majority of teachers reported that their training did not focus on classroom interaction. This latter is consistent with Walsh (2006; 2013) who identified classroom interaction as a missing strand in teacher education programs. According to teacher participants accounts, the main focus of their training was on course design and activities. For example, Talib had one-month training in course design in the UK, one which he characterised as interesting. The training, however, did not focus on classroom interaction.

Frankly speaking, I had the training if you want in EFL for one month in Lancaster....we had different teachers, showing us how to design courses in oral expression, especially, and written expression. It was very interesting, and we learned a lot...but it was not really based on interaction or communication.

{Talib}

Similarly, Laila, in addition to having studied in the UK for two years for her master's degree, also had two-week training in Algeria. She pointed out '*interaction was not the focus, the focus was on the activities and how to hold them*'. Laila considered these training sessions as a good initiative; however, this did not impede her from highlighting several issues. The participant took issue with the *status quo* nature of the training session. Teachers of English were trained together with teachers of other specialities such as law and mathematics: '*the main issue of this training is that all teachers are trained together without particular focus on their particular domain. teachers of language with teachers of mathematics with teachers*

of law and all are trained together.' In her account, the participant showed a level of awareness of the specific needs of EFL learners. At the same time, despite her awareness, the participant showed an underlined sense of conformity to the *status quo* as she maintained that these training sessions are *'better than nothing.'*

In other participants' account, it surfaced that training sessions were predicated on the understanding that the teacher is a provider of information. For example, participant Jamila shared,

So, with regardless to the speciality with regardless to the modules that we are doing to teach, but what was the core in general manner is to make this process easier for both students and the teacher. Because our role as a teacher...is making and conveying the message or the information the best way we could. So, the focus or the aim was that in fact.

{ Jamila }

Similar to Laila's account, Jamila's account also suggests that teachers of different specialities are trained together. Jamila, however, did not take issue with the mixing of specialities. Probably, the most interesting aspect in the participant's account is the fact she pointed out that purpose of the focus of the training sessions was on transmission of information. This means that even the training programs are reinforcing the view of the teacher as a knowledge provider.

Furthermore, unlike his colleges, Sami maintained that he received training on classroom interaction. The British Council organised these training sessions, and they involved Algerian teachers as well as teachers from abroad. Sami problematised the training sessions and took issue with the authenticity of the practical side of the training (Kumaravadivelu, 2006). According to the participant's account, the practical part of the training was with teachers rather than with students.

The problem when they came, they made of us teachers and students at the same time. In fact, we are teachers. See us as teachers and bring the students

and try to supervise our interaction with them... There is a practice but with the teacher. This is a problem...you bring me a theoretical basis lets me apply it on the students, not on the teachers.

{Sami}

The participant's account also highlights the *status quo* issue in the training programs. This is evident in the unauthenticity of the practical side of the training. Unlike, Laila, Sami expressed, rather angrily, his rejection the practical side of the training. The participant's tone gives the impression that his authority as a teacher was undermined. The participant's account also suggests the existence of a power hierarchy where the training institution has the upper hand, and teachers are considered compliant agents. Conformity to the *status quo* seems to be achieved through undermining teachers' authority. The latter is foreseeable, given the neoliberal agenda that promoted the status-quo of higher education (Jarvis, 2014; Raaper and Olssen, 2016).

The current situation of teacher training in the institution is improving, or so thought some of the teacher participants. According to Soumia's account, the university introduced in-service teacher training in compliance with the quality assurance (QA) policy (Saadi, 2019).

I think for the past two years, things have been changed and our university, we have what we call (Fr) 'Une cellule assurance qualité'. (Eg) [a cell of quality assurance] That means that every teacher who comes to teach at the university for the first time, he's not a permanent teacher, he is (Fr) enseignant stagiaire [trainee teacher], And every Thursday I think during the whole first year they attend some lectures. I myself lectured them on different things.

{Soumia}

According to Soumia's account, novice teachers now are getting in-service training. Teachers attend these training sessions at least once a week throughout the year to become permanent teachers. The most important aspect in the participant's account is her usage of the word 'lecture' in reference to the way training sessions take place in the institution. The use of word lecture by the participant recalls the transmission model of education. The participant's account suggests that the teacher training aspect in the quality assurance (QA) system is not operating at the expected level. One explanation is the absence of a national quality assurance framework that examines different aspects of the QA mechanisms such as training (Saadi, 2019;).

To summarise, the lack and the inadequacy of teacher training forced many to depend on their own experiences. Therefore, the classroom practices are more likely to be informed by those experiences. As will be explored below, many demonstrated a little interest in reading and applying EFL theories and seemed to be aware of the mismatch between the EFL teaching and learning theory and the actual classroom practice.

5.4 Teachers' beliefs about EFL teaching theories

The majority of the teachers interviewed for the study were either not acquainted with the notion of IC, or identified IC with the general notion of interaction, that is, the general skill by which a group of participants interact (Hall, 2018). It was found that the teachers, in their actual classroom practices, rely on their personal classroom experiences more than on EFL teaching and learning theories (Kumaravadivelu, 2006). Although some teachers acknowledged that they read about EFL teaching and learning theories, very few participants reported that they use EFL theories and methods in their actual classroom practices.

Teachers' little interest in theoretical nuances about EFL teaching and learning seems to be reinforced by a number of contextual factors. There is the unsatisfactory state of the institution's library facilities (Mohammed and Brahim, 2010; Ghemmour and Sarnou, 2016), as well as the inadequacy of the teacher training programs (see Section, 5.3). In addition, the university administration is not supporting teachers, and this had serious implications of teachers' motivation level to take initiatives and ameliorate their teaching practices. In this respect, Talib pointed out with a tone

filled with hopelessness and despair ‘*there is no effort from the administration or the university to try to update the knowledge, the techniques of teaching. There is nothing of that. Teachers are left alone.*’ Talib’s account albeit valid, also indicates a lack of autonomy. As will be explored in the next chapter, the lack of administrative support affected not only the level of motivation of teachers (see Chapter 6, Section, 6.7).

The teachers’ interest in theoretical aspects about EFL classroom interaction seem to be affected by their perspectives and experiences ((Borg; 2001, Borg, 2006; Borg, 2003, Levin et al., 2013; Levin et al., 2010; Kumaravadivelu, 2006). Teachers of literature or civilisation believed that IC is fundamentally a linguistic phenomenon; therefore, it should mainly concern teachers of linguistics. Advocates of the previously mentioned perspective include participants Asma, Jamila, Sami, Talib and Ahmed. For instance, Asma stated that she had some reservations about commenting on the field of linguistics; ‘*I cannot mention linguistic features per se because I am more into literature, and I have some reservations for linguistics.*’ The participant also maintained that she is more interested in the practice than in theories ‘*...I don't read a lot about the theories. I believe more in practice.*’ This means that the participants’ classroom practice is derived from the practice itself, and not from a set of pre-existing theories. In this respect, Asma’s account seems to be aligned with the principles of PMP which promotes the idea that teachers should theorise from their classroom practice and practice what they theorise (Kumaravadivelu, 2006).

Despite her lack of interest in pedagogical theories, the participant considered interaction as a key pedagogical tool in the classroom practice: ‘*I don't know if there's a whole theory for that, but there should always be interaction.*’ Therefore, the participant perspective of about the nature of EFL classroom interaction correlates with Allwright’s (1984, p.159) who argued that ‘*... in terms of pedagogy itself, in the most general sense, that all classroom pedagogy proceeds, necessarily, via a process of interaction, and can proceed only in this way.*’

Participant Sami also provided a perspective similar to Asma’s. Just like Asma, Sami believed the notion of interaction concerns more teachers of linguistics than literature: ‘*(...)probably you find it (interaction) more with teachers of ESP (English*

for Specific Purposes) and linguistics more than with other teachers mainly teachers of literature...' In addition, Sami echoed Asma's conception about theory and practice and maintained that that *'experience is far more important than any theory. Theory is just a convention, but the reality of teaching is some else.'* Unlike Asma who was not very keen towards reading about pedagogical theories, Sami considered reading about pedagogical theories as beneficial. At the same time the participant stressed the fact that theories should not inform teachers' classroom practices. Rather, teachers' classroom practices should be informed by the teachers' overall teaching experiences and the type of learners he or she has in the classroom. Accordingly, Sami pointed out *'...it is good to know theories...read theories but don't stick to any method...your strategy should be based on all of your learnings and your experiences and the students themselves.'* Sami's account demonstrates an awareness of the reality of teaching, and the role of contextual particularities. Therefore, the participant's account, to a considerable extent, echoes the particularity principle of PMP (Kumaravadivelu, 2006).

Participant Sami firmly believed that the students' nonverbal behaviour in the classroom is a good indicator of the success or the failure of a particular teaching strategy. In these regards, Sami put it *'...you should listen with your eyes not with your ears...'* He also added *'...you teach, and you learn even from your students. Believe me that students are the basis of your strategy, so look at them.'* From the perspective of IC, non-verbal cues are an essential element for the establishment of a successful interaction (Kramersch, 1986; Plough et al., 2018). Furthermore, the participant's account seems to put learners at the centre of the teaching and learning process which implies the participant's compliance with the pedagogical principles of the LMD (Idri, 2005; Djamàa, 2013).

Similarly, the respondent Jamila acknowledged that she was unfamiliar with the notion of IC and considered it, at heart, a linguistic phenomenon.

No...frankly speaking, as civilisation teacher, I do not have so many notions and concepts, and background in linguistics...I am trying to do my best sometimes to read something from here, from there... Since I am teaching a lot of modules, also teaching at superior

school of economy... I want always to have some knowledge about economy and politics, about what is happening around the world...

{Jamila}

The participant's preoccupation with the teaching task in and outside the university seems to offer her little opportunity to explore areas other than her field of interest. Despite the challenge of time constraints, the respondent showed the initiative of expanding her knowledge in the field of linguistics through engaging in occasional reading. Unlike Asma and Sami, participant Jamila seemed more accepting of reading and learning about new teaching methods. In her account, the participant referred to the 'Canadian research' which she described as 'really amazing'. This PhD study covered some of the Canadian research such as Canale and Swain's (1980; 1983) work on communicative competence. The respondent also showed interest in reading about economy and politics as they are related to her field of interest, that is, civilisation. At the global level, topics such as economy and politics fall within the category of world knowledge, or as Kramsch (1986) referred to 'the external sphere of the interaction.' This dimension is significant to the theory of IC and the attainment of a successful interaction.

Unlike the other teachers of literature and civilisation, Ahmed and Talib reported that they heard of the notion of IC, and both maintained that their knowledge of the notion is general. However, like all teachers of literature and civilisation, both participants attributed their limited knowledge of IC to the fact that they were teachers of literature. For example, Ahmed reported, *'I have heard of it; however, I do not have the expertise to talk about it...I don't know about the literature available, as well as the findings that are generated from interactional competence.'* In a relatively similar fashion Talib maintained *'I have an idea about it, a vague idea...Since you know my lectures are more literature dealing with texts rather than with what you call discursive, if you want, interaction.'*

Both participants' accounts suggest lack of interest in the theories of EFL classroom interaction which further suggests that their classroom interaction experiences are informed by their classroom practical experiences rather than rooted in particular

pedagogical theory (Kumaravadivelu, 2006). Ahmed in particular demonstrated an awareness of the mismatch between EFL teaching and learning theory and the actual classroom practices. For Ahmed, the challenge that accompanies the application of pedagogical theory, including IC, lies in the incongruity between theory and practice (Kumaravadivelu, 2006). In this respect, Ahmed maintained that *'The challenges lie in this kind incongruity Between the EFL teaching and learning in theory, and the real situation we are faced with.'*

Regarding teachers of linguistics participants, only two participants were familiar with the notion of IC; Soumia and Laila. For example, Soumia maintained that it is challenging to apply a pedagogical theory in full because of the numerous challenges that characterise the context (Kumaravadivelu, 2001). Within these regards Soumia put it as follows, *'Yes, you read, you try to apply them in your classroom, but sometimes you cannot, maybe, apply a little bit...because there are so many challenges, and so many problems.'* Amongst the challenges, the participant listed the lack of ICT equipment: *'sometimes you want to do a kind of (Fr) vidéo assisté par ordinateur [computer assisted video]. (En) You know, we still have problems of means and all that in our institutions.'* The participant's account suggests that the use of ICT equipment might assist the students' development of IC. The impact of technology on learners' development of IC remains unexplored territory (Plough et al., 2018). However, it can be argued that the use of tools such as video conferencing might enhance Algerian EFL learner interactional ability through interacting with native speaker students and teachers from other universities.

Apropos the respondent Laila, she reported that she is familiar with the term IC as a big umbrella term; *'As a big umbrella term, yes, I came across this notion or concept....'* In this sense, Laila's account is somewhat similar to other teacher participants accounts such as Talib, and Ahmed, who reported a generic knowledge of IC. In term of her views on about pedagogical theory, the participant stressed the role of teachers' intuition in the classroom practice.

There is some an intuition to start with, even though training there is a teacher who's going to be intuitive and who will do a good thing at the right time. This intuition is okay to start with, but it needs to be

*structured, to be informed to have some explanation
to become a strategy, a teaching strategy.*

{Laila}

The participant usage of the notion of intuition in her classroom practice demonstrates an awareness of the complexity of EFL classrooms. According to the participant's account, intuition alone is not enough. It has to be systematised. The participant also maintained that *'the intuition helps it can be a good starter, but it's not sufficient. You need to know what you're doing, and why are you doing it and to what extent it's going to be profitable.'* The participant's account in this sense echoes the principles of practicality in PMP. Intuition might be viewed as a teacher's belief or assumption about particular classroom practice. The teacher will turn this intuition into a solid theoretical understanding through the process of reflection (Kumaravadivelu, 2006).

The remainder of teachers of linguistics either misidentified IC with the generic notion of interaction such as Hayam and Amal, or were uncertain, as in the case of the participant Amina. For instance, Hayam reported that she is slightly familiar with the notion of IC. According to Hayam, her knowledge of IC is limited because the notion of the interaction is underestimated in the institution due to large class size: *'Slight'* said the participant. *'not much to be honest. Sometimes, when we gather between teachers, when we have got a meeting, we talk about interaction, but we don't give it its right value. Why? Because in our Algerian universities, the groups are crowded.'* It is noticeable that the respondent misidentified of the notion IC with the general notion of interaction. In addition, attributing the underestimation of the notion of interaction to the large classes is consistent with the literature. Teacher-centred approaches, namely the banking model of education, are usually reinforced in the large class environments (Hornsby and Osman, 2014; Mulryan-Kyne 2010; Exeter et al. 2010).

Similarly, participant Amal also misidentified the notion of IC with the notion of interaction, as shown in the excerpt below.

Excerpt 1: Amal

Researcher: *Let's move on to something related to the notion of interactional competence. Have you heard of the notion of IC?*

Amal: *You mean interaction between students and teachers?*

Researcher: *Yes, teacher-student interaction, and student-student interaction.*

Amal: *I have heard of it, I have read about it, and I have used a bit of it I think in my thesis, doctoral thesis.*

Like the majority of the interviewed teachers, Amal views about the notion of IC seem to be informed by her personal experiences: *'To me it is natural, I think. You are here to explain something, and students are here. You talk, you say we are going to do that, can you bring, can you do, what do you think etcetera.'* The participant's account suggests a simplistic view of the nature of classroom interaction. The participant's perspective does not take into account the dominating perspective in the literature on the complex and dynamic nature of the interaction (Walsh, 2011; Kramsch, 1986; Young; 2011, Apple et al., 2013). Furthermore, Amal's use of the term *'to explain'* in relation to the teacher's role suggests an endorsement of the transmission model of education.

As for participant Amina, at first, she maintained that she had not heard of the notion of IC. However, when she was prompted whether she read anything about IC, she replied *'Maybe I've heard about it but not too much. Maybe I've read it somewhere because, you know, I am also preparing my research, maybe I came across this word but not too much.'* The participant repeated use of the word 'maybe' indicates uncertainty. In her account, the participant showed an inclination toward the concept of method. She maintained that, in her classrooms, she used the same methods that she learned in her didactic classes, the ones that she complained about their inadequacy in term of her preparation as a teacher (see Section, 5.3). *'Teaching method, for instance, I'm speaking about myself, I usually use, of course, from what I have learned from the module of didactics, teaching methods I try to apply some of them.'* The participant's account lacks the understanding principles of particularity, that is, pedagogy has to be congruent with a particular group of learners,

in a particular institution, in a particular sociocultural milieu (Kumaravadivelu, 2001; 2006). Therefore, the participant's account is not consistent with PMP.

To sum up, in most cases, both teachers and learners were unfamiliar with the notion of IC. However, participants' lack of familiarity did not impede them from voicing their own beliefs and experiences with the notion. Surprisingly, some of the participants who had stated that they had no formal experience with the notion IC reported a perspective that was relatively consistent with the literature on IC. The next theme will provide and discuss the participants' perspectives on IC in more depth.

5.5 Interactional competence: Teachers' perspectives and experiences

Each teacher participant had their own understanding of the notion of IC. Teachers' perspectives on IC varied depending on their personal and academic experiences, individual beliefs, the module they teach, as well as on the type of learners they have in their classroom. Although each teacher perspective is different, an attempt has been made to group participants' perspectives that were relatively similar to one another under the same subtheme. Figure 5.5 briefly summarises the different perspective on IC reported by the participants.

Figure 5.5: Teachers' perspective on interactional competence.

5.5.1 Interactional competence as knowledge transmission

Some teacher participants defined IC in terms of knowledge transmission. To these participants, to teach meant to transmit information or knowledge to students. Such conception is not consistent with the theory of IC, which suggests that knowledge is jointly constructed between teachers and learners (Kramsch, 1986; Walsh, 2012; Young, 2011). Participant Jamila, for example, maintained that the aim of IC is to convey the message.

Interaction is, of course, the way the teacher deals with his students in class. Of course, the aim of this competence is to convey your message, information the best way you can.

{Jamila}

The respondent defined interaction as '*the way the teacher deals with his students in class.*' The participant has an individualistic understanding of responsibility and unilateral management of interaction. According to respondent's account, the aim of IC is conveying the message and information, a conception which further reinforces her monologic view of interaction. Hence, the participant conception of IC does not accord with the literature.

In addition, during the interview, the participant viewed herself a knowledge provider '*Our role as a teacher, we have an objective, we have an aim, a goal to reach, which is making and conveying the message or the information the best way we could.*' It can be argued that the participant's self-image and her conception of what it entails to be a teacher seem to influence her practice (Larenas et al. (2015; Borg, 2015). In addition, the participant also appears to dominate the classroom talk as she seems to prioritise delivering the lesson over co-constructing it with her students:

For instance, I am teaching American civilisation. I am going to, for instance, start by the first lesson, which is the discovery of the New World. So, of course, in here the students are going to listen, I am

explaining, I am giving them information, I am trying to dig back to the history to the past...later we are going to interact, we are going to exchange...

{Jamila}

The participant's account is clearly suggestive of her inclination toward the transmission model of education. Not only Jamila seems to prioritise knowledge transmission over the practice of interaction in her classroom but also characterised students' passive listening as a form of interaction. The participant's conception of the notion of IC does not accord with the literature. From the stance of IC theory, unfolding the agenda of the lesson is a dual practice, not the sole responsibility of the teacher (Walsh, 2013).

The respondent Laila shared similar beliefs with Jamila. She also maintained that the aim of the IC is to convey a message.

From my understanding, interactional competence deals with all the skills that the teacher needs to develop for himself and in his students to able to convey a message, and appropriate feedback and reach the requirements of the course.

{Laila}

The respondent's account suggests that the main responsibilities for reaching the requirement lie with the teachers. According to Laila, to achieve the requirement of the course, the teacher needs to develop interactional skills for himself and his learners. The teachers play a central role in the development of the learners' IC and this requires the teachers to promote students' active participation and engagement in the classroom (Walsh, 2011; 2012). However, the aim of IC goes beyond conveying a message and receiving feedback to negotiating meaning and co-constructing knowledge (Walsh; 2012).

5.5.2 Interactional competence: paralinguistic features

Some participants' perspectives on IC put more emphasis on paralinguistic features such as gazes and body language. This includes Talib and Ahmed, senior teachers of literature with over 30 years of teaching experience. Talib viewed IC as a notion that transcends the knowledge of words and grammatical structures into the social and cultural dimension of language use.

Some years ago, I used to teach oral expression, and I wanted to make students know that language is not only words and grammatical structure, Okay! It has if you want a cultural background.

{ Talib }

For Talib, the knowledge of grammar and sentence structures are insufficient for someone to interact effectively, and one should pay attention to the paralinguistic elements on the interaction such gazes and gestures.

It is not enough to know words and structures to communicate effectively in certain contexts with native speakers. There is this cultural boundary that we need to detect not only words but also gazes gestures if you want many other things in order to communicate effectively.

{ Talib }

In his account, Talib did not view himself as a teacher who develop his students' IC because he is not a native speaker of English. One explanation for this is that Talib has an idealised view of native speakers (Doerr, 2009; Sung, 2010).

I'm not if you want from the native culture. It is very difficult to make students be accurate and effective communicators... perhaps if we had native teachers that are British or American...that would help the

students to acquire, to be aware of these extralinguistic aspects of language.

{ Talib }

Due to his idealised view of native speakers, the participant not only seems to undermine and doubt his capacity as a teacher to improve his students' interactional skills but also seems to undermine his students' interactional ability: *'they do not know how to deal with a native speaker, how to behave in a way. If a native speaker comes, they will shock him.'* The participant's account is consistent with the literature, as the idealisation of native speakers might affect teachers' self-image and his attitude towards the teaching task (Medgyes, 1992). In addition, from the quotation above, it is apparent that Ahmed emphasised accuracy over fluency. The participant admitted as much when the participant was invited to share his thoughts on some of the features of IC that are particular to Algerian HE context: *'It is difficult, we are not trained, and our program is a little very individual rather than a collective one, in testing, even in teaching we focus on the individual competence. How far one student can use correctly grammatical or linguistic structures.'* The participant's account is consistent with Walsh (2011, 2012), who suggested that much of what happens in language classroom concerns individual abilities rather than collective accomplishments of pedagogical goals.

Participant Ahmed provided a similar perspective about IC, namely, the emphasis on paralinguistics features of the interaction.

Interactional competence, it refers to the way how to start a conversation, how to manage a conversation, how to negotiate the conversation. It is a kind of skill that you acquire in order to have more than this kind of communicative competence because it's more than that. I don't know. I am not specialised in that, but I feel it's more than language. It deals with the gestures, paralanguage and all that...And I think eye contact. That's why I think it goes beyond language. It is part of pragmatics, I believe.

{Ahmed}

Similar to Talib, Ahmed also conceived IC in terms of individual ability. This is evident in the participant reference to IC as a skill that is acquired by an individual ‘*kind of skill that you acquire...*’ Another evidence is the participant believed that IC is part of pragmatics. According to Young (2011), IC and pragmatics are two separate phenomena. Pragmatic meanings are one element of IC. Unlike pragmatics, IC views participants’ use and understanding of pragmatic elements as mutually co-constructed by all participants in a discursive practice (ibid, p.93). Therefore, the participant’s account does not accord with the literature as it underscores the individual agency.

Broadly, Ahmed’s and Talib’s perspectives on IC agree with the literature with respect to their emphasis on the role of paralinguistic features in the success of the interaction. For example, Kramsch (1986) underscored the importance of the paralinguistic features in establishing successful interaction over grammatical accuracy. She argued that, to native speakers, the paralinguistic errors are more irritable than grammatical errors and communication breakdowns are more likely to occur because of the former rather than the latter.

5.5.3 Interactional competence in reading

In their accounts, Talib and Ahmed addressed an interesting dimension in the theory of IC, that is, interactional competence in reading. It is a dimension that was given a secondary position as the notion of IC seems to overemphasise the speaking or the oral dimension (Campbell-Larsen, 2014).

*...If you want most of my classes are literature classes.
I mean the discursive the dialogic aspect of my
classes is between the text and the student rather than
between two persons. It's a little bit different.*

{Talib}

As a teacher of literature, Talib wants his student to learn how to interact effectively with the literary text. The interpersonal interaction is assigned a subordinate status in Talib's account: '*...what I want from the students is how to deal with the text, an authentic text like literary text...this is the interaction that I want to implement in the students...*' For him, interacting with a text is much more difficult than interpersonal interaction: '*it's very difficult, more difficult than the oral interaction*', said Talib.' He added, '*I'm speaking now, there are gestures, mimics, engages that helps. When you read a text, you have not these things. You are left with words.*'

There is a good ground for the validity of the participant's argument. However, it cannot be verified owing to the limited literature on IC in the area of reading skill because of the theory over-concentration on the oral dimension of the interaction as previously noted. Regardless, the respondent's account seems to correspond with the literature as IC is an omnipresent phenomenon in listening, speaking, reading and writing (Kramsch, 1986; Campbell-Larsen, 2014).

It can be argued that, in literature classes, in particular, there are two interrelated dimensions of IC. The first involves the individual interaction with a text. The second one is discursive in nature, where a group of participants can share and unfold their ideas about a particular text. Such an understanding of IC might be exemplified through drawing on participant Ahmed's perspective.

The more I give readings..., the more I believe that students are really able to participate and to be fully involved in class, and I feel like the building up is quite obvious from this kind of give and take, this kind of interchange...

{ Ahmed }

In his account, Ahmed maintained that students are more likely to interact and engage with the content of the lesson when they have knowledge about the topic of discussion. This perspective is consistent with the literature as the topic of discussion, or world knowledge is an important element for the establishment of a successful interaction (Kramsch, 1986).

Participant Sami also provided similar views to Ahmed and Talib. He maintained that he uses interaction as a tool to motivate his students to read and to engage with a literary text. *'Probably, as a teacher of literature, I try to use it in the way of motivating students to read the novels and, in a way, to see beyond the words the novel contains.'* To motivate his students to interact, Sami reported that he uses referential questions. For example, the participant stated that he asks questions such as *'who writes? When you really write something, are you really the writer? How many selves do we have? So, my aim is to squeeze their mind but not press so hard.'* These types of questions are meant to extend learners' turns, and they are more communicative than display questions (Walsh, 2011). Therefore, the participant seems to have an understanding of IC despite his lack of interest in reading about theories of teaching, as noted in Section 5.4.

Sami's conception of IC emphasised the notion of the students' motivation. *'It is a fact of making yourself a teacher and a learner and to know how to motivate students. How to interact means make yourself one of them, yet you show that you are a teacher more than a student.'* Herein, the participant seems to be referring to the notion of intersubjectivity which entails putting oneself in the shoes of the other in order to establish a successful interaction (Kramersch, 1986; Young, 2011; Walsh, 2011). For Sami, a teacher should integrate within his students as a learner to bring power balance and to make them feel sufficiently at ease to interact. At the same time, Sami maintained that a teacher should preserve his authority as a teacher. Sami's way of thinking is rooted in the shared Algerian cultural understanding that a teacher should always be perceived as an authority in the classroom (Miliani, 2012; Miliani; 2017).

5.5.4 Interactional competence as competency in the four skills

According to participant Soumia's perspective, IC is an all-encompassing term and not only limited to the speaking skill. Rather, for her, IC refers to students' competence in the four skills, that is, listening, speaking, reading, and writing: *'It means that our students should be competent enough in the four skills to achieve a successful interaction.'* The definition of IC provided by the participant is consistent with the literature. Kramersch (1986), for example, argued that IC applies to both speaking and writing. It also applies to reading (Campbell-Larsen, 2014), as well as

to listening (May, 2011). Therefore, interaction is an essential component of the four skills. In addition, the participant seems to stress the fact that developing those skills is the learner's responsibility. This means that the participant perspective is aligned with the principles of the LMD system (Idri, 2012; Djamàa, 2013), and PMP which views learners as autonomous and responsible for their own learning (Kumaravadivelu, 2006; Kumaravadivelu, 2001).

In her account, the participant provided an insider look at how oral expression classes are usually held.

You must have gone through this experience. You know a video or something, or a cassette, or a CD, where the native speaker is speaking, and you have to find out, and you have to listen to the text, answer questions and all that. But this is not that. What I wanted is that face to face interaction.

{Soumia}

The account provided by the participant on how oral classes are usually taught in the institution recalls the audio-lingual method (ALM). As explored in Chapter 3, ALM focuses on habit formation of native speakers through memorisation and repetition of dialogues and students are generally viewed as passive agents (Mart, 2013; Larsen-Freeman, 2000; Richards and Rodgers, 2014; Savignon, 2017). The participant seems to be aware of the drawbacks of the ALM, viewing face to face interaction as a more suitable teaching strategy. This means that the participant is more inclined towards the use of interaction as a tool for teaching and learning (Walsh, 2012). It remains unsurprising, however, to see a continuance of the use of the ALM in the institution is unsurprising given the inadequacy of the professional teacher training programs as explored in Section, 5.3, as well as teacher resistance to the innovative teaching practices brought by the LMD system reforms (Idri, 2005; Miliani, 2012; Choubane, 2019, Missoum, 2015).

In addition, in voicing her conception about IC, participant Soumia emphasised the role of interpersonal relationships. *'...according to me, interaction and social interaction, the relationship between student and lecturer. it's something very, very*

special, and very, very important.' The participant's emphasis on interpersonal interaction with respect to the notion of IC is owing to her previous experiences as an international student in the UK. During the interview, the participant seemed to be satisfied with her previous interaction experience with her native-speaker tutors. She described their interaction as '*spontaneous*' and '*fluid*' unlike her interaction with her students in the classroom. The participant's experience in the UK opened her eyes toward the role of interpersonal interaction in the promotion of students' learning. Soumia's beliefs and her actual practice are not consistent with one another. Her attempt to provide the same interactional experience for her students faced a considerable degree of resistance from '*decision-makers*' in the institution (see Chapter 6, Section 6.6).

5.5.5 Interactional competence as a social skill

For some participants, IC is a social skill. A proponent of the aforementioned belief is participant Asma.

This competence, it's more of social skill in a way because the classroom is no longer just like students sit in their seats behind the desks, and just like listening, it's more about them, than it is about the teacher. So, I think it's a skill for the teacher to be able to talk less and listen more to the students, because the students if you just give them a chance, they have a lot of ideas.

{ Asma }

The participant seems to reject the view of students as passive receptors of information. Instead, Asma viewed the classroom as a social environment where teacher and learners interact and negotiate their social identities. According to the participant, IC competence is a social skill which entails teachers reducing their talk time so that the students have more opportunities for learning through interaction. In this respect, Walsh (2006, 2012) argued that by reducing their talk-time and resisting filling up the silence in the classroom, teachers would immediately maximise learning opportunities and learning for their learners.

Besides, participant Asma viewed IC as a skill that is innate in some people and as one that develops overtime. *'I think it's something we're born with. And it's a skill that you kind of refine with time. Sometimes they're extremely shy people who turn into very outgoing people after having some class interaction or acting in the classroom'* The participant's account seems to echo the socio-constructivist view of learning, where the learners' interactional abilities are developed through active involvement and participation (Walsh, 2011; Larsen-Freeman, 2010).

5.5.6 Interactional competence as a change of paradigm

Amal's perspective on IC was closely related to the Asma's. Both perspectives echoed the notion of the shift from a teacher-centred approach towards a learner-centred approach. In her account, Amal addressed power imbalance in the institution's classroom, and defined IC as a change of paradigm:

It means... it is a change of paradigm where the first the old one, as usual, it still existing here, the teacher is above all, and the students are here to listen and to believe everything the teacher says. The change is that the teacher and the students interact, talk together, and the students' views are taken into account by the teacher.

{Amal}

According to the participant's account, the power imbalance between teachers and learners still exists in the institution. The teacher is still being perceived as a powerful figure in the classroom. Hence, the participant's account suggests that there is a resistance the implantation to the LMD system, which in its essence, came to establish power balance through reducing the role of the teacher into a facilitator of learning, and promoting learners' autonomy (Idri, 2012; Djamàa, 2013). For Amal, the change of paradigm constitutes moving from the view of the teachers as a power figure and dictator of instructions and students as passive agents into a paradigm that diminishes teachers' power, and promotes learner's autonomy to allow for a dialogical interaction. Hence, the participant's account suggests that the

new paradigm features the use of interaction as a tool for teaching and learning (Walsh, 2012; 2013).

For Amal, the responsibility of learning falls on the student, and the teacher's role is only to guide the students. In this respect, Amal defined interaction as *'what happens between the teacher and students...the teacher letting the students prepare the work, talk, walk around, and the teacher is here to guide them.'* Therefore, the participant's account is consistent with the principle of the LMD system (Idri, 2012; Djamàa, 2013). However, within the framework of IC and PMP, teachers are considered more that guides or 'facilitators' of learning. They are creator and maximisers of learning opportunities (Walsh; 2006; Kumaravadivelu; 2001).

5.5.7 Interactional competence as freedom

The respondent Amina defined IC competence in terms of freedom. The term freedom in this context primarily refers to the state of being free from, or not being controlled by psycho-affective factors such as shyness, fear, and lack of self-confidence.

How to make learners interact with each other. It is the ability of the learners to interact with each other more freely. Of course, between the teacher and the students and the students themselves.

{ Amina }

The participant reference to the notion of IC as an ability is consistent with the literature (Walsh, 2012). Also, defining IC from the part of the participant as 'the learners' ability to interact more freely' suggests that the students are not free to interact. Amina's perspective is inherent in her belief which is informed by her personal experience that the most major problem that students suffer from is the lack of self-confidence: *'we have to overcome their fear of speaking in front of others. this is the main problem with our students.'* Accordingly, in her account, the participant stressed aspects such as making students at comfortable and at ease in order to promote interaction in her classes: *'we should create an easy atmosphere, comfortable atmosphere so that your learners would be more at ease when they*

speak. According to Amina's account, students are not able to interact freely because some teachers are authoritative: *'in our context and the Algerian context; the teacher has an important role in the classroom. The teacher is still a little bit authoritative.'* This is consistent with the literature as teachers' authoritative behaviour in the classroom constitutes one of the main obstacles behind learners' passive behaviour (Choubane, 2019).

Amina also believed that teachers' ability to 'interact freely' in and out of the classroom depends on their personality *'...some teachers it's part of their personality to interact freely with people, even outside you find them like that.'* Thus, Amina's account seems to suggest that that personality might influence individuals' ability to interact which denotes an individualistic conception of competence, and this is not consistent with the literature of IC (Walsh, 2012; Young, 2011, Kasper and Wagner, 2011). Interactional competence 'cannot be reduced to an individual intrapsychological property' (Kasper and Wagner, 2011, p.118). Participants should always attend to each other's contribution. Thus, IC is concerned with co-fluency rather than fluency (Walsh, 2012; McCarthy, 2005).

After exploring and discussing the teachers' perspectives experiences about IC, the following section will explore and discuss students' perspectives and experiences with the notion of IC.

5.6 Students' perspectives on interactional competence

Data analysis revealed that none of the students from both focus groups heard of the notion of IC, as shown in the excerpt below.

Excerpt 2: Focus group one

Researcher: *Have you heard of the notion of interactional competence?*

S1: *Never*

Ss: *No*

S2: *No*

S3: *No*

Excerpt 3: Focus group two

Researcher: *Can I ask you a question? have you heard of interactional competence, classroom interaction competence?*

Ss: No

S1: *Like a theory?*

Researcher: *Yeah, have you heard about this?*

S1: *No.*

It was very surprising to see a considerably high level of interaction in both focus groups, given the teachers' complaints about students' level, level of participation, and passive behaviour. The overwhelming majority of teacher participants reported that the participation level falls below average. *'...around 35 until 40 you will be limited to five to six students who are interacting with the teacher. So basically, it is seldom to meet a class which is interactionally competent, honestly.'* {Hayam}. Similarly, Laila also maintained that *'... you always have the same five or six who will speak. The others don't even take the burden.'* There is a close relationship between learning and participation (Walsh, 2013). A low level of students' involvement is not usually a good indicator. Since learning equals doing, fewer students' involvement entails less learning opportunities (Ibid).

Contrary to the teachers' accounts, most of the students were enthusiastic and confident in expressing their views, which begs the question, what makes a difference? Before answering this question, first, it is important to gain an understanding of the students' perspectives about IC. The Table below contains transcripts from both focus group interviews where students shared, according to their own understanding, what interactional competence meant to them.

Table 5.6: Students' perspectives on interactional competence.

Focus Group 1 views on IC	Focus Group 2 views on IC
R: According to your own perspectives, what does interactional competence mean to you?	R: According to your own perspectives, what does interactional competence mean to you?
S1: The ability to interact with others and Share your ideas and thoughts	S1: The quality of interaction between the classroom students' and the teacher

<p>S2: The extent to which interaction is taking place between the teachers and the classmates</p> <p>S3: The level of exchange between the teachers and students.</p> <p>S4: Competence is knowledge, so it is the knowledge of how to interact with others</p> <p>S5: [interruption] Sometimes you have the competence, but you don't have the performance</p> <p>Ss: Yeah</p> <p>Ss: Yeah</p> <p>S7: You have the competence, but you cannot perform well.</p> <p>S8: It depends on the environment and the context.</p>	<p>S2: [elaboration] And to build towards the session</p> <p>S3: I think this notion means that ahh that ahh in the classroom teacher and. the student ahh discuss and talk to build the listen together and come up with ahh</p> <p>S4: [elaboration] use of specifics techniques to make ahh... I don't know the right environment for effective teaching.</p> <p>S4: the teacher is not the centre anymore, he is part of the discussion</p> <p>S5: The relationship between the students and the teacher and how to teach with them and what are the techniques that are included to interact with them.</p> <p>R: [inviting a shy student] What do you think of the notion of interactional competence?</p> <p>S6: Like she said (laughter)</p>
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As shown above, the students' account demonstrated an understanding of the notion of IC. The students discussed numerous fundamentals of the notion of IC. In Focus Group 1, for example, S1 referred to IC as the ability to interact with others. S2 defined IC as the extent to which interaction is present in the classroom. Defining IC in terms of 'ability' by S1 recalls Walsh's definition of IC (Walsh, 2011; 2012). S2 and S3 conception of IC suggests an understanding of the importance of interaction in the classroom (Walsh, 2011; Walsh; 2012; Kramsch, 1986; Young, 2011; Hall; 2018). S4 and S5 accounts echo Chomsky's (1965) famous distinction between competence (knowledge) and performance (ability). Using his previous experience with Chomsky's conception of competence, S4 logically deduced that IC should be defined as knowledge. S5 raised a very interesting point in respect to the theory of

IC as the participants distinguished between interactional competence (IC), and interactional performance (IP). Literature in respect of the interrelatedness between IC and IP is limited and more studies are needed in this particular area. Taguchi (2015), for example, distinguished between IC and IP. While IC is concerned with language use in the social situation, IP is contingent on the social background and experiences of the individuals.

Similarly, participants from Focus Group 2 demonstrated an understanding of IC. S1 and S4 conception of IC highlights the idea the quality of interaction should be prioritised over the quantity of interaction, that is, promoting interaction that is congruent with particular pedagogical goals (Walsh, 2006; 2012). S2 and S3 accounts echo the idea of teachers' and learners' collaborative efforts in unfolding the agenda of the lesson (Walsh, 2012). S4 view of decentralising the teacher as an important aspect in IC is consistent with the literature. Walsh (2013, p.55) pointed out that for learners to be able to articulate what they mean, the teacher has to adopt a student-centred, and decentralised role.

In respect of the performative elements of IC, as shown in the above synoptic overview, the students were able to demonstrate a good level of IC. Students knew when to speak, and when to hold the floor. There were also some interruptions, where students build upon each other's contributions. Probably, more features would have emerged with in-depth analysis using CA methodology, which was not possible within this thesis as it was beyond its capacity, as well as due to time limitation. Regardless, such a considerable level of participation is a very surprising finding given the teachers complaints about students' level, and passive behaviour in the classroom as previously noted. One explanation is that each student comes into the classroom with a basic level of IC (Kecskes et al., 2018). Students' accounts also offered other perspectives which might explain why their fluency and level of engagement are better during the focus group that during their interaction with some of their teachers in the classroom. In this respect, consider the following excerpt from Focus Group 1.

Excerpt 4: Focus group one

S1: *The first challenge is language difficulty; not all of us speak fluent English.*

Ss: [shouting] *yes fluency*

R: *What I can see here is that you are all fluent. So, what makes the difference?*

S2: *We feel more comfortable to talk*

S3: *I think the group is small...like we can talk our minds, not like the classroom there are 25 students... it is the pressure*

S4: *I think it depends on the teacher*[interruption]

Ss: *Yes*

S4: *He can make the lesson funny and make us feel comfortable.*

R: *Are you comfortable now?*

Ss: *Yes [Laughter]*

S2: *Yes, very much*

Ss: [Laughter]

Regarding the above excerpt, students seem to doubt their fluency level. The researcher reassured them that they are all fluent, which was the case for most of them. This reassurance invited more students to express their views on what makes them feel motivated to interact. Being comfortable was the number one reason. The students felt at ease during the focus group interviews, possibly because the researcher was approximately at the same age as the students. The latter allowed the researcher to connect with the students at the interpersonal level, hence the laughter. There was also the convenience of the small class size, as pointed out by S3, which is something the students are not used to, given the prevalence of large classes in the institution. In addition to the comfort factor, the students maintained that the teacher's sense of humour plays an important role in promoting students' engagement. The literature on foreign and second language classroom interaction revealed a strong connection between the use of humour and students' engagement. For example, in her review of the role of humour and play in language classrooms, Reddington (2015) pointed out that the use of humour might contribute to building

rapport and establishing relationships, reduce anxiety, promote group cohesion and develop relationships.

S4 account suggests the absence or minimal use of humour in their classes. His account might also be suggesting that teachers are severe. The latter might be rooted in the shared cultural belief that there should be a barrier between teachers and students. As will be explored in detail in the following chapter, the hierarchical power structure in the institution, and particularly the unequal power relations in the classroom constitutes an impediment to students' engagement and to the operationalisation of performative element of IC.

Chapter 6: The influence of power relations within the institution on interactional competence

6.1 Introduction

The findings established that the institution operates within a complex web of power relations (Foucault, 1984; 1982). According to teachers' and learners' accounts, the power structure within the institution is of a hierarchical nature (Mililani, 2017). It was found that the hierarchical power structure runs deep in the Algerian society. Individuals occupying a higher position within an institution, educational or otherwise, tend to have higher power and authority. At the level of the family (macro-level), the parents are viewed as the most powerful agents, the source of orders and instruction and the children as less powerful, compliant individuals (Semmouk; 2005).

At the level of the institution (Meso level), there are at least three layers of power at work which have had an impact on teachers' and learners' classroom interactive practices. The first layer of power is the university administration; the body responsible for enacting rules and regulations that govern the university. The second layer of power is the teacher; the power figure in the classroom and the provider of knowledge. The third layer of power is the students; the recipients of knowledge and individuals that undergo behavioural control who are expected to abide by the rules and conventions of the classroom.

The highest level of power that was referred to by teachers is the Ministry of Higher Education; a government body that is considered the sources of all decisions and policy-making, including the introduction of the LMD reforms. The analysis of the teachers' interviews revealed the imposition of the LMD system upon the workforce despite their legitimate concerns regarding the success of the reform. The findings also established that there is a strong correlation between the challenges that impeded the implementation of the LMD and those reported by the participants that might constitute an impediment to the operationalisation of performative elements of IC in the Algerian HE classrooms. The LMD system, as a system based on western philosophy, shares many aspects with the philosophy underpinning the IC such as

asserting the importance of dialogic interaction and promoting learners' autonomy (Choubane, 2019, Missoum, 2015; Idri, 2005; Djamàa, 2013).

6.2 The LMD system reforms between imposition and resistance

Teachers' account revealed that the LMD system was imposed upon the workforce, despite their continuous rejection of the system since its early stages of implementation (Idri, 2005; Mohammed, 2011). The institution's department of the English language was one of the last departments that adopted the LMD reforms: *'I tell you what, our Department was among the last Departments to adopt the LMD system.'*, said Soumia. In the same manner, Laila also reported the following *'We didn't have a choice. The English department was the last to apply the LMD system...we have kept refusing this because we don't have the means for tutors, and the classes are too big.'*

From the above accounts, it appears that the workforce had no alternative except to obey ministerial orders and to implement the system even though the institution does not have the necessary means for its proper implementation (Mohammed, 2011). The participants' accounts depict the hierarchical structure of the Algerian higher education system (Miliani, 2017). The imposition of the LMD reforms is not a surprising finding. In fact, Algeria has a history of ignoring workforce views when it comes to implementing reforms. The implementation of Arabisation, CBA, and CLT are prime examples of reforms imposition (See Chapter 2).

Jamila's account also raised the issue of the perceived imposition. She maintained that,

The implementation of this system...moving from the traditional one to this one, I was just wondering why? ...Of course, the answer is because we are living in globalisation. So, either you join, or you leave. We have to adopt the system.

{Jamila}

According to Jamila's account, the shift from the classical system to the LMD system is due to globalisation. The participants' account is consistent with the literature as the introduction of the LMD reforms is associated with the pressure exerted by globalisation on the Algerian system of HE (Miliani 2012; Djamàa, 2013). The participant awareness of the impact of globalisation on the Algerian HE system might be attributed to her interest in reading about economy and politics noted in Chapter 5, Section 5.4.

Jamila's conception of the LMD system imposition on the workforce is different from Laila's and Soumia's. Her understanding of 'imposition' is not circumscribed within a local governmental body, such as the ministry of higher education. Instead, in a sense, her account alludes to the presence of another layer of power that has the ability to shape the local higher educational system, that is, global economy and politics.

It is important to recall that European reforms of BP or the LMD is an Anglo-Saxon inspiration that is tightly associated with the international competitiveness in the global market that has little to do with the economic and cultural realities of Algeria (Kelfaoui, 2009). For many teachers, the LMD system was perceived as incongruent with the Algerian educational culture. For example, Amal believed that the LMD system does not fit the Algerian academic culture because of the unequal power relations between teachers and students.

It is not for us...it is not the model for us, it's been imported, it's done for the circulation of students in Europe to help them, but it's not for the African. We still have the old view of the master above all,

{Amal}

The participant's account indicates an apparent alienation of the LMD system by using the expression 'it's not for us'. Amal believed that the LMD system was only created to allow for students' mobility in Europe. Her perspective is not consistent with the literature as the LMD system was introduced to allow for students' mobility throughout the world, including Algerian students (Idri, 2005; Idri, 2012; Miliani 2012, 2016; Djamàa, 2013).

Other participants expressed their rejection of the LMD system through demonstrating their appreciation of the classical system. Hayam, for example, was utterly unsatisfied about the LMD system because of the large groups and classes and the overloaded syllabus.

I am not satisfied at all. Personally, I do prefer that we go back to the ancient regime for having a BA degree in four years better than to have three years of licence, without giving enough opportunities to our learners.

{Hayam}

Elsewhere Hayam added that,

It (LMD) is worsening our system. We have to be very clear with our words. We were better because now we have got in the first year 12 groups...I am really deceived with our new system, the LMD. It is destructive more than constructive.

{Hayam}

According to Hayam, three years are not enough for a bachelor's degree. For her, three years do not provide enough opportunities for students to learn and assimilate the material properly compared to the old system where students had a four-year bachelor's degree. The minimisation of four years of bachelor's degree into three years occurred with the implementation of the LMD system. The aim is to synchronise the Algerian higher education systems with that Europe and the USA to allow for students' mobility (Djamàa, 2013; Kelfaoui, 2009). According to Hayam's account, the workforce is not coping properly with the changes brought by the LMD system. Particularly, the expression of 'The LMD is worsening our system' implies that the LMD system is a system within a system. Here, the participant is suggesting that the LMD perpetuated the old habit of the workforce, and they are still struggling, and in the process of coping with the change.

Hayam's account also drew attention to the impact of the phenomenon of massification. According to her, the phenomenon was brought by the implementation of the LMD, and this is consistent with the literature as 'massification' was a core part of the LMD system reforms (Bouchikhi and Zine, 2017). As maintained by the research participant, the impact of the phenomenon of 'massification' in the institution is evident in the increased number of first-year students. Hayam's account clearly indicates that massification had a notable impact on the quality of EFL teaching and learning in the institution, and this was demonstrated by the participant's disappointment in the LMD reform.

For some participants such as Talib and Amina, the LMD system encourages students to be lazy because it offers them far too many chances to pass.

The LMD system is working works with credits or points something like that. They make students I think lazy. Because if you do not get your module this year. You can pass it the next year, and you have a credit of the module from the previous year. I think it's not really good for students for our students.

{ Amina }

Amina seems to be less informed about the LMD system of evaluation, and this is evident in her uncertainty which was demonstrated through her use the expression '*something like that*'. The LMD system of evaluation, technically, works with credits or what is commonly known as the European Credit Transfer System (ECTS), and not points. In her account, Amina seems to be referring to the system of compensation. This system allows students to compensate for failed modules with the grades of passed modules (Mohammed and Brahim, 2010). In many cases, students end up compensating fundamental modules with secondary modules just because they require minimal effort, and this might encourage laziness (ibid). Similarly, Talib also had some reservation about the LMD system of compensation.

It is not the LMD system. It's a system that has no name. It's started with a copy of the French LMD, but they have perverted it. With new laws and new regulations, they killed its heart...they killed its spirit...In the LMD system, students are supposed to pass each module separately. Now, they have perverted it with this system of compensation which is in contradiction with the LMD system.

{Talib}

Talib's account on the LMD system of compensation is erroneous. His perspective about the LMD system of compensation is not consistent with the literature. As explored above, the compensation system is within the LMD philosophy, and by no means is an alteration of the LMD philosophy as Talib pointed out. Like Amina, this shows a lack of familiarity with the LMD system. Besides, Amina and Talib's fixation on the structure of the LMD system rather than on its pedagogy recalls the common criticism that the LMD system is only implemented in terms of structure and not in terms of pedagogy (Idri, 2005; Djamàa, 2013; Khelfaoui, 2009). Regardless, the participants' concern about the threat the compensation system might pose to students' learning and motivation is valid and aligns with the literature. For example, Labeled (2007, as cited Mohammed and Brahim, 2010) referred to the compensation system as 'pedagogical cemetery' and found that it affects students' motivation and encourages them to look for easy ways to pass.

The majority of teachers agreed on the fact the old system still prevails. In this regard, Ahmed maintained that *'I believe that many of the teachers are still within the classical system, and still teaching the same way they used to teach before...'* On a related note, Soumia provided a similar perspective:

For some teachers, the LMD system is the classical system in an LMD shell... all these teachers in the English Department they used to teach in the classical system. Now, when the LMD was adopted, so there is a shift. There must be a change. But they

refuse to change. Some teachers are very reluctant to the LMD system.

{Soumia}

Ahmed and Soumia's accounts indicate that many teachers are still clinging to the classical system teaching habits. Particularly, Soumia's account raised the issue of the teachers' stiffness to adjust their practices to the new reforms (Mohammed and Brahim, 2010). Her account also suggests her endorsement of the LMD reforms. The expression '*the LMD system is the classical system in an LMD shell*' featured in Soumia's account eloquently echoes a popular perspective in the literature which argues that the structure of the LMD system, which includes the three-cycle system LMD, teaching units, and system of credits, is emphasised over the fundamental pedagogical content that underpins the LMD reforms such as the promotion of dialogic interaction, and learners' autonomy (Kelfaoui, 2009).

The same phenomenon was also reported by participants Jamila and Hayam. Their accounts also raised the negligence of the content of the pedagogical canons of the LMD in the institution.

The implementation of the system it's just the label. Okay, it was changed from the traditional classical one to the new one, which is the LMD, but of course, the modules are the same. The syllabus, the schedule is the same.

{Jamila}

No. we did not see a difference between the ancient regime and the new regime. It is only a label, But the content and the management of the classes is the same. Even the syllabus, or the syllabi of all the modules.

{Hayam}

The participants' referred to the status of the implementation of the LMD system in the institution as a label. The usage of the term label is very similar to the term shell used by Soumia's in her account. Both terms seem to convey the idea that the LMD is only a front to old pedagogical content. According to Jamila's and Hayam's account, the syllabi of the modules has not been readjusted to the new reforms. The syllabus issue will be addressed in detail later in this chapter (see Section, 6.5.1).

In general, the participants' statements regarding the current status of the implementation of the LMD, gives the impression that the existing system is a Hybrid between two systems, the LMD and the classical system. The notion of hybridization was explicitly expressed in the Laila's and Talib's accounts. Laila, for example, maintained that,

The LMD system is taught...it's a kind of a hybrid teaching, between the classical and the LMD system. Concerning the principles of the system itself. Of course, the marks, moving from one grade to the other is within the LMD principles, but the teaching itself the philosophy of teaching and learning, I don't feel they are what the LMD is expecting them to be.

{Laila}

Similarly, Talib argued that,

We have a system that looks like nothing. It's not the old system, and it's not the LMD system. It's a strange combination of both. And so, it produces the same if you want low level.

{Talib}

Laila and Talib's accounts embody this idea of teachers being torn between the classical ways of teaching, and western pedagogy (Miliani, 2012; 2017). Therefore, their accounts, broadly, highlight the clash between two distinct pedagogical trends; traditional Islamic pedagogy and the western pedagogy, that is, one which promotes

unequal powers relation and the banking model of education, and one that encourages equality of roles and promotes dialogic interaction (ibid).

The clash between the two pedagogies seems to have created tension in teacher-teacher relationships. Teachers who think that their practices are aligned with the LMD requirements heavily criticised, and in other instances, mocked resisting teachers. Asma, for example, mocked her colleagues' way of teaching and described it as one that belongs to the middle ages.

I think they have a problem with their teaching methods. They need to work on their teaching methods. Because we don't live in the Middle Ages. And maybe even during the Middle Ages, there were there was some kind of interaction between people.

{ Asma }

Soumia's account was somewhat similar to Asma's account above.

There are some teachers who are very reluctant to use some technology. Some teachers are very old in this business of teaching. So, I don't mean myself, but still, they have been educated under another system. It's not the 21st-century era.

{ Soumia }

The above accounts communicate more than a clash between two different perspectives. They are suggestive of the fragility of the social fabric inside the institution. Participants' use of mockery in their account can be viewed as an example of the nature of behind the scenes discourse about teachers whose classroom practices are not aligned with the LMD reforms. This discourse might be harmful to teacher-teacher relationships and teacher-student relationships, and ultimately on the quality of EFL education in the institution. It seems that teachers whose practices are aligned with the LMD system reforms act as agents of surveillance for those who are not

(Foucault, 1977). This system of surveillance creates conformity to the *status quo* or be more exact to the 'new' *status quo* brought by western-based reforms.

The imposition of the LMD reforms upon a workforce whose educational culture is incompatible with the LMD and within an institution that lacks the necessary means for its successful implementation, resulted in the LMD system being emptied of its substance and led to the maintenance of old practice. As Talib maintained, *'they killed its philosophy...the LMD as it was proposed in the beginning is a very good system.'* It is perhaps true that the LMD system, at least in theory, is a good system. In practice, the evidence suggests that the system is not compatible with the Algerian sociocultural context. Rebalancing power between teachers and students through promoting students' autonomy and reducing teacher role into a 'facilitator' is still ink on paper. As Amal maintained, *'I have not seen a change really a change maybe it's written somewhere in the paper that it is LMD (laughter), but it is still the old system. Really, nothing new.'*

The imbalanced power relations between teachers and students are rooted in the shared cultural belief that teachers by virtue of their knowledge and experience are assigned a higher status than learners (Miliiani, 2017; Choubane, 2019). The shared cultural belief that promotes teachers' superiority is the main reason for the teachers' tendency to dominate the classroom talk. The analysis of teachers' interviews revealed the imbalanced power relations is a phenomenon that dates to the time the teacher participants were EFL learners (Richards and Lockhart; 1996; Farrell, 2007). Therefore, in order to understand the contemporary nature of teachers and learners power relations, it is important to draw on the teachers' former classroom interaction experiences as EFL learners.

6.3 Looking back: Teachers' former experiences as EFL learners

There was a general agreement between the teachers' accounts that their former teachers always had the upper hand in the classroom talk. This was clearly articulated in the accounts of the participants Laila and Amina who perceived no difference between their current classroom interaction experience as teachers, and their previous experience as EFL learners. *'I think it's the same thing. We did not have much chance to talk. Not to talk but to interact outside the oral expression class. We were Speaking*

of course, but it has always been teachers centred.’, said Laila. Amina echoed the views of her colleague and maintained that *‘I think it’s the same what I’m seeing as a teacher. I think it’s the same situation, the same problem. Usually, it is a teacher-centred classroom.’*

The above account clearly indicates unequal power relations and teachers’ increased talk-time. According to the participants’ accounts, most of the classes were teachers centred, and interaction was only circumscribed to the oral expression classes. In an agreement with his colleagues’ perspectives and experiences, Ahmed maintained that *‘I believe that the most important situations I remember in which we really interact was in one course, which is oral expression and comprehension. In the other courses, I believe, we were only recipients, we were very passive.’* Jamila also shared the same perspective and experience: *‘it (interaction) was really applied and practised, and we really enjoyed this competence. It was, of course, in oral sessions, in which of course, we were explaining, expressing our points of views.’*

Limiting interaction to the oral expression is still an ongoing phenomenon in the institution. In these regards, Soumia maintained that,

In our University, and especially in our Department, I feel that this interaction is only included in the oral expression module which is not a good idea, and one-hour and a half or three hours a week but it’s only first and second-year BA, so that’s why it is not enough. I suggest oral expression should in the three years BA.

{Soumia}

Soumia took issue not only with limiting interaction to the oral classes. She also argued that the time allocated for oral expression classes per week (3 hours on average) is not sufficient, especially when it is one of the few opportunities for students to interact in English. To maximised students’ opportunities to interact in the target language, Soumia suggested that the oral expression should be taught along the three years of the BA degree. This indicates that Soumia’s is aware of the

importance of maximising interaction opportunities for learners in the learning of the target language (Walsh, 2012; Kumaravadivelu, 2006).

A possible explanation for the ongoing existence of this phenomenon, that is, limiting interaction to the oral classes was offered by Laila. She maintained that '*...As the other modules are called content modules, the teachers think still they have a content to convey. And they are the only ones who have the content, so they come with it, they convey, and they leave.*' Laila's account is demonstrative of how teachers' beliefs about the nature of the modules affect their classroom practices (Borg, 2006; 2018). According to Laila, the name '*content modules*' ascribed to the modules other than oral expression is suggestive of a content to be delivered. Therefore, teachers assume the role of the knowledge providers and limit interaction to the oral expression classes. Hence, the banking model of education in the institution seems to be reinforced by the type of discourse used by the workforce to name the modules.

According to the teachers' accounts, apart from the oral expression classes, lecturing and dictation were the dominant forms of teaching at the time when they were EFL learners. Their role as learners was only to listen and take notes: '*At that period when I was a learner... the most important thing is to present a lesson, to give the lesson sometimes to dictate, sometimes just to distribute polly copies and that's all. If he is going to do so, of course, the task is done.*', said Jamila. This perspective was echoed by many participants. For example, Amal reported that '*We had no interaction. No interactions with the teachers. The teachers explain the course and leave the class, that's it.*' She also added that '*I don't remember having other things than just the teacher is here, and the students listen and take notes, and that's all.*' In similar veins, Hayam also maintained: '*I have never been given the opportunity to interact.*'

The teacher participants former EFL teachers' tendency to dominate the classroom is attributed to the fact that knowledge transmission was the only way teachers knew how to teach. The use of interaction as a tool for teaching and learning, according to the participants' account, was an unfamiliar notion at the time teachers were EFL learners. On this note, Ahmed argued,

We were not familiar with this kind of interaction, this kind of exchange. We had very strict, very

authoritative I would say way of looking at teaching. The teacher is here, the master, le maître as we call it in French, and he's supposed to give everything. they do not object if we ask questions, but we were not supposed to interfere constantly in class, and this kind of exchange. We used to be allowed to ask questions when the teacher finishes his class. We cannot interrupt him. No interruption.

{ Ahmed }

The term ‘*master*’ that was used by the participant to refer to his former teachers is indicative of unequal power relations. According to Ahmed, the master’s way of teaching is severe and authoritative. Asking questions was permitted at the end of the class; however, interaction and constant interruptions were not allowed, which suggests a degree of behavioural control and the teachers’ dominance of the classroom talk. In particular, the participant’s account recalls the view of the teacher in the Islamic pedagogy as powerful and authoritative figure (Miliani, 2017; Miliani, 2012; Choubane, 2019), and broadly recalls the banking model of education (Freire, 1970).

It is important to note that Ahmed and the other teachers did not condemn their former teachers’ way of teaching. Rather, it was viewed as culturally established practices where lecturing was the norm, and simply interaction was not. This was clearly demonstrated in Sami’s account, who argued: *‘Look when we say authority, not in the understanding of never say any word, I am here to say everything. ... and if we say something that contradicts in a way what they said they became unhappy...It means I am here; I have a product to give you. Stop!.’*

Sami’s account suggests that there was an accepted and mutual understanding that the teacher is a knowledge provider, and the learners are the recipients of knowledge. For Sami, authority does not mean that the students are not allowed to talk. Rather students do not talk or interrupt the teacher during the lecturing because they understand that such behaviour might be construed as disrespectful and threatening to the teachers’ authority. In his account, Sami emphasised the notion of respect and

argued that teachers were respected for their authority as teachers, as well as for their competence. Particularly, when the Sami was asked whether his former teachers were the ones who had the total authority in the classroom, Sami responded '*Yes, but with respect, we respected them all...and all of them in a way were competent.*' Sami's account suggests that teacher-student imbalanced power relation is associated with the notion of respect. The participant's account is consistent with the literature because Algerian teachers are assigned a higher status and honour and treated with greater respect compared to western teachers (Miliani, 2012; Choubane, 2019).

It was surprising to find out that the new generation of teachers, such as Asma and Jamila, did not take issue with their former teachers' use of lecturing as a teaching strategy. In their accounts, the participants emphasised the notion of teachers' charismas and argued for its important role in attracting the students' attention.

It depended from one teacher to another. There were some teachers like even when they come with the lecturing style like you enjoy. Sometimes...you find a charismatic teacher, who comes in there with, like, some real knowledge. But what I like more is those who allowed us to, to share our ideas, those who valued our ideas.

{ Asma }

They had, of course, such charisma. Once they started presenting the lesson, you are just you have, you don't have another alternative or choice, but to follow, not because you are obliged, but because they were really impressive.

{ Jamila }

The participants' accounts show conformity to the banking model of education. their accounts also suggests that teachers' self-presentation plays an important role in students' attentiveness in the classroom. Personality traits such as charisma can be captivating to students' attention which could facilitate getting them engaged in the

classroom. The fact that Asma and Jamila were very pleased with the lecturing experiences and had such positive emotion towards lecturing cannot be ignored. Lecturing might indeed take from the learners' opportunities to interact, especially in language classrooms where interaction is the beating heart. At the same time, it is also important to realise that not all lecturing is bad. Lecturing can be considered as the initiation of a dialogic exchange between teacher and student, and not necessarily on monological performance (Fulford and Mahon, 2018). However, the participants' understanding of lecture seems to fall within the view of the lecture as a monological performance.

Participant Asma seems to be aware of the importance of interaction in language classrooms. Although she showed her appreciation to the somewhat sophisticated and mesmerising lecturing styles of some of her former's teachers, she leaned more towards those who allow her to interact and participate in the making of the course.

To sum up, the teachers were enculturated in a system that promotes unequal power relations and the banking model of education. The next section will shed light on the contemporary nature of power relations in the institutions EFL classroom.

6.4 Maintenance of old practices

The unequal power relations and the banking model of education continue to hold their grounds in the institution. Not much has changed since the old days. In fact, if anything the situation became worse. The tone of respect that was present when the teachers reported their former classroom interaction experience has now disappeared. The practice of lecturing and dictation that was once considered the norm now is viewed as a form of '*dictatorship*' and '*authoritarianism*'. Teachers' authoritarian behaviour seems to be prevalent alongside other phenomena that characterise the banking model of education in the institution, such as teachers' reliance on the lecturing and dictation, and rote learning.

6.4.1 Teachers' authoritarian behaviour

To express her views on the unequal power relations in the classroom, Asma used the term '*dictatorship*' to refer to teachers who exert behavioural control on their students in the classroom. In these regards, Asma maintained that,

When the teacher is the centre of everything, there are no questions, the students cannot, for example, if you give them back to their marks, they don't have the right to ask you why. They don't have the right to check their copies, they don't have the right to answer, or if they answer, you tell them that you're wrong, or that's a stupid question or something like that. So, I call this dictatorship in a way.

{ Asma }

Asma's account suggests that students might not be allowed to discuss their marks with the teacher. In the Algerian educational culture, discussing mark with the teacher is a challenge to his/her authority and might be construed as a form of disrespect. This was clearly indicated in Sami's account who drew on his own experiences as an EFL learner. He argued *'We respected them (his former teachers), and we never protest about marks, never. In a way, respect is the key.'* In addition, in the above account, Asma maintained that students might also be discouraged from participating in the classroom due to the teachers' discouraging comments. Similarly, participant Sami also maintained that *'...I think there are some teachers who try to be very authoritarian...there's still some who do not want any student to participate because he or she comes to give back what she or he in a way has prepared and full stop.'* In correspondence with Sami's account, Amal addressed the hierarchical power structure in the classroom and maintained that *'We have an idea of the teacher is above here (high hand gesture) in the classroom, and the students are here (low hand gesture), and they don't ask questions. They just listen, and that's all.'* Not allowing students to participate and to ask questions is indeed an authoritarian act and it is a threat to the promotion of the learners' autonomy which is a key factor in the successful implementation of the LMD reform and in the implementation of the pedagogies of freedom and emancipation (Kumaravadivelu, 2006).

The evidence suggests that teachers discourage not only teacher-student interaction, but also obstruct student-student interaction as shown in the excerpt below, participants S1, S2, and S3 from Focus Group 1 also reported that teachers monopolise the classroom talk, and do not encourage student-student interaction.

Excerpt 5: Focus group one

S1: *Mostly yeah, they don't give us the opportunity to talk and to discuss things between each other he might just answer the questions that's all.*

S2: *with the teacher likes to keep guiding the conversation so they won't allow us to make conversation between us may go far from the topic.*

S3: *Probably with the teacher more than within each other.*

S4: *Because the teachers do not allow us to talk.*

The students provided different reasons as to why their teachers dominate the classroom talk. The first reason is that teachers do not encourage students to interact. Second, teachers do not allow students to interact because they fear that the students might digress from the topic being discussed, which suggests that teacher's endorsement of the deficit model (May, 2011). Teachers not allowing students to talk suggests an authoritarian behaviour.

On the note of teacher not allowing students to talk in the classroom, a student from Focus Group 2 shared the following experience:

There was one time I was talking to my classmate. The teacher thought that was talking about something else. I said I was explaining to her your idea. She said 'no, no, don't do that let her ask me.' This makes the teacher more selfish like a dictator, like 'I am the one who gives information, and your information is rubbish.

{Student 1f2}

The participant's account indicates that some teachers might be threatened when the student assumes the role of the provider of information. Hence, to preserve their level of authority, as the participant's account suggests, '*dictators*' tend to monopolise knowledge. Although the participant's account might be truthful, it might be the case

that the teachers perceived his behaviour as disruptive to the class. Regardless, there seems to be a misunderstanding between the teacher and the student. The misunderstanding is inherent in a shared cultural presumption that when a student is talking to a classmate, he/she must be talking about something that is not related to the lesson. For example, teacher participant Hayam endorses the same belief. Accordingly, Hayam promotes neither pair work nor groupwork as explored in Section 5.2.

Teachers' authoritarian behaviour in Algerian higher education institutions is a common phenomenon (Miliani, 2017; Choubane, 2019). According to Asma, teachers' authoritarian behaviour is established through the element of fear. She maintained that '*here in Algeria, they believe if you are a teacher, your students should be scared of you...this wrong understanding of what is a teacher.*' For the teacher to be fearsome, he or she needs to set up some ground rules. The most important of which is for the teacher to present himself or herself as someone of a higher status than his learners. Soumia argued that '*It (authoritarianism) is very social...there are some teachers who establish a kind of barrier. So, from the beginning, you're the student I am the lecturer. And this has a repercussion. It's very social. I don't want to go into details (annoyed).*' The imbalanced power relations seem to be emphasised since the first encounter between the teacher and learners.

To show his or her superiority, the teacher must appear as severe, tough, and firm as smiling and making jokes might detract from the teacher's prestige and authority and break the power barrier that is important for controlling students' behaviour in the classroom. On this note, and not far from the research participants' circle, Jamila's account echoed the existent shared cultural understanding that there should be a barrier between teachers and students. With complete honesty, the participant admitted that her severe, firm and tough behaviour is inhibiting her students from interacting in the classroom. She maintained that '*If I am going to speak about myself, I seem to be tough, I seem to be strict, and I seem to be firm...this, of course, will not encourage my students to speak or interact, especially at the early start of the year.*' She also added that '*...they are really surprised and shocked...they are almost, if you may say, frustrated because they are going to be taught by this teacher, oh my god, she is too tough, she is so strict, she doesn't smile.*'. Nevertheless, the participant believed that the students' inhibition is temporary, and as soon as her students get

used to her, they will interact: *'...after the first early sessions, of course, they understand that all their interactions are welcome, then they start to interact to ask and of course to express their views.'* The participant's account shows a certain degree of resistance to the correction of her authoritarian behaviour despite her awareness of the negative impact it has on the students' opportunities to interact. In addition, there seems to be a coordination between the participant's severe personality and her teaching method. This is mainly because teachers are more likely to adopt a teaching method that matched their personality (Richards and Lockhart, 1996).

The student participants' account further illustrates teachers' authoritarian behaviour on the institution. Echoing Asma's account, the students' referred to the teachers who tend to dominate the classroom talk as *'dictators'*. On the other hand, teachers who adopt an interactive approach and open to listen to students' views were referred to as democrats. *'There are some teachers who are like dictators, and others who are, I don't know how to say, democratic people.'*, said the participant. The student's account highlights the distinction between Islamic teachers and Western teachers, where the former is viewed as authoritative and all-knowing and the latter as a democratic guide or 'facilitator' for learning (Miliani, 2012; Miliani, 2017; Choubane, 2019). Within the same focus group, another student shared similar views. He maintained that *'Some of them (teachers) are dictators, a little bit not most of them, but others like as my classmate said they really like the answers they already have in mind.'* The participant's account suggests that teachers do not take students' contributions into consideration. Such behaviour might inhibit students' participation in the classroom and minimise their learning opportunities.

In line with Jamila's account above, a student from Focus Group 1 maintained that their teachers are strict, severe, and like robots, as shown in the excerpt below.

Excerpt 6: Focus group one

S1: *Sometimes you feel like they are robots, they are not human, the way they speak with us, they way ask questions.*

S2: *So strict so severe*

S1: *yeah*

R: *So strict so severe. Do you agree with that?*

S3: *I think it is mostly the old generation of teachers.*

S2: *yes.*

An important aspect that surfaced from the participants' account above is that teacher-centred approach is more common amongst teachers of the older generation. The same perspective was also echoed by a student participant from Focus Group 2. He maintained that *'The teachers who give you space are mostly the new ones, younger teachers, but the old teachers they're like dictators, they're like we are the provider of the knowledge.'* There are numerous explanations for the prevalence of teacher-centred approach amongst teachers of the old generation. It is perhaps because of the fact these teachers had extended exposure to the old teaching methods which led them to be deeply rooted in their subconscious (Benadla, 2013). Another possible explanation is that the implementation of western methods might be threatening to their authority as teachers (Miliani, 2017). It could also be because of the inadequacy of the training they received as explored in Chapter 5, Section 5.3.

Another important aspect is S1 reference to his teachers as robots. This suggests that teachers' way of teaching is redundant and pay little attention to the students' wants and needs. Elsewhere, another student within the same focus group echoed his classmate's perspective and referred to his teachers as *'dictating machines'* due to their excessive reliance on the practice of dictation.

In our University, there is a great lack of communication, especially between the teacher and his students. The teacher is like a machine dictating the lesson, and that's it. Most of the times the lesson is dictated from A to Z. They don't make a lot of effort to listen to what the student has to say.

{S1F2}

The participant's account is consistent with the findings of Miliani (2017), who argued that the students' concerns are usually ignored by the teachers. Lack of communication between teachers and students can also be detrimental to the learner's

motivation to learn. In fact, many students from Focus Group 01 and 02 reported that they get bored during the class. For example, students from Focus Group 2 maintained that the way by which the modules are delivered is boring.

Excerpt 7: Focus Group 2

S1: *The lessons are boring.*

R: *Why is it boring? Do you think the lessons you take are boring?*

Ss: *Very*

R: *So, what is boring about the lesson then?*

S3: *The way of the presentation of the lesson*

S4: *and the strategy. They don't use the right strategy teaching strategy.*

One of the main reasons behind the students' boredom in the classroom is the teachers' increased talk time through lecturing and dictation, or spoon-feeding as participants Soumia and Asma preferred to call it. This will be explored in the next section.

6.4.2 Lecturing and dictation

According to Soumia spoon feeding is a very common phenomenon in the institution: *'The majority of teachers adopt spoon-feeding to tell you the truth.'* Elsewhere, Soumia referred to the same phenomenon as *'the classic way of teaching'* where *'the student is here to accept whatever instructions come from the lecturer.'* The participant's account suggests that students lack autonomy, and they are not able to operate without the teacher's instructions. The term spoon-feeding signifies an imbalanced power relation in the classroom where the teacher is a knowledge provider, and students are passive receivers (Benadla; 2013; Raelin, 2009). Asma also expressed her disagreement with the continuance of the usage of the 'spoon-feeding' method: *'a teacher is someone who helps other people learn. It's no longer about spoon-feeding them, spoon-feeding learning. It's no longer applicable. I guess.'* A teacher in Asma's view is a 'facilitator' of learning, not a provider of information. Her views about the nature of teaching and learning correspond with the principles of the LMD reform that promote learners' autonomy and dialogic interaction (Idri,

2012; Djamàa, 2013). Asma's account also shows her inclination toward the use of western teaching methods, perhaps because of her former training experience in the USA (see Table 5.1.1). However, the participant's account is aligned with the principles of IC and PMP which views teachers not only as facilitators of learning but as creators or learning opportunities.

Teachers' reliance on dictation as a teaching strategy is a prevalent practice in the institution, and both teachers and learners problematised its use. For example, participant Amal shared one of her experiences as follow:

The teacher is above all...last time I went to the Amphi (Amphitheatre) for a quiz, and they had to take the Amphi with another teacher who was teaching there, So I was astonished to hear teacher dictating the course. Dictating the dots, the commas, everything word by word, and even the punctuation, and my students were astonished.

{Amal}

Amal's account highlights two main issues. First, teacher use of dictation as a teaching tool. Second, the inconvenience of the shortage in learning space. According to the participant's account, students were being quizzed within the same amphitheatre while another teacher was delivering his/her course. Students' accounts from focus group one was also consistent with Amal's '*Sometimes we study two groups together.*', said a student. Teaching in such circumstances might be challenging for teachers and students and might affect their motivation levels. The lack of space for learning might be related to the phenomenon of massification, and the inappropriate conditions in which the phenomenon was managed in the Algerian HE context (Teferra and Altbachl, 2004; Souleh, 2017; Rose, 2015).

Participant Sami, from his perspective as a teacher of literature, also expressed his disagreement with teachers' reliance on dictation '*...for example, those who dictate for example, how can you dictate literary discussion?*'. For Sami, a literary discussion should not be dictated. It should instead be discussed with the students because, for the participant, a literary text is like a piece of art. Its interpretation is relative and perspectival: '*...Since any piece of art is very relating, it does not give one truth it*

gives so many truths, and so it is for the teacher in a way to motivate students and to let them look beyond words and to give interpretations...' Sami's account is consistent with the principles of IC and PMP as he seems to be in favour of the use of interaction as a tool for teaching and learning, as well as in promoting his learners' autonomy (Walsh, 2012; Kramersch, 1986; Young, 2011; Kumaravadivelu, 2006).

Students from Focus Group 1 and 2 also communicated their rejection to the use of dictation. For example, a student participant from Focus Group 2 shared the following:

...I'm not saying that everyone, every teacher does this (Dictation), but as I said before 70% of them, and mostly it is common with old ones with old teachers. Because all teachers, in my opinion, they have long experience. They just need to tell the lesson and dictated and leave...interaction is very rare in the classroom.

{S1F2}

The participant's account suggests that the older generation of teachers use the transmission model of education because they view themselves as more experienced and knowledgeable than learners. This the reason behind the rarity of the interaction in the classroom as the participant's account suggests.

Other students from the same focus group reported that at least half of the teachers dictate the lesson, as shown in the excerpt below.

Excerpt 8: Focus group 2

R: *Can you please tell me about the problems you have with your teachers and your experiences with them?*

S1: *the lesson...when they give the lesson, they only dictate it. They love dictation, and when you go home and searching on the Internet, you find the whole lesson from A to Z on the Internet from one site maybe even the whole semester lessons from one site.*

S2: *not all of them do that for sure.*

Ss: *Most of them*

S3: *You find some really competent teachers that surprise you, and you really feel like they go through good books to provide the information.*

R: *You said not all of them, are we speaking about minority or majority of teachers?*

S4: *I think half*

R: *The majority of teacher do dictation?*

Ss: *Yes*

Ss: *Yes*

S4: *The ones that do dictation are the good ones, because the other ones that don't do the dictation, there rarely give us time to take notes...so either dictation or nothing.*

S2: *About dictation, I would like to add even if they dictate the whole lesson, usually, there is a lot of explanation involved in the middle of dictation. So, they dictate and explain dictate explain and so on.*

With reference to the excerpt above, students did not only complain about their teachers' reliance on dictation. They also seem to reject the practice of teachers bringing the lessons from the Internet. For the students, a competent teacher is someone who digs into the books and provides the information as pointed out by S3. This demonstrates that students are very dependent on their teachers and lack autonomy. Students' lack of autonomy is not surprising given the prevalence of teacher-centred approach. Also, teachers' dictation of a lesson brought from the Internet is certainly unfair to the students and their learning opportunities. Such practice goes in opposition to the maximisation the learning opportunities principle advocated by both the theory of IC and PMP (Walsh, 2012, Kumaravadivelu, 2006). For the students, it is a sign of incompetence that a teacher obtains the lesson from the Internet. Perhaps because it implies that there was a little effort invested by the teachers in the preparation of the lesson. The use online recourses seem to have an impact on teachers' and learners' power relations in the classroom. This will be explored in detail below.

6.4.3 *The impact of online resources on power relations in the classroom*

Before the internet, books, course materials, and teachers' lectures were the only source of information for students, which might position the teacher in a more central role as a knowledge provider. With the coming of the internet, things changed a great deal. Students nowadays have access to all sort of information at their fingertips, way beyond what a teacher could provide in a single session. Therefore, the availability of online sources might alter power relations in the classroom. Learners might become more responsible for their learning, and the teacher might act only as a facilitator of learning. However, one must realise that the impact of the internet on the nature of power relations in the classroom differs from one culture of another.

Particularly in the context where this study was conducted, data analysis revealed that students use of online sources might have a negative impact on teacher-student relationships. Not only because students might interpret teachers bringing course from the internet as a sign of a low time investment in the course preparation as explored in section 5.1. But also, teachers might be threatened by the students assuming the role of knowledge providers. For example, in his account, participant Sami referred to the internet as the 'enemy of the teacher', and he maintained that,

This Internet is supposed to be the friend of the teacher, but it has become its enemy with some students because you may hear that what I have found is better than what he has given us. They do not know for example that literature is so various and diversified with theories and approaches... (for some students) the teacher is somehow like an encyclopaedia he must give all the different interpretations of the novel.

{Sami}

To provide an accurate interpretation of the above quotation, there is a need to consider other aspects in the participant's account. For example, in his report, the participant over-emphasised the notion of respect, namely students' respect to the teacher *'our nature as Algerian, we respect teachers, mainly in the past, it's not*

similar in a way to today... with the coming of the media and so on, the teacher somehow not as if you want in the past.' Respecting the teacher and placing him at a higher level is deeply rooted in the Algerian Islamic culture (Mililani, 2017; Choubane, 2019). Sami's account suggests that he is very attached to the way teaching used to be in his days, one that he described was based on ultimate respect. According to Sami the internet and social media had an impact of that level of respect and authority.

Therefore, a more likely interpretation of the quotation provided above is that Sami seems to be threatened by students' possession of knowledge. His account clearly illustrates that some students are challenging their teachers by demonstrating that they have better information than theirs. There is a level of resistance from the part of the student, or an attempt to make teacher drink from the same cup. According to Sami, the ongoing discourse between the students that they have more valuable information than their teacher is considered as a distressful act. In retrospect, the participant maintained that his students do not know about the different theories, which suggests that the participant is positioning himself at a knowledge provider. It also indicates that the participant is in favour of the deficit model.

Therefore, the internet became the teachers' enemy because it has empowered students. At the same time, the participant's account also indicates that some students are very dependent on their teachers. Therefore, because of students' lack of autonomy, the availability of online sources seems to put more pressures on teachers as they need to meet the expectation of some, if not many of the students, who are utterly dependent on the knowledge provided by their lecturers. Due to the hierarchal power structure in the classroom, the use of online resources seems only to aggravate the tension in the teacher-student relationship, which might impede the quality of teacher-student interaction in the classroom. In these regards, Alshahrani et al. (2017) maintained that the use of the internet might harm teacher-student relationships and classroom power relations in societies of hierarchical structure.

Moreover, the availability of online sources also seems to have a negative impact on students' level of attendance. According to Sami's account, some students *'go directly to the Internet, and some of them do not come, do not attend the course.'* Absenteeism

has a negative impact on students' engagement which is pivotal in the development of their IC (Walsh; 2012; 2013).

Furthermore, the students' excessive use of social media platforms is another indication of the extent to which the internet seems to influence the quality of interaction between teachers and learners in the classroom. According to participant Hayam's account, many students do not revise their lesson because of the overuse of the Facebook app. *'They spend hours and nights into Facebook, and they don't revise. I am against such a way because they don't care about their studies.'* Excessive use of social media platforms might impact student engagement in the classroom. For example, if students did not do their reading assignments, the level of interaction and participation will be affected.

Now, attention will give to another characteristic on the transmission model of education in the institution which is the prevalent practice of rote learning.

6.4.4 Rote learning

Another prevalent phenomenon in the institution that echoes the banking model of education is rote learning. According to Amal rote learning is tightly associated with the practice of dictation, and broadly with the spoon-feeding approach (McKay and Kember, 1997). She maintained that *'When you see a teacher dictating the course, it's because the teacher wants the student to learn by heart.'* In line with Amal's account students from Focus Group 1 reported that the teacher put a greater emphasis on rote learning. *'It all depends on memorisation'* said a student. Similarly, another student maintained that *'Most of them (teachers) they don't give us like debatable questions, they just care about memorisation. They see if you memorised, they give you the mark.'* The practice of rote learning is a relic of the Islamic pedagogy which was revived upon the introduction the Arabisation project where many Koranic schools were built to promote the learning and the use of Arabic (Miliani, 2013; Miliani, 2017; Choubane, 2019). Amal's account addressed the correlation between the religion of Islam and the rote memorisation practice.

*We still have the view of the master above all (Ar) Kif El
Jamaa [just like in the koranic school], do you ask*

questions in the mosque? (Ar) Kima ta3 El Jamaa. Trouh ta9ra fi El Jamaa [Just like in the Koranic school. When you study at the koranic school], you don't ask questions, you are here you learn by heart. Learning by heart is the biggest threat to education in Algeria, rote learning...and it is still done here when you see a teacher dictating the course because the teacher wants the student to learn by heart the text.

{Amal}

Amal's account indicates that the power relations in the classroom are uneven. She compared teachers' dominance of the classroom talk to the way teaching is undertaken in Koranic schools, where the 'Cheikh' is the only provider of information or knowledge, and interruption is not allowed. Just like the 'Cheikh' in the Koranic school, teachers are the ones who do most of the talk while the students are passive. They are only required to listen to memorise the information by heart (Miliani, 2013; Miliani, 2017; Choubane, 2019).

Whether rote learning is the biggest threat to Algerian education or not is a question for debate. However, rote learning or memorisation is a serious issue in the Algerian context of education as it intervenes with learners' opportunities for learning, and motivation, as well as it constitutes a threat to the development of students' creativity critical thinking abilities, and problem-solving. In these regards, teacher participant Hayam pointed out, *'The crucial lack that I complain from is that they don't synthesise, is that they don't make a relation. they go chapter by chapter, if the chapter finishes, they don't relate it to the ensuing chapter.'* The students were also aware of the negative impact of rote learning on their critical thinking. One of the students from Focus Group 1 maintained that *'I think they don't really train us to be critical and to analyse critically, and then they come to us on master two or whatever, and they ask us to prepare something critically and analytically like how we are going to do that?'* The student posed a very legitimate question. How is it possible for students to demonstrate a high level of thinking when they are constantly fed information, forced to rote learn, and discouraged from producing knowledge?

Another student shared that teachers' emphasis on rote learning forced him to become careless *'This method of memorisation, I feel myself like a computer... I became as if I don't mind...'* Carelessness, in this sense, can be viewed as a form of resistance against teachers' adoption of practices that threaten students' critical thinking ability. The use of the term *'computer'* by the student in relation to his sense of self indicates that he is no longer able to think for himself. His academic needs and interests are being marginalised. Some students express their resistance through silence and passivity. For example, a student from Focus Group 2 maintained that *'Sometimes, I prefer to remain silent'* as a reaction to the teachers' lack of flexibility and academic intolerance, that is, not accepting any answers other than the ones they have in mind.

Teachers' emphasis on rote learning seems to have a notable impact on teacher-student relationships, as shown in the excerpt below.

Excerpt 9: Focus group 1

S1: *The exact words word by word*

S2: *You need to say exactly what they gave you, it's wrong.*

R: *What do they give you, handouts?*

S3: *No Dictation*

Ss: *Dictation*

S4: *For example, the teacher of xxxx, she wants quantity than quality. If you write a small paragraph which is a good content, she doesn't accept it. She wants big text, even if the content in the big one is uh*

S5: *it is useless*

S4: *It is useless.*

S6: *If right small but correct, she says no she proves you're wrong... Some of the answers on the first exams were correct, but you didn't give us the right point.*

S7: *if we argue they tell us you didn't give more detail.*

S8: *As for me it happened with me with xxxx, like she gave us hundreds and hundreds of handout and then she told us to resay everything in the exact words And I couldn't really I couldn't*

memorise all of that I just said it the way I understood it, and she gave me 9...I just said that you're not being fair and this is nonsense, so she kicked me out and then I went out...

S9: *This is our interaction with teachers*

Ss: *Yes's*

The students' accounts indicate that teachers are more into rote learning than into promoting students' creativity and critical thinking. The students' accounts also indicate that there is some tension in their relationships with their teachers, primarily because of marks. Students who do not like to memorise the lesson by heart, and instead answer according to their understanding, might need to dispute their marks. This latter might lead to tension in teacher-student relationship such as in the case of S8. It might also force students to resort to unethical practices such as cheating as also surfaced in S8 account above. Cheating is also another form of indirect resistance to a particular institutional practice; in this case, rote learning (Foucault, 1978).

The prevalence of old practices consequently led to the limitation of the practice of interaction in the institution's EFL classroom. Teachers' and learners' interview analysis revealed various factors that affected the performative element of the IC. Time constraints were regarded by the participants as a fundamental impediment to the quantity and quality of the interaction. The next section will explore the main factors behind time constraints.

6.5 Time constraints

Time constraint is one main factor that impedes the proper implementation of the LMD system, particularly the use of dialogic interaction as a tool for teaching and learning. All the participants, teachers and learners, reported that time limitation is a key factor behind students' limited opportunities in the classroom. The data analysis revealed three main factors behind time constraints, and the limited opportunities for students to interact, as shown in figure 5.8.1 below.

Figure 6.5: Main factors behind time constraints.

The first reason behind time constraints is teachers' dominance of the classroom talk through lecturing, explanation, and dictation, and this was explored thoroughly in Section 6.4.2. The second is the overloaded syllabus. The third factor is the large class size in the institution. The last two factors will be discussed thoroughly in the next Section.

6.5.1 *The overloaded syllabus*

From the analysis of the interviews of both teachers and learners, it became clear that there is a serious issue regarding the syllabus, and it is affecting the quality of teaching and learning, and most importantly, students' opportunities to interact. It transpired that teachers are using the same syllabus used in the old system. Teachers are now working against the clock to finish a syllabus that used to take four years in the old system in only three years: *'the syllabus, we are always in a hurry to finish them on time...they have said we have now adopted instead a BA of four years into three years, but it is just a matter of squeezing the syllabus.'* Said Hayam. The issue of squeezing the syllabus was also raised by many participants, both teachers and students. For example, a student from Focus Group 1 maintained that,

In the previous system which is the classical system, they had so many time the teacher told us that we

studied African literature in a year, any year for American literature, in a year for British literature, but in this year we studied them all of them in a single year. There's no time for interaction. I don't know.

{S3F2}

The above account also resonates with the understanding of the teacher participant Jamila

We are no longer having two separate modules in civilisation. We have them both in one module, which is going to be labelled culture and civilisation of the language, the first semester is going to be devoted to the British civilisation, the second one is going to be devoted to American civilisation. So, you see, you are going to teach a module in just one semester and of course, one session a week.

{Jamila}

Due to syllabus overload, teachers become primarily focused on its completion on time, disregarding in the process the dialogic interactive dimension of the classroom life. In this respect, Jamila maintained argued that *'Teachers sometimes are not willing to give space to students to speak. All that they think about is to finish is to cover the lessons, and that's all. whether the students have understood or not, it is not really that important.'* Soumia also had a similar take on the issue of the overload syllabus and its impact on the learners' interaction opportunities: *'they're pushed to finish the program and all that. So, I don't think they are very much interested in this notion of interaction.'* The participants' account suggests that students communicative and interactive skill are being marginalised in a bid to finish the syllabus on time (Benadla, 2013). The participants' accounts indicate that there is a strong correlation between the overloaded syllabus and the time constraints. Teachers are not inclined towards the use of interaction in their classrooms because of time limitation.

Students' accounts from both focus groups also highlighted the issue of time constraints. A student from Focus Group 1 echoed Jamila and Soumia's accounts and maintained that *'teachers are pressed with time. They have a lesson they need to give us the lesson and go we don't really have this time to give us to talk and discuss. One hour and a half and they are pressed.'* Another student extended on his college contribution and maintained that *'time-wise I think it's a tiny bit overloaded, but they're like take off this module take off this lesson. They don't add; they just take off stuff. It affects the confidence of students and their learning.'* Removing modules and lessons for the program to be completed on time implies that the syllabus is overloaded. The student argued that syllabus overloaded affect students' learning and confidence. An overloaded syllabus teacher might reinforce teachers' reliance on old teaching methods, that is, knowledge transmission, to finish the program which would minis the students' interaction opportunities with the language and therefore their confidence to use the target language.

Likewise, a student participant from Focus Group 2 made a similar reflection, however, the participant attributed time limitation to the LMD reforms *'the system of LMD we have now, I'm not going to criticise or anything I'm just giving an observation, this system is very limited in time, and there are a lot of lessons to be explained, and there is no time for interaction.'* The participant's account raised the issue of the overloaded syllabus. According to him, the issue of time constraints was non-existent in the old system, and it only emerged with the coming of the LMD, and this is due to the teachers' maintenance of old system syllabus as maintained earlier. The student account also claimed that the LMD system is limited in time. His account is like Jamila's account who argued that,

Frankly speaking, I don't think that it (LMD) fits our educational system. With the traditional one, of course, we just to devote more time and an extra year, four each level. Okay, so we used to have enough time to teach, we used to have enough time to interact, we used to have enough time to evaluate and assess. But with this new system, of course, with the LMD, we don't really have enough time.

She also added that,

How could you cover the syllabus that, of course, was covered in four years, are going to cover it in three years with no change? It is unbelievable. I don't think that the LMD system is fitting our educational system at all.

{ Jamila }

The expression is '*I don't think that the LMD system is fitting our educational system*' suggests that the participant is still attached to the old system, and resistive to the LMD reforms. In her account, Jamila seems to be aware that the overloaded syllabus caused the issue of time constraints. Regardless, she insisted on the fact the LMD reforms is unsuitable for the '*Algerian educational system*'. The fact that the participant is aware of what is causing time constraints and still attributing the issue to the unsuitability of the LMD reforms is unreasonable. Her account also indicates that she is not aware of her responsibilities as a teacher within the LMD reforms, and the fact that devising a syllabus is one of her duties. In this respect, Ahmed maintains that '*teachers nowadays are still they have got this kind of resistive nature to change...they have this kind of resistance to the technical novelties brought by this kind of LMD reform like devising a syllabus.*' Within the LMD system reform, teachers are obligated to design a syllabus that is needed to be agreed upon by the students and the university administration (Idri, 2012).

Teachers' resistance to devising syllabus is primarily attributed to their lack of autonomy, which is not surprising factor considering the fact they were encultured within a system of education that suppresses autonomy and promotes overreliance on teachers (see Section 6.3). Their lack of autonomy is also due to the inadequacy of training and lack of administrative support. Accordingly, many teachers spoke of the issue of the overloaded syllabus as if it is out of their control. There is a shared belief that the syllabus should come from the ministry of higher education located in Algiers. For example, Hayam maintained that '*the syllabus is also very overloaded. Again, we have to make meetings, and this comes from the ministry because the ministry obliges us to follow such syllabus. and what we have to do is only to apply.*'

The participant's account echoes the notion centralisation of power at the level of ministry of higher education and limited autonomy of the institution (Souleh, 2017; Bouzid et. 2013). At the same time, the participant's account also suggests a lack of teacher autonomy and over-dependency on the ministry to resolve a local issue related to certain institutional practices, syllabus design in the present case.

Teachers' lack of autonomy might be further exemplified through drawing on Amal's account. In her account, the participant complained about lack of specificities in the syllabus as follows: *'there are only general guidelines...it is not really specific, and you do what you want.'* Perhaps, what the participant is referring in her account is the curriculum, not the syllabus. Amal viewed the lack of specificity in the syllabus as a negative aspect, which should be a positive one since it provides teachers with the freedom to teach what goes hand in hand with the students' needs. Amal also maintained that *'if it is a specific program it was done by young teaching here in xxx, it is not from Algiers.'* The participant's account highlights two issues. First, her lack of autonomy, and over-dependency on a higher power for the resolution of the syllabus issue. The latter further reinforces the hierarchical nature of the power structure in the institution (Miliani, 2017). The participant's account also suggests her underlined rejection to a syllabus that did not come from the ministry of higher education. Participants Hayam and Amal accounts are not consistent with the literature, as PMP expects teachers to be autonomous (Kumaravadivelu, 2006) which is crucial for the development of students' autonomy and the operationalisation of IC (Campbell-Larsen, 2014; Walsh, 2012).

Another contributing factor to syllabus overloaded is repetitive content of the lessons. A student Focus group 1 reported the following *'For example, we have didactics, and we have ESP, though we can find ESP in didactics. So, ESP can be just a lesson in didactics.'* The participant's account echoes Idri's (2012) findings which address students' dissatisfaction about the content of the syllabus and its repetitiveness. As the participants' account suggests, the repetitiveness of the lesson content might be attributed to the lack of collaboration between teachers. This was clearly articulated in by Soumia during the interview *'...lecturers would come, and they don't have any syllabus. Few teachers teach in the same level. Every teacher is cooking in his own kitchen.'* According to Souma, some teachers do not have a syllabus when they come to the class, and this seems to affect students' engagement in the classroom. For

example, a student from Focus Group 1 reported that they could not interact in the classroom because the teachers do not provide them with the syllabus *'they should provide us with the syllabus at least so we can prepare and do some research.'*

In addition to the syllabus issue, the analysis of teachers' and learners' interviews also revealed that class size is one of the main factors behind time constraints and student limited opportunities for interaction.

6.5.2 Large class size

One of the main obstacles that threaten the quality of interaction in the institution's EFL classes is large class size. The problem of large classes is an evitable and natural consequence of the phenomenon of massification (Bouزيد, 2013; Mohamedbhai, 2014). According to the teachers' and students' accounts, the number of students per classes ranges from 25 to 40 students. In these regards, participant Amina maintained that,

One of the problems here in our university is the size of the class. The number of students is usually more than 30. I think the least one, maybe 25 students per class. For instance, for a session of one hour and a half or two hours is not sufficient to interact with all the students to make all the students speak.

{Amina}

On a related noted, Sami also maintained that,

'the main challenge is the number of students. Around 40 in one group, so it's too much. It's very difficult for me.'

{Sami}

From Amina's account, it can be seen that the large class size interferes with the time factor. The time, as it were, is not sufficient for all students to interact. The issue of large classes with the problem of the overloaded syllabus discussed above further

diminishes students' opportunities. It is also important not to forget teachers' domination of the classroom talk with lecturing and dictation. For example, participant Soumia reported that she leaves only 15 minutes at the end of the session for students' interaction. The rest of the session is allocated for lecturing as shown in the following transcript *'I schedule myself when I say, well I'm going to give the lecture and leave something like 15 minutes before the end of the lecture so that we can interact. and sometimes I am pressed by time, and I don't have this time.'* Students' development of IC requires the promotion of students' active engagement in the classroom. From the perspective of IC competence, maximising learning opportunities entails maximising students' opportunities for interaction (Walsh, 2012; Walsh; 2013). In these regards, participant Soumia posited a legitimate concern.

How can you succeed in interaction competence with a huge number? It's not possible. It's out of the question. We used to be something like 15 students in the class in the whole promotion is very good. This is great; I mean this is ideal. But nowadays now. I used to have groups of 35, which is impossible.

{Soumia}

Echoing her colleagues' perspective, participant Jamila also reported that,

It is more than impossible to make and to motivate and to push and to enhance the interaction for each individual student.

{Jamila}

According to Soumia's and Jamila's account, the problem of large classes constitutes an obstacle to the operationalisation of IC. For them, it is impossible to have a successful interaction with many students per class. It is well established in the literature that large classes posit many challenges to the teacher and learners (Mulryan-Kyne 2010; Exeter et al. 2010; Hornsby and Osman, 2014). Chances of interaction within large classes are more likely to be diminished (Mulryan-Kyne, 2010; Exeter et al. 2010). Particularly, students who need interaction to be motivated

in the classes are more likely to be disappointed and less motivated (Mulryan-Kyne 2010; Exeter et al. 2010). Large classes make it difficult for a teacher to know about the students' needs (Hornsby and Osman, 2014). In this regard, Soumia maintained that,

The number of students is a primordial criterion for the success of this interaction. So, that you can give a chance to everybody, everyone individually to speak and to interact, and find out about the competences as well, what are the deficiencies he might be, or she might be in need of something you know boosted.

{Soumia}

In addition, the issue of large classes in the institution impedes the implementation of key pedagogical canons of the LMD system, particularly, the promotion of students' autonomy. For example, within the LMD philosophy, there is a pedagogical practice called 'tutoring' (Idri, 2012). Tutoring involves teachers' supervision of 1 to 8 students during the first year of Bachelor degree. During the tutoring session, the teacher should offer support to students in their study and assist them in any difficulties they may encounter throughout the year. According to the participants' accounts, however, the tutoring system is not being applied in the institution due to large classes and shortage in teaching staff. In these regards, participant Soumia maintained that,

On top of what we call here with the LMD system. (Fr) 'Le tutora' [tutoring]... First-year students, how can you allocate 400 students for advisors and the lecturers are not that numerous. That means that every lecturer should have something like ten students if no more. So that we haven't applied it. I mean, we are still thinking how to do it. But we haven't managed to do it.

{Soumia}

Teacher participant Laila also provided a similar account,

This self-learning which is a key in the LMD system is very difficult to achieve. The principle is that a lot of time should be allocated to self-learning, which is not the case. And tutor would have two students who would be in charge of because it is not possible if you just look at the ratio of teachers and learners.

{Laila}

The tutoring system is in place to ensure that the students are well supported during their first year at the university and to assist them during their path towards autonomy (Idri, 2012). The lack of application of tutoring might delay students taking responsibly of their learning. It is more likely for students to lose motivation, and to struggle if there are not properly supported during their first year at the university. The absence of tutoring is more likely to make the transition into a system that requires them to be autonomous a challenging task for many students (Idri, 2012).

The promotion of students' autonomy is also hampered by students' passivity. The issue of students' passive behaviour is inherent in the inadequate parenting styles and a system of education that nurture learners across all stages of education. This will be explored in more details in the next section.

6.6 Roots of passivity and maintenance of power imbalance

According to the teachers' accounts, students' passive behaviour in the classroom is rooted in the authoritarian parenting style inherent, in some, if not many, of the Algerian families (Benadla, 2013; Semmouk, 2005). This passivity is further nurtured in the primary, middle and secondary school where the teacher assumes the same authoritarian role.

Amina's account addressed the role of society and the education system in nurturing students' passive behaviour. She maintained that '*...the problem starts from primary school secondary and middle school. Usually, students are not given enough time to speak freely and confidently. Especially self-confidence, one of the problems with our*

students is that they are not self-confident.' The participant's account suggests that the education system conditions students to be passive (Choubane, 2019). The participant further argued student's passive behaviour is rooted in the Algerian society and parenting style,

Within the family itself, society and family environment as well. For instance, there are some parents; for instance, they make obstacles; they impede their children from speaking freely about some topics you know. There are some traditions, and we have some bad traditions in our families. We don't give our children the opportunity to speak freely.

{Amina}

A similar perspective was given by the participant Jamila who maintained that,

Why students are not willing to interact or why the teacher is going to think that is the centre of this process of teaching...it is something which is rooted back, Of course, even in the family, for instance, where the parents are the ones who are going to speak, who are going to decide, who are the ones who are going to control, to dominate. In a way, they are the authority for us. So here the child...he is the one who is going to accept everything...I am speaking about the vast majority of students and pupils how they do think. So, once joining the primary school, they think that's what their job is, in fact, is to listen, to obey.

{Jamila}

From Amina's and Jamila's account, it can be deduced that there are certain social expectations which reinforce the maintenance of the unequal power relations in the classroom. The participant's account highlights the notable impact the macro culture of society and family had on the micro-culture of the classroom. Therefore, the shared

cultural belief of respect and authority which are deeply rooted in the Algerian community seems to be transmitted from one institution for example family to another institution, for example, the classroom (Fullinwider and MacLean, 1996; Wren, 2012). Hence, the classroom operates in relation to beliefs that are shared and define the Algerian community (Nguyen, 2013).

Participant Jamila elaborated on her account and argued that is difficult for students to change their passive behaviour at the university level.

The day when you are going to talk to college, of course, it is not going to have that great change. You are going to play that passive role...you have already such idea in mind that between brackets He is Mr or Mrs all-knowing. He has the knowledge; he has the power. So, and here the students are going to listen, you are going to obey.

{ Jamila }

Throughout their educational career, the students had not been given the opportunities to be autonomous. As participant Soumia argued, echoing Amina's and Jamila's accounts *'From the primary school till college, and then secondary school, the teacher does everything. the student is here, or the pupil is here to take notes, copy down things from the blackboard, and that's it.'* All of a sudden, the students find themselves in a system that expects them to be autonomous and to think critically.

The analysis of the teachers' interviews also revealed that power relations in the Algerian families also seem to be influenced by EFL classrooms. In these regards, Sami shared the following,

The authority of parents is due to disappear. Because they fear, in a way, their parents. Because they are learning something strange, Foreignizing, it means we are foreignizing the Algerians, this is the way they think...to make the student forget about his cultural background and adopt a new one. Because any language

links with its own culture, and so, you become more English than an Algerian. It happened to me that a student of mine, they (parents) said we sent you to learn English not to be another one. Because they learned raising questions, she said to me a quote 'we sent you to learn not to become another one.'

{Sami}

Sami believes that the English language is foreignizing the Algerian culture. He maintained that when students learn English, they might endorse certain western behaviour such the freedom to express ones' self and questioning which might be threatening to the parent's authority. In addition, such behaviour might also be construed as impolite and disrespectful by the parents. Sami's idea of foreignizing the Algerian culture through the English language recalls the notion of linguistic imperialism where English is used as tool dominate foreign countries culture, politics, and economy (Phillipson, 2008).

The findings also revealed that the workforce and decision-makers also maintain the unequal power distribution in the classroom and in the institution. As noted in the participant's profile, Soumia had her PhD degree from the UK. Throughout her comparison between the two societies, that is, the UK and Algeria Soumia discovered that there are cultural differences in terms of teacher-student relationships. Soumia maintained the following,

I have been a student in the UK, and I tend to compare the two societies. In the UK, for instance, if I can give you an example, there are no barriers between the supervisor and the supervisee, the lecturer and the student. In Algeria, the culture is completely different. We tend to have a barrier. So, that's why the interaction in the UK between the student and the teacher or the lecturer, is very fluid. It's very spontaneous.'

{Soumia}

The participant's account suggests that the cultural context values the unequal power dynamics between teacher-students. According to the participant's account, this barrier of inequality is what affects the fluidity and the spontaneity of the interaction. In an attempt to eliminate the 'power barrier', upon her return from the UK, Soumia decided to interact with the students informally in a bid to strengthen their interpersonal relationships and develop their oral fluency. Her attempt failed as a 'decision-maker' prohibited her from engaging in such practice and urged her to establish some ground rules between her and the students. In these regards, she maintained that,

When I first came from the UK, I was very spontaneous with my students. My idea was in one hour and a half in the classroom or in the laboratory; you cannot develop this oral expression competence. So, I used to go out with them in the yard of the university, have some coffee, have some tea. Interact in English just to develop their oral expression, and some decision-makers told me off. They said well you don't have to that because you are not in the UK. Here you have to establish some kind of room barrier between you and the student...So I just stopped doing that.

{Soumia}

Likewise, participant Asma also went through a relatively similar experience. During her one-year teacher training in the USA, a native speaker teacher introduced Asma and her fellow Algerian trainees to her fellow colleges as 'friends'.

I was once with a professor. She had like a lot of degrees. She took us out, and she was walking with us. We were walking together talking using English... and then she met a friend of hers. I thought she's gonna say oh! These are a bunch of Algerians, like

savages coming from the other part of the world visiting, but she said these are my friends... You see?

{ Asma }

This experience had a great impact on Asma which made her decide to use the same strategy with her students, i.e. to consider her students as her friends: *'That word she said touched me a lot. And I decided that when I come back, I am going to treat my students in a way in which they feel they are respected, that they are important and that they matter. They do matter in every possible respect.'* Asma's way of dealing with her student, such as being close to them and befriending them was faced with a degree of resistance from her colleagues.

A lot of people disagree with me. They say you are too nice to them. You give them like more liberty. For example, if the students' come and say good morning, and kinda like I keep talking to them outside, and sometimes like the girls they kiss me. They kinds like say 'it shouldn't be that way' and I say why? I know a couple of teachers who are applying the same thing like me. Sadly, it is not the case for everyone.

{ Asma }

Asma and Soumia's accounts demonstrates that the introduction of western pedagogy represents a threat to the existing cultural belief that encourages imbalanced power relations between teachers and learners. The accounts further show that the members of the workforces maintain the unequal power dynamics, be it work colleagues or decision-makers. This means that individuals in the institution are vehicles of power, and power as it were 'is transmitted by them and through them' as Foucault (1984) maintained.

The inadequate parenting styles and teachers' authoritarian behaviour in the classroom across the different level seem to have had a notable impact of the students' classroom engagement. In their accounts, both teachers and learners referred to other complex and interrelated factors that are contributing to students' passive behaviours.

❖ *Psycho-affective factors*

The participants listed psycho-affective factors such as low self-confidence and shyness as one of the main contributors to students' passive behaviour in the classroom. For example, participant Talib reported that: *'Many students, lack confidence in their linguistic capacities. Even though they know things, they hesitate to express them...very few dare to use the language. Linguistic limitations. It's not a limitation. It's a psychological factor.'* One explanation of student inhibition was provided in Jamila's account. Participant Jamila maintained the teacher's severity is inhibiting students from expressing themselves: *'...students sometimes have such feeling of being afraid of expressing themselves because you are the teacher...'* Students are afraid of expressing themselves in front of the teacher. They are afraid of making mistakes' *first the students, don't want to, don't dare to speak to the lecturer because they're scared that they are going to make mistakes or errors or something like that.* **{Soumia}**. On the same note, participant Laila maintained that *'they dare not speak because they're afraid of pronunciation, making mistakes, and the others would laugh at them, that's the main issue I think, and this interaction process it is in speaking.'* The participants' account reveals that students do not participate because their classmate might ridicule them if they make a mistake. Hence, the classroom atmosphere might not be encouraging for students to practice their speaking skills.

❖ *It is all about the grades*

Another factor behind student passive behaviour that surfaced from the teachers' and students' account is that the students are not motivated to learn. They are primarily interested in grades. In these regards, a student participant from focus group two reported that *'many students are not comfortable to interact because they do not revise their lesson... that's a key point that we see a lot, and very rare people admit it.'* The students account suggested student's demotivation and carelessness. One explanation that surfaced from the students' accounts that might explain why students are demotivated is the fact that the majority of students seek marks and not competence: *'The most and the biggest important motivation in our university is the mark given by the teacher. If the teacher says if anyone gives a good answer, I will add two points in the exam, everyone talks, everyone interacts...'*

In accordance with the students' participant accounts, some teacher participants, including Jamila, Asma, and Sami, reported that they use marks to motivate students. For example, participant Jamila *'I do not have another solution, but just to oblige them to interact a bit. So of course, you are going to have additional grades, you are going, this will influence your grades. I always, I devote some grades for this interaction and participation on purpose to encourage them all to speak.'* Similarly, Asma pointed out *'sometimes, we need to force them, like you give them the role play, and you say, if you're not going to do this one, you're not going to get the mark.'* 'obliging' or 'forcing' students' engagement further echoes the severity of students' passive behaviour in the classroom. As it were, marks are used as tools to force students to get out of their bubble and interact. Even with the use of extra marks, the level participant is still unsatisfactory: *'...I have to encourage them. I am already doing this by giving them extra grades and so on and so forth. But still, it is not really enough.'* Teachers' use of marks as a motivator also reinforces the students' habit to prioritise marks rather than learning.

❖ *Students' low level*

For some teacher participants students referred to the low level of the students. Participant Soumia for example, pointed out *'sometimes the interaction it's not that fluid, and it's not very easy. just because there is a language handicap from the part of the learners.'* In another excerpt, the participant also maintained that *'...another feature or another criterion it stopped me from applying this is the level of students, time. and sometimes students didn't understand what I was talking about.'* Soumia's account is consistent with some of the students' account. For instance, students from focus group one criticised the way teachers ask questions. As one student described it as 'complicated', another maintained that *'as if they are speaking Chinese.'* Similarly, participant Hayam rejected the possibility that some students might be shy and insisted that student have a language problem *'I mean they are forced to behave in such a way. Because maybe they don't have even the language. It's not shyness. It's the language itself.'* The students' low level might be related to teachers' demoralisation and underperformance (see Section, 6.7). It might also be attributed to teacher reliance on old teaching methods, which leaves the students with minimal learning opportunities.

❖ *Studying English was not the dream*

Another reason for student's passive behaviour is that for many students, studying English was not their own choice. Particularly, students who joined the English language department just to secure a position at the university because their baccalaureate average did not allow them to get admitted to the speciality they want. In this respect, participant Soumia reported that,

I tend to mention something else, as well. At the graduate level, why these features (IC) are not developed. For the simple reason that some students came to choose English as a specialisation just by chance because they didn't know where to go, or they didn't have any other opportunity to register for another...most of them they come from science and technology, and from scientific streams as well, and that's why they didn't have the chance to do medicine or pharmacy or something like that. So, they come to do English. Because they have to have a place at the university. So, what do you expect? You don't expect much.

{Soumia}

A similar account was also provided by participant Hayam who pointed out,

Another crucial impediment is most of the student are from the scientific streams. So, their interest was not really to be in the English department. Their dream was to be doctors, pharmacist and in architecture, but because of their average, they will not be allowed to register in medicine department, pharmacy and so on...

{Hayam}

Soumia's and Hayam's account indicate that student gets admitted into a particular course in the university depending on their grades in the baccalaureate's exam. Students who do well, they usually end up studying the course they prefer. However, those who did not do so well, they find themselves doing a course they do not like. The latter has a profound impact on their motivation level on their self-esteem (Mahdjoub and Miliani, 2017). Not only because they are doing something they do not want, but also the fact that they failed to get access to prestigious disciplines. Social sciences and humanities are usually placed in secondary position compared to other disciplines science and technologies. Therefore, the latter disciplines are assigned higher grades, which makes them more desirable to students.

The implication of this dysfunctional admission system has a severe impact on the level of participation in English language classrooms. Students from the scientific stream usually do not have a good command of English to interact. For the simple reason is that science students need to focus on these modules such as mathematic, natural science and physics, which are assigned a higher coefficient. On the other hand, English in the scientific streams is assigned a low coefficient. The fact that students are not sufficiently equipped might also lead students to demonstrate signs of speaking anxiety, fear, and lack of confidence when invited to participate.

In conclusion, there are various intersecting factors that might be contributing and reinforcing students' passivity in the classroom. Teacher demoralisation and underperformance is also another contributing factor to students' passive behaviour.

6.7 Demoralised and underperforming teachers

Teachers' underperformance is another factor that seems to influence the quality of EFL teaching and learning in the institution. According to the teachers' and students' accounts, teachers' underperformance can be viewed in several areas. Some teachers do not commit to the full time allocated for the session, which is according to teachers and students account is 90 minutes. The participant Hayam's account also highlighted a similar issue,

Some teachers, say, do not make their session of one hour and a half. The session is programmed into one hour and a half. Some teachers just get for 10 minutes

15 minutes. They deliver the handouts, and the students they study alone. Not all the teachers are making an effort to explain.

{ Hayam }

A similar issue was also raised by the students from Focus Group 2. One of the students maintained that *'It is usually less than 90 minutes...it is always like minus 5 minutes, minus 10 minutes with most teachers.'* Not adhering to the time allocated for the session is also a contributing factor to the issue of the time constraints addressed earlier (see Section 6.5). According to Hayam's account, teachers only provide the student with the handouts and do not teach. This indicates that some teachers lack professional ethics and integrity, and the sense of responsibility toward their learners and their duties as teachers.

According to Hayam, teachers underperform in the sense that they do not update the content of their lessons: *'What is new is that the delegate takes the handouts to the shop, and the handouts are sold in the shop. So, can you conceive that the handouts are sold in the shop?'* Due to the lack of innovation from the part of the teachers, the handouts are sold in shops. In addition, Hayam also pointed out teachers do not innovate in exam question: *'Sometimes we have got the repeated questions, so the students from one year to another, they take the same question, they focus on the answer, and they come prepared because teachers do not innovate in the way of making their questions.'* Knowing the exams questions before the exams might encourage the students to resort to rote learning, or even to cheating. It is therefore unsurprising that some teachers complained about their students' level and their lack of critical thinking.

Apparently, handouts are not the only thing sold in shops. According to Amal, the shop next to the institution also sells ready-made research projects. The participant provided the following account via email after the interview schedule: *'I'm really concerned about is the overall use of plagiarism in memoirs and theses. As the only. Students have got used to bringing and buying research works from (Fr) cybercafés (Tr) [Internet café] before university, they continue "borrowing" others' works without citing them.'* It seems that even businesses are also another contributing

factor to students' passive behaviour and lack of critical thinking. The participant pointed out that students also engage in plagiarism which might have reputation research quality in the institution. Students tendency to plagiarise can be explained in the light of their mere interest in grades and not in learning as explored in section 6.6. Plagiarism can be viewed as a form of resistance to teachers' underperformance which might have resulted in student not having adequate research skills.

Teachers' underperformance can be attributed to a number of factors. For the most part, teachers are demoralised because of the inadequate working condition, lack of administrative support, and low pay. Low pay is a common issue in the Algerian HE sector (Farah, 2010; Alexander et al., 2016). According to Hayam's account, the salaries teachers receive do not reflect the effort they make in the classroom: *'...teachers are seldom conscious because they try to not make so much effort vis-a-vis the low salary they get.'*

According to Amal, teachers underperform because they have disagreements with the university administration. The relationship between teachers and the administration seems based on authority, that is, a top-down relationship (Idri, 2012). The administration of the university gives little attention to the teachers' voices.

I think because of the problem of the administration; they are all trying to give a bit, not everything. (Ar) Makserch rasek, mid w rouh, wa3leh tougtel rohek fil khidma, (En) and most them are always absent... (Fr) par ce que (Ar) edinya makla ba3daha (Fr) il sont foux wahed myhawess 3la loukher.

{Amal}

[I think because of the problem of the administration, they are all trying to give a bit, not everything. They are like 'don't bother yourself, just give the students whatever. Why would you exert yourself at work?' And most of them are always absent. All of this because of the hustle and bustle, and no one cares about the other.]

{ translation }

After prompting Amal on the nature of the issue teachers have with the university administration, she reported that the administration is not supporting teachers properly. *'Well, the administration...usually we meet at the beginning of the year to say we are going to do that, and we are going to do that, and maybe one or two times during the year. So, we are left alone here.'* Talib also maintained that *'...The administration, the university doesn't do anything to help the teachers. This is one of the obstacles.'* The participants also added *'This is a terrible thing. Teachers are left alone, and nobody is checking, nobody is helping, and nobody is encouraging. So, that's why even students feel that. There are some classes which there are serious lectures and the others there is nothing.'* Similarly, Talib's account suggests there is a dereliction in the teachers' duties due to the lack of administrative support. Regardless, the participants' account also shows a lack of autonomy which might be the result of a low level of motivation due to the lack of administrative support.

The university administration negligence of the teaching staff concerns about the inadequate working conditions, lack of resource, and low salaries forced teachers to put their own convenience over the learners. Hayam pointed out *'...If they (teachers) are not getting whatever they want from the university, so like it's a way of showing their anger or their dissatisfaction, so they try not to be productive with their learners.'* Hayam, for example, pointed out that teachers are more interested in their personal gains than on students' learning: *'teachers are seldom conscious. For them, it is not the level that has to be higher from one year to another, but they see their personal conditions like for example salary, like the advantages The University may attribute for them.'*

Similar to Hayam, Asma argued that teachers underperform because they join the teaching profession not out of love, but because they need the job.

Like nowadays, many people, they just come into the teaching, let's say profession, not out of passion...they just come here for just a job. And I'm just coming into that classroom. And I'm going like a bunch of people, and they look at me in a weird way. And you just go

and teach them whatever you want or something, or sometimes not even teaching the entire session.

{ Asma }

The absence of accountability in the institution also seems to be reinforcing the phenomenon of teachers' underperformance. Due to the accountability issue within the Algerian HE system of education, many teachers do not do their jobs properly and teach however they please without being held accountable for their actions (Mohammed and Brahim, 2010). In these regards' participant, Talib maintained that *'there is an absence of authority, a pedagogical authority. Nobody is asking for teachers what did you do, what is your course design? What is your innovation? Do you know this? If you don't know you go to training...Nobody! that is why this is the main obstacle.'*

6.8 The unsupportive society

Maximising learning opportunities for learners entails maximising chance for student interaction and engagement with the target language in and outside the classroom. Interacting in the target language outside the classroom might promote the student's development of IC. However, according to both teachers and students accounts, the Algerian society is still not ready yet for the use of the English language outside the classroom. As shown in the excerpts below, students from Focus Group 1 reported that they do not use English outside the classroom because people laugh at them and perceive them as showing off.

Excerpt 10: Focus group one

R: *So, you don't use English outside?*

Ss: *No.*

R: *Why is that?*

S1: *because of habit I think, because of the habit of using Arabic, some feel ashamed of using English, they feel ashamed if they make mistakes.*

S2: *Maybe not afraid to make mistakes, maybe people who see us and hear us talking in English they say they are showing off and so on... society problem.*

S3: *It is a society problem*

S4: *We don't find the right environment to practice like when talk outside, people stare at you or showing off.*

S5: *yes, society.*

S5: *Some of them even laugh. If you speak in a language, they don't understand they laugh at you.*

In line with the students' account, participant Soumia reported that

I always tell my students, in order to excel or to develop your communicative competence in English; you have to speak English even outside the classroom. And I believe it is very difficult. Why? Because people either laugh at them or they think they are showing off. So that's why there is a kind of ideology, society is not that prepared to hear people speak in English outside.

{Soumia }

The participant's account indicates that individuals in Algerian society might ridicule the use of students' use of English outside the classroom. Students' might even be perceived as a show-off. Such a reaction might discourage students from interacting in English outside the classroom. According to the participant's account, the Algerian society is not only against the use of English but also the use of French. The participant reported that *'there are some families who speak exclusively in French, other people look at them scornfully as if they are showing off or they are westernised or something like that. But I personally encourage this, and I don't think it is a very bad idea at all because I encourage languages.'* The Algerian society rejection of the use of French might be because the French language reminds Algerians of the bitter

memories of the French colonialism (Benrabah, 2014). It could also be the case that Algerian individuals are sabotaging the use of French language as a form of resistance to the sabotage of the Arabic language which associated with the language of Coran (Maamri, 2009).

Talib had a different perspective from Soumia. Unlike Soumia, Talib maintained that the use of French in public placed in the Algerian society is a 'natural' phenomenon. *'it is more natural to speak in French in Algeria than in English. People do not turn when they listen to French; it's natural. of course, when they listen to English, I can't say it is unnatural, but it's not habitual.'* The use of the English language is not habitual in the Algerian society because the English language is still being challenged by the presence of the French language (Benrabah, 2014; Le Roux, 2017). In an agreement with Talib's account, a student from *Focus Group 1* argued that *'...we are English students in Algeria, Algeria they speak French and a lot Arabic, English is not spoken anywhere except the classroom.'*

6.9 Closing remarks

In conclusion, Chapter 5 and 6 were designed to present and discuss the findings to provide answers to research questions posed in Chapter 1 Section 1.3. First, the findings established that teachers' and learners' belief and experiences with the notion of IC were experiences based rather than theoretically informed. Second, the data revealed that the unequal power relation in the institution presents a challenge to the operationalisation of the performative element of the notion of IC. Finally, the findings also established several challenges that impede teachers' and learners' use of dialogic interaction in their EFL classroom including, large class size, lack of teachers' autonomy, lack of students' autonomy and many more which will be revisited in the next chapter, the concluding chapter.

Chapter 7: Conclusion

This chapter will state the main conclusions of this small-scale case study which explores Algerian EFL teachers' and learners' perspectives of and experiences with the notion of IC and the challenges associated with the implementation of its performative elements in the context of higher education in Algeria. The study also explored Algerian EFL teachers' and learners' perspectives on the nature of power dynamics and their impact on their classroom practices. The study made use of a qualitative research approach underpinned by a constructivist/interpretivist research paradigm which asserts the reliance upon the participants' views, backgrounds and lived experiences in the study of a phenomenon (Creswell and Creswell, 2017). This helped to derive a deep and nuanced understanding of the notion of IC in the Algerian HE context.

7.1 Main conclusion

The findings of this study demonstrated that teachers in the institution under study do not operate in the classroom in relation to a set of theories. Instead, they seem to rely on their epistemic perspectives shaped by their lived experiences which are informed by various contextual factors, such as large class size, lack of means and administrative support, and inadequate training programs (Kumaravadivelu, 2003; 2001; 2006). This was evident in the fact that many teachers, especially more experienced ones and those who had the opportunity to study abroad, did not pay much attention to the theoretical aspects of foreign language teaching and learning. Instead, they argued that they believe in practice more than theory and demonstrated an unawareness toward the incongruity between EFL theory and practice (See Chapter 5, Section 5.4). Reporting their perspectives and experiences with the notion of IC followed a similar pattern. Teachers' understandings of IC differed according to their own perspectives and experiences, and in certain instances, their perspectives seemed to correspond with the literature.

To exemplify, teachers of literature emphasised the role of reading in the promotion of student's engagement in the classroom by highlighting the interrelatedness of the interaction between the reader and the text, and other interlocutors. Similarly, teachers who considered affective factors such as low self-confidence and shyness as

the main impediment of dialogic interaction emphasised students' ease and the notion of freeing oneself from the fears and anxieties associated with interpersonal interaction. Some emphasised the role of interpersonal relationships among teachers and learners because of their positive interaction experiences when they were EFL learners. Other teachers viewed IC in terms of knowledge transmission because they viewed themselves as knowledge providers.

The findings of this study also show an inconsistency between teachers' beliefs about the nature of EFL interaction and what they said they do in their actual classroom practices due to a number of contextual factors (Borg, 2006; 2018). Despite the different opinions of teachers about the notion of IC, there was a general agreement on the factors that might hinder the operationalisation of its performative elements in the classroom context. The findings revealed that the participants' interactive practices might be affected by social, cultural, political, and institutional dimensions (Young, 2011; Kumaravadivelu; 2006). The most important factor is what is related to the social and the cultural aspect of Algerian society in general and the culture of the educational institution in particular. It has been established that there is a strong correlation between the broader sociocultural context and what happens between teachers and learners inside the classroom (Kumaravadivelu, 2006). The adoption of an authoritarian parenting style that runs through Algerian society has a negative impact on pupils' and students' self-confidence as it represses their freedom of expression (Benadla, 2013; Semmouk, 2005; Mililani, 2017). The view of children as executors of orders seems to obstruct the development of their autonomy which is a vital element in the development of their IC in the classroom, particularly, in initiating speech, managing topics of discussion and asking for clarification (Kumaravadivelu, 2006; Walsh, 2011; 2012).

The evidence gathered in the course of this study suggests that students' lack of autonomy and passive behaviour in the classroom is one of the main impediments to the operationalisation of IC in the Algerian HE education context. However, it would be misleading to attribute students' lack of autonomy to a particular parenting style. The evidence suggests that the Algerian education system conditions learners to be passive across all stages of education, including primary, secondary, high school, and university level. The large class size is contributing to students' passivity, and to the prevalence of the banking model of education across all four stages of education.

Despite the existence of this model all over the world, in Algeria, the banking model is primarily associated with the religion of Islam (Miliani, 2012; Miliani, 2010; Choubane; 2019). The policy of Arabisation, which was launched during the post-colonial era to reinstate the Algerian identity, was mainly motivated by religion as Arabic is the language of Quran and Islam (Maamri, 2009; Benrabah, 2014). This policy led to the revival of old teaching practices rooted in Islamic pedagogy that champions knowledge transmission and rote learning and assigns teachers the privileged and honourable status of the all-wise and all-knowing (Milani, 2012; 2017). The shared cultural belief that assigns a higher status to teachers led to the existence of unequal power relations in the classroom. The evidence gathered in the course of this study suggests that teachers tend to monopolise the classroom talk by lecturing and dictating, which minimised the students' opportunities to interact in the target language. The limited opportunities for interaction in the classroom are one of the leading factors behind students' speaking anxiety and lack of confidence in their conversational abilities. The latter is also fostered by some of the teachers' perception of their learners as deficient communicators. In addition, the evidence also suggests that the Algerian society is not supportive of the use of English outside the classroom context. This presents an impediment to the maximisation of students' engagement with the target language.

It is this tight association with the religion of Algerian people that made the banking model to be firmly established within the Algerian education culture. Therefore, introducing reforms that are based on western philosophies of education that aims to balance the power between teachers and learners in order to promote learners' autonomy seems only to threaten established practices in Algerian educational culture (Milani, 2017). The unequal power relations are preserved by decision-makers who dismiss teachers' initiatives to improve their classroom interaction experiences with their students by establishing equality. The breaking of the power barrier is viewed as a threat to the educational culture. The failure of the communicative approach and the level of resistance that accompanied the implementation of the LMD system in the context of higher education in Algeria are prime examples of the powerful impact of the banking model of education (Foucault, 1982).

The application of a pedagogy based on western models such as the LMD led to the creation of a conflict between two distinct pedagogies within the institution, Islamic pedagogy and western pedagogy. It has also led to a conflict between teachers who are in favour of western pedagogy and those who are not. Teachers who resist the application of the LMD system pedagogy are subject to surveillance by conforming colleagues. This system of surveillance led to dispersion in collegial relationships, which resulted in the lack of collaboration between teachers.

Students' development of autonomy in the Algerian higher education context is also hampered by the failure to implement key pedagogical canons of the LMD system such as the use of tutorials where teachers offer support to students during their freshman year. This pedagogical procedure is not being applied due to shortage of staff which is a consequence of the rapid increase in the student population, that is, the massification that was discussed in Chapter 2. The shortage of teaching staff also had an impact on the students' supervision in bachelor and master's degree theses. Teachers were obliged to supervise many students, and this had an impact on the quality of research output. The lack of adequate library facilities and ICT equipment also constitutes a hurdle to the development of students' autonomy.

Another important factor that affected student development of autonomy and had a negative impact on their engagement in the classroom is the lack of autonomy in many teachers. The evidence suggests that teachers lack autonomy because they were also enculturated within the same educational system that promotes the banking model of education. Many teachers demonstrated a dependency on a higher power, such as the university administration and ministry of higher education in resolving issues that are within their abilities such as generating a feasible syllabus and improving their teaching practices. Notably, the teachers' reliance on a syllabus that is the remnant of the old system had a remarkable influence on the time allocated for students' interaction due to the teachers' preoccupation with completing an overloaded syllabus on time. Another reason behind the lack of autonomy in many teachers is the fact that although the philosophy underpinning the LMD system promotes learners' autonomy, teachers' autonomy is completely neglected within the reform.

The findings also established that there is an inclination from teachers towards the use of a dialogic approach with learners. However, their old teaching habits that are deeply rooted in their psyche, in a way or another, prevail (Benadla, 2013). It is challenging for teachers to change the students' passive behaviour that became so deeply entrenched over the years, especially in the light of the inadequacy of teacher training in the context. The training programs tend to promote the *status quo* through the transmission of pre-sequenced theoretical knowledge that has little to do with the particularity of the Algerian sociocultural context and the challenges that threaten the quality of Algerian HE education, namely the unequal power relations in the classroom and the prevalence of the banking model of education. Besides, the evidence suggests that teachers are not adequately supported by the university administration and the negligence of their legitimate concerns, which has affected teachers' morale and self-efficacy.

This research also showed that the quality of student-teacher relations, especially between more experienced teachers and students, is compromised due to the authoritarian behaviour of some of these teachers and their lack of respect to their students (Miliani, 2017). Some of the teachers in the study did not consider their students' views and limited students' opportunities to express themselves. In some cases, this resulted in some students resorting to silence and passivity in the classroom as a form of resistance to the teachers' authoritarian behaviour.

On the note of surveillance, the findings also established that the lack of accountability in Algerian HE affected learner's engagement and participation in the classroom. The lack of accountability resulted in some teachers abusing their authority and behaving unethically, for example, by not adhering to the time allocated for teaching sessions. In addition, the absence of accountability reinforced teacher's reliance on old practices and resistance to educational reforms.

The economy of Algeria also seems to have an impact on the quality of HE education (Rose, 2015; Benziane, 2004). The evidence suggests that many teachers underperform due to the belief that the low salaries they receive do not reflect the effort they make in the classroom. The low salaries paired with the bad working conditions such as lack of means, as well as the lack of administrative support (see Chapter 6, Sections, 6.7) are leading factors behind teachers' underperformance in

the institution. Students' passive behaviour in the classroom can also be attributed to the disconnection between HE institution and local labour market conditions, which are characterised by high youth unemployment rates. A broad socio-political awareness of these inauspicious conditions is engraved into the minds of the students.

It is also essential to recognise the impact of Algerian language policy, which is highly influenced by neoliberal globalisation (Mami, 2013; Bellalem 2012). The promotion of the English language with the vision to expand the horizons of Algeria's economy is a good initiative; however, it comes with its downside. English language teaching and learning became tightly associated with linguistic instrumentalism which takes away the fun and aesthetic nature of language teaching and learning due to Western EFL imposition (Ennsner-Kananen et al., 2017). Students will unwillingly find themselves studying the English language not out of interest in the subject but due to the market opportunities it is perceived to offer, despite the dearth of employment opportunities referred to above. This situation seems to have had an impact on their level of motivation and engagement in the classroom. This language policy seems to have led to an increase in the number students within the English language classrooms. On average, a class of 30 students in the third year of study, that was the focus of this research, was not uncommon in the institution. The large class sizes reinforced teachers' reliance on old teaching methods. Consequently, the students' opportunities to ameliorate their conversational skills were minimised.

To summarise, the notion of IC presents an interesting philosophy that corresponds with pedagogies of freedom and emancipation, namely maximising learning opportunities and promoting dialogic interaction in the classroom. The application of this philosophy on the Algerian higher education context has the potential to improve the quality of EFL teaching and learning by promoting students' autonomy, creating a collaborative and supportive teaching and learning environment, promoting critical thinking and creativity. However, the application of IC in the Algerian HE context is still a challenging endeavour. Many of the principles underpinning the notion are not compatible with Algerian sociocultural context, especially the hierarchical power dynamics in the institution and in society at large, lack of means, and inadequate institutional governance (see Chapter 6). Nevertheless, if the notion of IC is going to be applied in the Algerian HE context, several factors need to be considered, and a series of changes need to take place.

7.2 Research implications and recommendations

This thesis foregrounded Algerian teachers' and learners' perspectives of IC, and their perception of the challenges they face in implementing this notion in an Algerian HE institution. The findings of this study have several implications for all stakeholders, including policymakers, higher education institutions in Algeria, administrative staff, teachers, learners, and parents. The findings are not meant to blame any of the stakeholders, nor to show who is more responsible than the other for the unsatisfactory state of the HE institutions in Algeria. Instead, the aim is to promote the idea that education is a shared commitment. A shared commitment that begins by learning to negotiate rather than to impose, to be autonomous and at the same time to recognise the energy togetherness, cooperation, and collaboration create and to thrive on it. These values coalesce in the notion of IC, broadly understood.

7.2.1 Implications for policymakers

The ministry of higher education and policymakers should consider teachers' perspectives about the implantation of new reforms because they are the ones who are in the terrain and dealing with day-to-day challenges with learning, learners, and contextual limitations and opportunities. Policymakers should proceed with extreme caution with the implementation of any western-based theory or reforms and carefully consider the contextual particularities which this study highlighted. Policymakers need to recognise the difference between viewing of globalisation as a phenomenon to undergo, and a phenomenon to live with or in (Miliani, 2010). The former view promotes imitation, while the latter promotes creation and innovation.

It is perhaps time to acknowledge that the Algerian education system has been subject to enough imitation, and been over-exposed to the principles of CBA, CLT, and LMD. The system of education is in desperate need for stability (ibid). The achievement of stability should come from the inside out by promoting teachers' autonomy and supporting them with training that helps them to overcome their day-to-day challenges rather than equipping them to maintain the *status quo*. Stability can be achieved by decreasing employment among young people in Algeria by connecting HE institutions with the labour market, that is, ensuring the HE institution are equipping learners with the skills that are pertinent to the needs of corporations and

public administrations. Enhanced employment opportunities post-university might boost students' engagement and motivation in the classroom. Policymakers should recognise the damaging effect of the banking model of education and promote dialogic interaction for EFL teaching and learning in particular and for teaching and learning in general. To do this, policymakers should be willing to create space with teachers, learners, and administrators for negotiation and dialogue and work cooperatively with them for bettering education.

7.2.2 Implications for administrators

Administrators of higher education institutions in Algeria should be aware that the quality of their interaction and relationship with teachers and students has a notable impact on the quality of teaching, learning, and students' achievements. Administrators should listen to teachers and students' concerns and attempt to address them within the means available. It is recommended that teachers, students, administration staff, and other responsible parties put their differences aside and prioritise teaching, learning, and learners' achievements. There should be willingness from all parties to reinstate relationships based on love for one another, mutual trust, honesty, and cooperation. This could be achieved by organizing social events, where teachers, learners, school administrators, and senior staff of the university meet and discuss their concerns and possible ways to resolve them in an informal way.

7.2.3 Implications for teachers

Based on the findings of this thesis, teachers' domination of the classroom talk constitutes one of the main impediments to the implementation of IC in the context. Therefore, teachers are advised to reduce their talk time in the classroom and to offer more space for students to interact. To do this, they should eliminate the power barrier and seriously consider bonding with the students at the interpersonal level through dialogue. This will assist the teachers in gaining more understanding of the issues the students face with their leaning or otherwise, and help them to determine how they might intervene to enhance students' motivation to learn and to partake in classroom discussion.

Teachers should also remain vigilant to what is happening in the classroom and use classroom research such as diaries and journals to collect data on students' needs and

wants and work cooperatively with other teachers on how to address them. They are also advised to step away from the focus on the accuracy of pronunciation and grammar and consider promoting fluency by appreciating students' ideas. To do so, teachers should become less reliant on the use of handouts and consider interacting with students and building the lesson cooperatively.

According to the findings of this thesis, time limitation was also an issue that threatens the quality of interaction in the classroom. Teachers, therefore, should meet with senior members of staff to discuss a syllabus that is feasible rather than depending on the old syllabus of the classical system. Teachers are also advised not to treat the syllabus as a blueprint that needs to be meticulously applied. Instead, they should be more flexible with the syllabus to address students' differing wants and needs.

Teachers are also advised to refrain from being controlling and authoritarian, and treat students with respect, and carefully recognise the implications of their actions on their relationships with their students and students' achievements and motivation.

7.2.4 Implications for students

Students should understand that they form an integral part of the teaching process and that their active engagement in the classroom could make a considerable difference in the development of their discursive practices. To achieve this, students should be autonomous. For example, they should prepare their lessons, and do the necessary reading before class to be able to participate. This would facilitate both the teaching process and lead to the emergence of new ideas and maximise their learning opportunities. Students should also initiate talk, ask for clarifications when they do not understand. They should overcome their fear of making mistakes and view mistakes as part of the process of learning.

Students should also be patient with their teachers and refrain from correcting them constantly. Not every error or mistake should be corrected on the spot. Pointing out a mistake or an error made by the teacher, such as mispronounced or misplaced word could be beneficial for the whole class. However, if a student felt the need to correct or point out a mistake, it is better to do it in a non-confrontational way as correcting teachers in public might be off-putting and threatening.

7.3 Limitations

Although this study achieved its objectives and outlined a range of significant conclusions, it is important to address several shortcomings and limitations.

The first limitation in respect of the present study is time constraints. More time could have been advantageous in using more research tools. Even though teachers' beliefs play a central role in the understanding classroom practices, combining interviews with classroom observation could have been useful to demonstrate how teachers' perspectives about IC play out in their actual classroom practices. More time could also allow for a longitudinal study of teachers' beliefs to see how their beliefs about IC change over time.

Another limitation that should be addressed concerns the sampling of the study. Although the teachers' sample was representative to the overall population, the study could have made use of a larger sample. For example, it could be advantageous to interview teachers from multiple institutions, as well as other stakeholders such as senior university managers, parents, and even ministry representatives. This would have generated a more holistic and more complex perspective on the nature of the phenomenon of IC in the Algerian HE.

In respect of the students' sample, this study could have made use of conducting a focus group with students across all graduate-level and from different institutions, including 1st year and 2nd-year students. This would allow uncovering the different challenges students face across different levels while operationalising the performative element of IC.

7.4 Future research trajectory

After addressing the limitation of this study, it is important to point to potential future research.

Future research investigating the notion of interactional competence in the Algerian HE context or another second and foreign language context should consider using larger samples and include a longitudinal dimension.

It would be advantageous for future research investigating the notion IC in the Algerian context or other second and foreign language contexts via the lens of the participants' perspectives to consider using classroom observation along with interviews. This would allow cross-matching of participants' beliefs with their actual classroom practices.

Evidence from this research suggests that Algerian parenting styles have an impact on pupils' and students' engagement in the classroom. Therefore, it would be worthwhile to conduct further research to explore the nature of Algerian parenting styles in more depth and its implication on the promotion of autonomous learning in the context.

Further research is needed on the notion of IC to explore if there are any differences and similarities in the challenges pupils and students face in the development of IC across the different stage of education.

It would also be interesting to conduct a cross-cultural comparative study on the notion of IC. This could be investigated by interviewing teachers and learners from different sociocultural contexts, for example, from Algeria and the UK. This would provide an in-depth understanding of how the beliefs of different individuals from different sociocultural contexts affect classroom interactive practices. It would also be beneficial for the study if the interviews are paired with classroom observation to cross match between the participant beliefs and classroom practices, as well as to compare the extent to which the participants' beliefs and practices correlate in both sociocultural contexts.

Finally, there are a couple of findings that emerged from the in-depth review of the literature and have not been explored within this thesis. The first finding is that the notion of teacher autonomy is under-researched or completely absent within the framework of LMD system reforms. Therefore, additional research is required to get a deep understanding of the reasons why teachers' autonomy has received scant attention. The second finding is that the speaking dimension within the framework of IC is overemphasised. Future research on IC should consider exploring the impact of the non-verbal dimension of the participants' development of IC.

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Appendices

Appendix A- Interview Schedule (teachers)

I. The opening

A-Establishing rapport: [shake hands], Hello, my name is Saif Eddine, a Ph.D. researcher from the school of education at the university of the west of Scotland. I thought it would be a good idea to interview you. First, I would like to thank you for taking time from your busy schedule to take part in this project.

B-Purpose: I would like to ask you some question in relation your perspectives, beliefs, and experience regarding classroom interactional competence. I believe you have a good idea of what this project is about, right?

C- (Motivation) well, just to refresh your mind, I am interested in classroom interaction, particularly in the context of EFL teaching in Algeria

D- Timeline and interview: I would like to inform you that this interview is expected to take up to 45 minutes' maximum. Moreover, this interview is being recorded for the sake data transcription and analysis. Any information that you are going to provide is going be strictly confidential and secured. Are you available to respond to some questions?

II. Body

(Transition) Great, thank you, let me begin by asking you

A-How long have been teaching here?

B-What subject/subjects that you are teaching?

C-Have you taught English anywhere else?

If yes, where, and for how long?

D-Can you tell me about how you were prepared for your current role? (*Probe for training, study abroad, short courses, etc*)

E- Did you receive any specific training? If so, what was the focus?

F-What are your views on any training you received?

G-Does this training session include any aspect of how to interact with students?

H-Do you think the inclusion of such training, i.e., classroom interaction, is salient?

If yes, why?

1-Beliefs/perspectives

A-In your view, what are the qualities and competences that make good teacher of EFL?

B-Have you heard of interactional competence?

If yes, what does this notion mean to you?

Are there any specific features that characterize interactional competence in our context?

If yes, in your views, what are the features of an interactionally competent classroom in the Algerian context?

2-Experiences

(Now we are going to focus on both your personal experiences, and your experience with schooling and instruction in relation to classroom interactional competence).

2.1. As a former student and currently as a teacher

2.1.1. The teacher's former experiences as a student

A-(Transition) considering the fact that you were an English learner, how would describe your former classroom interaction experience as a learner?

B-Can you tell me something about how your teacher managed interaction in the classroom?

D-Did teacher give you enough space to express your thoughts, ideas etc...?
(*Probing on opportunities for learners to interact in the classroom setting.*) E-
What do you think of his/her feedback on your contributions?

F-If I ask you, what thing you would have liked to change with regards to classroom interaction, what would it be?

G-What are the challenges that might impede classroom interactional competence at that time?

H-Now, as a teacher what do you think of the students' way of interaction?

I-How do you give space to students to express their thoughts, ideas and the like?
How do you respond to their contribution?

G-Do you think that your past experience with your former teachers shaped the way you manage interaction today?

If yes, How? If No, why not?

2.1.2. The teacher experiences

A-How would you describe your teaching experience here?

B-Do the working conditions help you to give your best?

If no, what are the obstacles?

(Transition)Now moving on to something more specifically related to classroom interactional competence.

D-How would you describe your interaction with students?

E-How is the level of participation in your classroom?

F-What are the challenges that impede our students from being interactionally competent?

G-What are the challenges that are specific to teachers that might impede them from being interactionally competent?

3-Moving on to something more related to your Experience with formal knowledge of classroom interactional competence

A-What experiences with the formal knowledge that you have had in relation to classroom interactional competence?

B-Do you implement this knowledge in your classes?

C-What are your thoughts on the level implementation of this knowledge in your classrooms?

D-What are the challenges that you can think of that might be impeding the proper implementation of this knowledge?

4-Perspectives on the improvement of classroom interactional competence in the context

In your views, how can we improve classroom interaction experience in the context? **III. Closing**

A-(Gratitude) Thank you so much for taking part in this research. I really appreciate the time you took for this interview. Is there anything else that you can think of that would be of helpful in relation to classroom interactional competence that you can provide me with?

B- (Maintaining rapport) thank you so much again. I think I have all the information I need. Would it be okay to give you a call, or to get in touch with you via email in case I have further questions?

C-(Ending) I must say I am very honoured that have had the opportunity to interview you. [Handshake] Thanks again.

Appendix-B- Focus Group topic guide (students)

I-Introduction: Hello my name is Saif Eddine, I am a PhD research interested in foreign language classroom communication and interaction. How is everybody doing today?

<Perfect>

a) Purpose of the focus group discussion

I'm very grateful to you all for sparing time to talk about your views on classroom interactional competence. Today I want to concentrate on discussing this notion of CIC, your classroom interaction experiences as well as we will shed lights on the contextual factors that impede the implementation of such notion in the context. There are no right or wrong opinions, I would like you to feel comfortable saying what you really think and how you really feel.

b) statement of confidentiality:

Opinions expressed will be treated in confidence among the researcher and the research supervisory team for the purpose of investigating learners' perspectives on classroom interactional competence, and in the production of the research project report. All responses will remain anonymous. I would also like to draw your attention that this focus group session will be recorded for aforementioned purposes.

c) Warm up questions:

How long have you been studying here at this university?

What is the average time a particular class/session usually take?

What is the average number of students per class?

d) Opening:

We all know the importance of interaction in learning, so I would like to start of this session with the following question:

How would you describe the quality of interaction in your classroom room? To clarify, this involves both your interaction with your teachers as well as with your peers (classmates).

*Can you also please tell me about your past experiences of classroom interaction? **II-Body***

1-Learning opportunities creation

How is the level of participation in the classroom? / Do students participate in the classroom?

Does your teacher give you enough opportunities to participate in the classroom?

Are you aware of the ways that your teachers create those learning opportunities?

If so, how do your teachers create those learning opportunities?

What are your views on the amount of time that your teachers spend talking in the classroom?

2-Extending wait time:

Do your teachers give you enough time to think in order to respond to questions and participate in discussions?

3-Clarification requests:

When you do not understand something either from your teachers or from your classmates, how often do you ask for clarification?

4-Shaping contributions

This happens when you take part in a discussion, participate in the classroom and/or answer a question

Do your teachers shape (rephrase) your contributions in a discussion?

Do you shape (rephrase) you classmates' contributions in a discussion?

5-Feedback:

-How would you describe your teachers' feedback to your contributions?

Probe on both Content feedback and feedback on the form **6-Turn taking:**

How turn taking is usually orchestrated in the classroom?

Do the teachers select/ distribute turns?

Do you or your classmates initiate turns? (Students turn initiation is commonly demonstrated by Scottish students)

7-Teachers' use of language

Tell me about your teachers' use of language. Do you think that the teachers use of language encourage you to interact and partake in discussions?

8-Meaning negotiation

Is it common that you negotiate meaning in the classroom with both your teachers and your classmates? (Do you usually co-construct or build meaning/understanding together in the classroom?)

9-Classroom interactional competence:

Have you ever heard of the notion of classroom interactional competence?

If yes,

Could you please tell me what that means?

If not, from your own perspectives, what do you think classroom Interactional competence mean?

10-Contextual factors:

Can you think of any factors, this involves (for example), classroom, the instruction (university), society as whole, that impede you from interacting and partaking in discussions competently, sharing your opinions as well as negotiating meaning?

10-Perspectives on the improvement of CIC in the context

In your views, how can we improve classroom interaction experience in the context?

III-Closing:

-(Gratitude) Thank you so much for taking part in this research. I really appreciate the time you took for this interview. Is there anything else that might be of relevance to what we have already been discussing that you would like to say something about? In case you thought of anything else that might be of relevant, please do not hesitate to drop me an email provided both in your consent form and information sheet?

-(Ending) I must say I am very honoured that have had the opportunity to interview you. [Handshake all of the participants] Thanks again.

Appendix C- Participant Information Sheet (teachers and students)

Participant Information Sheet for teachers

School of Education

Title of study:

Conceptualizing classroom interactional
competence: the case of Algeria

Introduction

This research project is run by Saif Eddine Necib, PhD student in the School of Education, University of the West of Scotland.

What is the purpose of this investigation?

This dissertation centres on the notion of classroom interactional competence in English as Foreign Language (EFL) classrooms, with specific reference to the Algerian context. It will explore teachers' and learners' perspectives, beliefs, and experiences, which I believe play a salient role in shaping their classroom practices. Previous research in this area did not pay enough attention to teachers' perspectives on classroom interactional competence. The empirical element of the research will be conducted at Badji-Mokhtar University of Annaba, where in-depth, semi-structured interviews with Algerian EFL teachers and focus group interviews with EFL learners will be conducted. The interviews will be audio-recorded and transcribed for analysis using a thematic coding approach. The purpose of this study is five-fold. First, to develop a deeper understanding of classroom interactional competence in the Algerian higher education context. Second, to explore Algerian EFL teachers' and learners' perspectives, beliefs and experience regarding the aforementioned notion. Third, to explore Algerian EFL

teachers' shared beliefs vis-à-vis classroom interactional competence. Fourth, to uncover challenges and contextual features, and the teachers' and learners' perception of them, which might impede interactional competence in the Algerian EFL classrooms. Finally, to make a contribution to knowledge on classroom discourse, particularly on the phenomenon of classroom interactional competence.

The ultimate aim of the study is to enhance the quality of EFL in the Algerian context, with a specific emphasis on developing teachers' interactional competence.

Do you have to take part?

Taking part is entirely voluntary and participants who do choose to become involved will have the right to withdraw up until the data analysis stage, without penalty.

What will you do in the project?

You will be asked to take part in a semi-structured interview lasting approx. 30 to 45 minutes. You will have the opportunity to express your views on classroom interactional competence and to use your own terms to express your experiences, beliefs in respect of this. Anything that will be discussed between you and the researcher is strictly confidential and there will be no direct reference to any of the participants in either the analysis and/or on the report of the findings.

Why have you been invited to take part?

You have been invited to take part in this research as you are an EFL teacher at an Algerian higher education institute. This study looks at the conceptualisation of classroom interactional competence from the teachers' perspectives. Also, being part of the Algerian sociocultural context help in the investigation of this notion.

What are the potential risks to you in taking part?

Participation will involve participation in a semi-structured interview with the researcher on a topic of mutual professional interest. I can guarantee that there

are no potential risks of you taking part in this research. The confidentiality and anonymity of the research participants are guaranteed.

What happens to the information in the project?

Information supplied by participants will be entirely confidential and all activity will be undertaken anonymously. All data will be securely stored within the university.

Thank you for reading this information – please ask any questions if you are unsure about what is written here.

What happens next?

If you are happy to be involved in the project, you will be asked to sign a consent form to confirm this. Thank you very much in advance for taking time from your busy schedule to participate in this project.

Once the project is complete, you will be given a short-written report of its findings, with the option of further verbal communication.

This investigation was granted ethical approval by the School of Education Ethics Committee.

If you have any questions/concerns, during or after the investigation, or wish to contact an independent person to whom any questions may be directed or further information may be sought from my supervisor:

Dr Anne Pirrie

Reader, School of Education

University of the West of Scotland

Email:

Personal details withheld.

Researcher Contact Details:

Saif Eddine Necib

Personal details withheld.

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Scotland, UK

Email: [REDACTED]

Participant Information Sheet for students

School of Education

Title of study:

Conceptualizing classroom interactional
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Introduction

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You have been invited to take part in this research as you are an EFL learner at an Algerian higher education institute. This study looks at the conceptualisation of classroom interactional competence from the teachers' perspectives. Also, being part of the Algerian sociocultural context help in the investigation of this notion.

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Participation will involve participation in a semi-structured focus group interview with the researcher on a topic of mutual professional interest. I can guarantee that there are no potential risks of you taking part in this research. The confidentiality and anonymity of the research participants are guaranteed.

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Thank you for reading this information – please ask any questions if you are unsure about what is written here.

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If you are happy to be involved in the project, you will be asked to sign a consent form to confirm this. Thank you very much in advance for taking time from your busy schedule to participate in this project.

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Reader, School of Education

Personal details withheld.

University of the West of Scotland

Email : [REDACTED]

Researcher Contact Details:

Saif Eddine Necib

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Appendix D- Consent forms (teachers and students)

Teachers' Consent Form

School of Education

Title of study:

Conceptualizing Classroom interactional competence:

the case of Algeria

-I confirm that I have read and understood the information sheet for the above project and the researcher has answered any queries to my satisfaction.

-I understand that my participation is voluntary and that I am free to withdraw from the project up until the beginning of the data analysis, without having to give a reason and without any consequences.

-I understand that any information recorded in the investigation will remain confidential and no information that identifies me will be made publicly available.

-I agree / do not agree (delete as applicable) to take part in the above study.

(PRINT NAME)	Hereby agree to take part in the above project
Signature of participant	Date

Students' Consent Form

School of Education

Title of study

Conceptualizing Classroom interactional competence:
the case of Algeria

- I confirm that I have read and understood the information sheet for the above project and the researcher has answered any queries to my satisfaction.
- I understand that my participation is voluntary and that I am free to withdraw from the project up until the beginning of the data analysis, without having to give a reason and without any consequences.
- I understand that any information recorded in the investigation will remain confidential and no information that identifies me will be made publicly available.
- I agree / do not agree (delete as applicable) to take part in the above study.

(PRINT NAME)	Hereby agree to take part in the above project
Signature of participant	Date

